

VOC Collections: Scoping Report

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The purpose of this document is to report on the breadth of *Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie* (VOC/[Dutch] United East India Company) collection material world-wide (and on the world-wide-web). This considers the objects, documents and data currently held and/or communicated relevant or related to the VOC which operated 1602–1799. This includes reference to individual projects and interfaces that use or create data from material collections. Inclusion in this scoping report is not an endorsement of collectors and collections, or any related activities and methodologies.

This report is split into four sections:

- 1) Scoping Summary.
- 2) What is a 'VOC Collection'.
- 3) Overview of Collections/Institutions.
- 4) Overview of Projects and Resources.

In compiling this document, primary attention was given to 'shipwreck' collections. This has the aim to identify resources that can be utilised or potentially emerge from existing VOC collections for the wider aims of the *Mobilising Dutch East India Collections for New Global Stories* (MOB-VOC) project (ARC LP210300960): in particular, to contextualise the Australian collections and facilitate new interpretations of and interactions with that material.

This scoping exercise identified that VOC material is incredibly dispersed and has become part of exceedingly diverse institutional and private collections. This report has aimed to highlight those aspects of the institutions or collections, or associated activities, that can inspire potential integrations and connections, and therefore facilitate the production of new perspectives. Hopefully this report can also create exposure for these collections and stimulate their further research.

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Figure 1. Distribution of VOC shipwrecks in collections (red), and four intra-Asian cargo shipwrecks (black). Approximate distribution of VOC-shipwrecks in total indicated in white. Source data: Manders et al. 2022; *Stepping Stones of Maritime History (MaSS)*. Base map: ESRI Oceanographic. Compiled: Rebecca Repper.

Scoping Summary

The 78 institutions holding VOC shipwreck material identified by this study have material from 50 identified VOC ships (Figure 1; Table 1). Four intra-Asian shipwrecks are also included. This is because institutions often presented material from these vessels in association with the VOC as they are thought to have been carrying cargo for VOC trade.

Predominantly these collections are a result of the rapid development of modern maritime archaeology and salvage of shipwrecks from the mid-twentieth century. These activities resulted in acquisition of VOC underwater cultural heritage (UCH) through three main pathways:

- Archaeological investigation and deposit at a state collecting authority.
- Salvage agreement with percentage of artefacts raised surrendered to nominated institution and/or state partner (with varying success).
- Purchase of material at auction or other private purchase.

Much VOC shipwreck material has entered personal/private collections which are rarely described publicly and are therefore grossly underrepresented in this report.

Another method of collecting is of note – collection at a site by private persons or groups. Material collected in this way has entered institutional collections through two main pathways:

- Material collected as relics or curios since the 19th century. Many of these have come to be donated/acquired by institutions. For example, items from the Abrolhos collected on the third expedition of *The Beagle* are now located in the WA Museum (ZW5636 and ZW 5637,

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originally given to the Nicholson Museum, Sydney), Greenwich Maritime Museum (GGG0222-224) and Royal Armoury (XIX.238).

- Seizure or surrender (sometimes in the form of donation) of looted/illegally salvaged material. For example, material seized by Kementerian Kelautan dan Perikanan (Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, Indonesia), the looted material from *Risdam* now held by Muzium Negara, and items surrendered under a nationwide amnesty in Australia 1 May 1993-31 March 1994.

The collections that hold shipwreck material are highly dispersed – across at least 22 countries and territories (Figure 2). Collections are concentrated in Australia, South Africa, the U.K. and the Netherlands. This generally matches the concentrations of known investigated shipwrecks, with the exception of Southeast Asia.

Material that has travelled furthest or is most dispersed is that salvaged and/or auctioned. This is typified by the distribution of material from the wreck of *Geldermalsen* (Table 1). The report captures only a very partial picture of this trend due to the limited extent of material known to be held in private collections.

The form or make up of the collections are diverse, ranging across:

- Those resulting from dedicated excavation, monitoring and study of particular wrecks. These include, for example, WA Museum, Maritime Museum Galle Fort, Shetland Museum and Archives, Rijkscollectie Scheepsarcheologie (Batavialand/Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed), and Musée National de la Marine.
- Partial or representative collections of shipwreck material or maritime heritage. These include, for example, Rijksmuseum, Iziko Museums of South Africa, National History Museum of Mauritius, Kerry Stokes Collection, and Hastings Shipwreck Museum.
- Sentimental, trophy or specialist collections, which concentrate on material of a particular ‘type’ or subject. These include:
 - ‘Treasure’, such as Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum, Wrakkenmuseum and Shipwreck Treasure Museum.
 - ‘Discovery’, such as Silentworld Foundation.

Figure 2. Distribution of collecting institutions with VOC shipwreck material identified in this report. Base map: ESRI Oceanographic. Compiled: Rebecca Repper.

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- Art or ceramic collections, such as Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum, Art Gallery of Greater Victoria, Keramiekmuseum Princessehof, Groninger Museum and Musée Guimet.
- Numismatic collections, such as Monnaie de Paris, De Nederlandsche Bank, The British Museum and University of Oslo Coin Cabinet.
- Local collections with representative samples of the local wreck. These include, for example, Isles of Scilly Museum, Museum of Saint Helena, Sierra Leone National Museum, and Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum.

Online, public and freely available collection databases, such as the WA Museum Maritime Archaeology Collections, are rare. Only 43 of the identified 78 institutions have some kind of collection portal or interface, and in some instances, the material is not yet documented and/or available (e.g. the *Akerendam* (1725) material at the Universitetet i Oslo). The reality is that despite publicly accessible item or collection records increasing for cultural heritage collections, many of the collections identified by this scoping report – especially those outside of Europe – do not have description available online. Moreover, the level of description that does exist is highly variable. Consulting publications or contacting institutions and individuals directly has been necessary (but sadly not always successful) to positively identify instances and scopes of collections.

The factors hampering this collection scoping can be summarised as follows.

Firstly, identifying 'VOC' collections is difficult due to the many ways these collections are described. This diversity can reflect the priorities of the institutions. For example, rather than associate the object with the 'VOC', collections may reference an object to an individual maker, collector, style, period or place – particularly evident in art and reference collections. Moreover, the reference to the VOC may be implied through other means, such as by referring to the item as 'Dutch', from a 'Dutch East Indiaman' or 'Retourschip', or specifically reference the name of the wreck. The reference to a wreck or place may also vary due to spelling (e.g. 'Vliegende Hart' instead of *Vliegende Hert*), translation (e.g. 'Gilt Dragon' instead of *Vergulde Draak*), or how the salvage was marketed (e.g. 'Nanking Cargo' instead of *Geldermalsen*).¹

Secondly, due to the extent of activity of the VOC, collections are held across multiple countries and described in multiple languages. While efforts have been made to look for collections across the breadth of the former VOC activity, there are undoubtedly many collections that have been missed due to differences in language and expression. Others may have been missed due to differing capacities and priorities of institutions when communicating their collections.

Lastly, there is a large amount of VOC shipwreck material that has become dispersed through salvage, auction, re-sale and inheritance. As already mentioned, this has resulted in many items becoming part of private collections. Private collections are very rarely fully described or publicly searchable (exceptions noted in this report include Silentworld and Ottema-Kingma Stichting). Moreover, this activity can result in collection items becoming disassociated from their provenance information, for example, the Michael Abbott Collection of Trade Ceramics in Australia.

To assist in ameliorating these gaps and add to this document, please email rebecca.repper@uwa.edu.au.

¹ This report will prioritise ship naming used by the Stepping Stones of Maritime History (MaSS) project which is an easily accessible public resource: <https://mass.cultureelerfgoed.nl/>.

Table 1. Summary of known/located VOC-shipwrecks and the collections/institutions where their artefacts are known to be held. Ship names and dates follow *Stepping Stones of Maritime History (MaSS)*.

Ship Name	Wrecking	Institutions where collections known to be held
Nassau	1606	Lukut Museum (Malaysia), Muzium Negara (Malaysia)
Middelburg	1606	[None known]
Mauritius	1609	Musée Guimet, Musée National de la Marine (France)
Witte Leeuw	1613	Amsterdam Museum, The British Museum, Groninger Museum, Keramiekmuseum Princessehof, Macau Museum, Maritiem Museum Rotterdam, Musée Guimet, Museum of St Helena, Ottema-Kingma Stichting, Rijksmuseum, Scheepvaart Museum, Shipwreck Treasure Museum, Wereld Museum
Banda	1615	Frederik Hendrik Museum, Mauritius Commercial Bank/Blue Penny Museum, Mauritius National History Museum, Musée Guimet, Scheepvaart Museum
Geünieerde Provinciën	1615	[Note: Mauritius National History Museum]
Hert [?]	1622	[None known]
Kampen	1627	The British Museum, Martin Woodward (Maritime Archaeology Trust), Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Shipwreck Treasure Museum, Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum
Batavia	1629	Australian National Maritime Museum, Kerry Stokes Collection, Powerhouse Museum, Silentworld Foundation, WA Museum
Rob [BZN3]	1640	Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Rijkscollectie Scheepsarcheologie (Batavialand/Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed), Stichting Texels Museum
Haarlem [Nieuw Haarlem] [?]	1647	The British Museum
Lastdrager	1653	Kerry Stokes Collection, Maritiem Museum Rotterdam, Scheepvaart Museum
Vergulde Draak [Vergulde Draeck]	1656	Australian National Maritime Museum, Kerry Stokes Collection, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Powerhouse Museum, Silentworld Foundation, South Australian Maritime Museum (History Trust of South Australia), WA Museum
Avondster	1659	Maritime Archaeology Museum (Galle, Sri Lanka)
Hercules	1661	Maritime Archaeology Museum (Galle, Sri Lanka)
Kennemerland	1664	Shetland Museum and Archives
Zeepaard	1665	Irish Archaeological Collection (National Museum of Ireland)
Wapen van Amsterdam	1667	Skógar Museum
Prinses Maria	1686	Amsterdam Museum, Hastings' Shipwreck Museum, Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Martin Woodward (Maritime Archaeology Trust), Museon Omniversum, Rijksmuseum, Scheepvaart Museum
Waddinxveen	1697	The British Museum, Iziko Museums of South Africa

Ship Name	Wrecking	Institutions where collections known to be held
Oosterland	1697	Iziko Museums of South Africa, University of Cape Town Department of Archaeology
Huis te Crayenstein	1698	Iziko Museums of South Africa
Voetboog [?]	1700	[None known]
Merestein	1702	Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum, Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Iziko Museums of South Africa, MuseuMAfricA, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Rijksmuseum, Simon's Town Museum
De Liefde	1711	Amsterdam Museum, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Rijksmuseum, Royal Collection UK, Shetland Museum and Archives, Silentworld Foundation
Zuidorp [Zuytdorp]	1712	Australian National Maritime Museum, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), WA Museum
Bennebroek	1713	East London Museum (South Africa), Iziko Museums of South Africa
Loosdrecht	1719	Martin Woodward (Maritime Archaeology Trust Collection)
Schonenberg	1722	Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum
Meteren	1723	South Africa Heritage Resources Agency (SAHRA)
Slot ter Hoge	1724	The British Museum, Casa Colombo – Museu do Porto, Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Monnaie de Paris, Rijksmuseum, Scheepvaart Museum, Shipwreck Treasure Museum,
Akerendam	1725	Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum, Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Universtitet i Oslo Myntkabinettet
Ravesteyn	1726	[None known]
Risdam	1727	Muzium Negara, Malaysia
Zeewijk	1727	Australian National Maritime Museum, Royal Armories UK, Royal Geographical Society South Australia, Royal Museums Greenwich, Silentworld Foundation, WA Museum,
Middenrak	1728	Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum, [Iziko Museums of South Africa]
Adelaar	1728	[None known]
Vliegent Hert [Vliegent Hart]	1735	Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Martin Woodward (Maritime Archaeology Trust), Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Rijksmuseum, Scheepvaart Museum, Zeeuws Archive, Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum
Rodenrijs	1737	[Note: Iziko Museums of South Africa]
Reigersbroek*	1738	Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum
Boot	1738	Rijksmuseum
Rooswijk	1740	National Museum of Singapore, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Rijkscollectie Scheepsarcheologie (Batavialand/Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed), Silentworld Foundation, Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum
De Vis	1740	Hout Bay Museum (South Africa)

Ship Name	Wrecking	Institutions where collections known to be held
Hollandia	1743	Amsterdam Museum, The British Museum, Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Isles of Scilly Museum, Nationale Numismatische Collectie (De Nederlandsche Bank), Rijksmuseum, Scheepvaart Museum, Shipwreck Treasure Museum
Reigersdaal	1747	BayWorld Museum, Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum, Iziko Museums of South Africa, Simon's Town Museum, South Africa Fisheries Museum, South African Naval Museum
Diemermeer	1747	Sierra Leone National Museum
Nieuwerkerk	1748	[None known]
Amsterdam	1749	Amsterdam Museum, Hastings' Shipwreck Museum, Kunstmuseum Den Haag, Rijkscollectie Scheepsarcheologie (Batavialand/Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed), Scheepvaart Museum
Vlissingen	1747	[None known]
Geldermalsen	1752	Art Gallery of Greater Victoria, Asian Civilisations Museum, The British Museum, Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum, Groninger Museum, Keramiekmuseum Princessehof, Kerry Stokes Collection, Museum Joure, Ottema-Kingma Stichting, Shipwreck Treasure Museum, Te Papa Tongarewa, Victoria & Albert Museum, WA Museum, Zeeuws Archive, Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum
Bredenhof	1753	The British Museum, Iziko Museums of South Africa, Nederlands Zilver Museum, Scheepvaart Museum, Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum, Zeeuws Museum
Buitenzorg	1760	Rijkscollectie Scheepsarcheologie (Batavialand/Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed), Scheepvaart Museum
Leimuider	1770	Museus de Cabo Verde, [De Nederlandsche Bank]
Nieuw Rhoon [?] [Civic Centre Ship]	1776	Iziko Museums of South Africa
Woestduin	1779	Zeeuws Maritiem MuZEEum, Zeeuws Museum
Middelburg	1781	Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum, Iziko Museums of South Africa, MuseuMAfrica, Simon's Town Museum
Brederode	1785	Hille van Dieren Collection (Wrakkenmuseum), Iziko Museums of South Africa
Zeelie	1795	Rijksmuseum
[Bình Thuận]**	1608	Kerry Stokes Collection, Vietnam National Museum of History
[Hatcher Junk]**	1646	Art Gallery of South Australia, Asian Civilisations Museum, The British Museum, Groninger Museum Keramiekmuseum Princessehof, Ottema-Kingma Stichting, Rijksmuseum, Wereld Museum
[Vũng Tàu shipwreck]**	1690	Asian Civilisations Museum, Ba Ria - Vung Tau Provincial Museum, Ottema-Kingma Stichting
[Cà Mau Shipwreck]**	1725	The British Museum, Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum, Groninger Museum, Victoria and Albert Museum

* Not listed in Manders et al's *Wrakkentelling (2022)/MaSS*. See *Dutch Asiatic Shipping 7019.4*.

** Not a VOC-ship, but was likely transporting cargo for the VOC market out of Batavia.

[?] Find status/identification uncertain.

Takeaways for MOB-VOC Project

The current diverse landscape, both in terms of types of collections and level of documentation/description, means there is no current prospect for integration/aggregation of itemised collection data for shipwreck material. A standalone pilot project between the WA Museum and RCE/Dutch museum collections might be feasible as these are the more comprehensively documented and available collections. This would not be currently feasible as WA Museum is in the process of transitioning to a new institution-wide CMS, and many of the Netherlands institutions are in the process of transitioning away from Adlib. If attempted, the pilot project methodology could be extended to facilitate exposure and documentation of other collections, such as those held by Iziko Museums, as an ongoing concern.

An integration or communication of international VOC collections at the collection level is more viable and what this scoping report has focused on. This also has the capacity to recognise the places/organisations/activities (e.g. excavation and exhibition) involved with handling and housing VOC collections, and therefore reflect their global and ongoing lives. By communicating where institutions with collections are, we can stimulate interest, and hopefully resourcing for their further research and access. For example, the project could be a platform for the current data on the Iziko collections, and through platforming these collections stimulate further research and interest.

What this scoping exercise has demonstrated is that many individuals and institutions have been working in the VOC space for years, if not decades – especially in the study and use of archival collections. This has resulted in a lot of information regarding sites, collections, exhibitions, events and relevant actors, but this unfortunately in a lot of cases remains unconnected. There is opportunity to aggregate and apply this data to extend the ‘mapping’ of the VOC to the ongoing lives of VOC shipwrecks and shipwreck material, such as to the activities involving these sites and collections (salvage, excavation, monitoring, auction, exhibition), the people involved, and where the collections are currently housed.

Project outcomes need to be conscious of not reproducing existing or current work by other projects: several data projects facilitated through Nationaal Archief, Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed (RCE) and KNAW/Huygens ING (e.g. GLOBALISE, Maritime Careers, and Maritiem Portal), and GIS/mapping projects such as ‘Atlas of Mutual Heritage’, MaSS (RCE) and ‘Global Sea Routes’ (Nodegoat), overlap with the scope of the MOB-VOC project. There are also a number of public run or facing portals in this space that demonstrate a public appetite for engaging with and contributing to research about the VOC: e.g. [Wrecksite](#), [VOCsite](#), and [MAARER](#). The Maritiem Portal is a good example of institutional efforts in the Netherlands to try and bring together information about these collections and the research landscape in one place.

Technological and digital obsolescence is a real risk: an interface or portal, or other online resource, does not guarantee the availability of the research and the data long term, as has been demonstrated by the ‘Towards a New Age of Partnership’ (TANAP) project.

It therefore may be more effective to utilise the existing digital infrastructures, such as Wikidata or MaSS, to acknowledge and link existing resources, and platform the new information and resources produced by the project. This will facilitate connection, engagement and ongoing use of the many VOC collections, both material and digital.

‘VOC Collection’?

The primary purpose of the scoping exercise was to identify VOC shipwreck collections. It quickly became apparent however that the majority of collections do not describe these collections as ‘VOC’. What do we therefore mean by a ‘VOC collection’?

The scope of VOC collections can be considered in three main ways.

1. A traditional custodial perspective: material made directly by or for the VOC, or owned by them, during their existence.
2. A post-custodial network perspective: collections that are indirectly connected to the VOC, such as those owned or used by employees, their families, servants or slaves, or items that depict, describe or critique the VOC’s people, places, ships and activities, both contemporaneously with the VOC and those since.
3. VOC legacy collections: data derived from the information inherent in the first two types of collections, the catalogues, inventories and indexes of those collections, the archives and grey literature that details how those collections have come to be, and modern legislation and policies that govern VOC material and sites.

Notably – shipwreck collections, which are a central interest of the MOB-VOC project, span both the first and second categories, and result in the production of the third. This is because the act of shipwreck creates an assemblage comprised of the items that are directly associated with the VOC (e.g. the ship and its furnishings), the various global commodities traded by the VOC (e.g. kraak porcelain, pepper and silver coins), and the items more directly associated with individuals that were also on the ship (e.g. clothing and contraband). The investigation and documentation of the shipwreck and its artefacts, and laws governing how they can be interacted with, produces the third type of collection. Moreover, interest in or reactions to VOC voyages, shipwrecks and individuals creates new collections of material, such as commemorative stamps and currency (such as those featuring Abel Tasman in the Te Papa Tongarewa collections), or artworks (such as by ceramicist [Diane KW](#) in the Groninger Museum collections).

Interpretation and exhibition continues to rely upon information and research of collections both directly associated with the VOC – such as the VOC archives held at the Nationaal Archief and Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia (ANRI), and less directly, such as the wealth of art that depicts VOC ships, people and places, or examples of the items they traded, such as textiles, or the traces of them from where they were produced, such as kiln sites. The scope of items included in exhibitions and associated publications, such as *In Pursuit of Pepper and Tea* (Jacobs & Nederlands Scheepvaart Museum, 1991) and *Travellers & Traders in the Indian Ocean World* (WA Museum, 2016), are testimony to this.

In this way, items that are not strictly ‘VOC’, in that they are not ‘by’ or ‘of’ the VOC, are part of collections that are used to understand the VOC, its activity and empire, and also document and record our continuing interaction with the ‘VOC’. Moreover, we, as a society, continue to create VOC collections through the investigation and management of sites and material culture associated with the VOC. A ‘VOC Collections’ scoping exercise therefore is seemingly without limit. The scoping exercise therefore prioritised three groupings of collections:

1. Collections that hold VOC shipwreck items.
2. Partner institutions on the MOB-VOC project.

3. Broader 'VOC collections' noted in the course of research of the above groupings.

This allowed the scoping to concentrate on the VOC shipwreck collections, take note of other 'VOC collections' that assist in the interpretation of those collections, and recognise the ongoing resources, such as photograph and document archives and literature, that are a product of us, as a society, engaging with these collections.

This scoping exercise has inevitably only been able to shed light on part of what are a multitude of diverse VOC collections across the world. It is hoped that this initial work is a resource for those researching the VOC through its collections beyond the MOB-VOC project, and will continue to be added to in the spirit that it was created.

Collections/Institutions

Many crossovers and connections exist between the collections, institutions, projects and resources listed below. The collections are listed according to their institutions/collectors, and effort is made to contextualise these with the other organisations, institutions, or projects with which they are associated. The order of presentation is:

1. [VOC Shipwreck Collections](#): collections that contain VOC shipwreck items, arranged by country, then alphabetically.
2. [VOC Collections – Other](#): collections that contain VOC material more broadly, across libraries, museums, archives and private collections, arranged by country, then alphabetically.
3. [Other Collections of Note](#): a list of institutions where collections are small or very little detail is currently known to allow a fuller description, arranged alphabetically.

Please note that inclusion in this scoping report is not intended as endorsement of collectors and collections or any related activities and methodologies.

In some instances in this report, the amount of material held in a collection will be referred to by the number of ‘records’ returned from a search of the database rather than the number of items. This is because there is no guarantee that a record equates to a single physical item, e.g. a set of plates, a pair of figurines, a purse of coins, a barrel of bones.

To assist in ameliorating any omissions or errors, please email rebecca.repper@uwa.edu.au.

VOC Shipwreck Collections

Australia

Art Gallery of South Australia

The art collection for the state of South Australia – a broad collection of art, with a distinct speciality in Asian art/artisanal craft.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- 'Hatcher Junk' (1646) – at least one item of ceramic (Bennett & Kelty 2014, no. 48).

Note: the collection includes an extensive collection of Asian ceramics 'found' or 'purchased' – these reflect European influence on ceramic production and trade from the 16th centuries, and some may be sourced from Southeast Asian shipwrecks.

Other Relevant Collections

Collection strengths include Asian art and artisanal craft which will reflect various aspects of interaction and trade with Europe. A small number of items held have 'VOC' stamps/marks, including two textiles, a piece of Arita ware, and a [wooden chest](#).

Collection Access: [online catalogue](#).

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Treasure Ships: Art in the Age of Spices](#), 2015.

References

Art Gallery of South Australia. (n.d.). AGSA - The Art Gallery of South Australia. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.agsa.sa.gov.au/>.

Bennett, J., & Kelty, R. (with Art Gallery of South Australia & Art Gallery of Western Australia). (2014). *Treasure ships: Art in the age of spices*. Art Gallery of South Australia.

[Australian National Maritime Museum \(ANMM\)](#)

National public collecting institution, located on Darling Harbour, Sydney. Collection centres on the Maritime Heritage of Australia, which includes the European ‘discovery’, contact with, and charting of Australia.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The ANMM holds VOC shipwreck material because of the [‘Agreement between Australia and the Netherlands concerning Old Dutch Shipwrecks’ \(ANCODS\)](#). Under this agreement a ‘representative collection of the contents of each statistical sample’ of the Dutch wrecks was transferred to a Commonwealth Government institution (ANCODS, 1972). As a result of this the collection has a representative sample of shipwreck material from:

- *Batavia* (1629).
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656) (as ‘Vergulde Draeck’).
- *Zuiddorp* (1712) (as ‘Zuytdorp’).
- *Zeewijk* (1727).

Note that the WA Museum has maintained record of the artefacts sent to ANMM in their in-house shipwreck artefact database.

Other Relevant Collections

Collection includes material that relates broadly to the VOC’s navigation, trade and exploration which led to their contact with Australia and First Nations people. These include:

- *Duyfken replica* – full-scale reproduction built to maximum practicable authenticity (Burningham & Jong, 1997; Worth, 2013).
- Art, including:
 - period works, e.g. [Engraving by Romeyn de Hooghe, 1670, depicting the conquest of the Kingdom of Makassar 1666 - 1669 by the Dutch East India Company \(VOC\) under the command of Cornelis Speelman](#).
 - modern works, e.g. [Representation of first contact with the Duyfken off the West Australian coast, by Laurel Nannup](#).
- Books and journals, including:
 - Jan Jansz’s 1647 publication of Francisco Pelsaert’s account [‘Ongeluckige voyagie van’t schip Batavia’](#).
 - Schouten’s account of the first rounding of Cape Horn to South East Asia: [‘Journal ou relation exacte du voyage de Guill Schouten, dans les Indes’](#).
 - Published account [‘Historie van Indien, waer inne verhaelt is avonturen die de Hollantse schepen bejegenet zijn, T Eerste Boeck’](#): the very first journey of the Dutch to the East Indies under Cornelis de Houtman (1540-1599), based on the account of Willem Lodewijcksz, a clerk on board *Mauritius*.
- Ephemera – such as a [VOC notebook](#), and a [contract of service to the VOC](#).
- Maps/charts – such as Johannes Janssonius [‘Mar di India’](#) (1650).
- Numismatics – 10 late 17th century VOC ‘duits’ of unknown provenance (subject of current research).

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- Ship models – modern, including of *Zeehaen*, *Heemskerck* and *Duyfken*.

Collection Access: Primary access through [Collections online](#) currently represents 65% of collections (Annual Report 2022-23). Collections also available on [Google Arts and Culture](#).

Collection Data Sharing: ANMM has made its data available on TROVE, the National Library of Australia’s collection aggregator.

- [Trove API](#): API key required. A good introduction and tools for using TROVE’s API are given by the [GLAM Workbench](#).

Licensing: All Rights Reserved – contact institution regarding reuse/reproduction of collection images and data.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- ‘Commerce and Conquest: the story of the Dutch United East India Company’, 24 November 1999–30 July 2000.
- ‘Batavia: a magnificent ship, an incredible story’, 5 December 1999–19 March 2001 (featuring the Batavia reconstruction during its around the world voyage).
- ‘A Curious Coincidence – Two 17th century Dutch explorers encounter Australia’, 20 August 2000–28 February 2001 (Official event in the Olympic Arts Festival).
- Batavia Tapestry, by artist Melinda Piesse, exhibited 2017 (‘The Batavia Tapestry’, 2017).
- [‘Submerged. Stories of Australia’s shipwrecks’](#), 2018-2020.
- [‘Under Southern Skies’](#), current gallery space.
- [Brickwrecks: Sunken ships in LEGO® Bricks](#), with WA Museum, exhibited 2022–23.

References

Agreement between Australia and the Netherlands Concerning Old Dutch Shipwrecks, and Arrangement [1972] ATS 18 (1972).

<https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/other/dfat/treaties/ATS/1972/18.html>.

Australian National Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Australian National Maritime Museum. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.sea.museum/>.

Australian National Maritime Museum, Sydney, Australia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/australia-national-maritime-museum>.

Australian National Maritime Museum. (2001). Temporary Exhibitions. In *Australian National Maritime Museum Annual Report 2000-2001* (pp. 11–14). Australian National Maritime Museum. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-2062498302>.

Australian National Maritime Museum. (2023). *Australian National Maritime Museum Annual Report 2022-23*. Australian National Maritime Museum. <https://www.sea.museum/about/corporate-information/planning-and-reporting/annual-reports>.

The Batavia Tapestry: A tragic tale told in stitch. (2017). *Signals*, 119, 22–29.

Burningham, N., & Jong, A. (1997). The Duyfken Project: An Age of Discovery ship reconstruction as experimental archaeology. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 26(4), 277–292.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1997.tb01339.x>.

Mather, W. (2022, March). Blood money: the coins of Batavia. *Signals*, 138, 18–25.
<https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.505767704268899>.

Terry, M. (2000, June). Bring a plate [A Curious Coincidence exhibition - 17th century Dutch explorers encounter Australia, part of this year's exploration of the United Dutch East India Company in Australian history]. *Signals*, 51, 4–6. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/ielapa.200011465>.

Worth, H. (2013). The Duyfken: An exploration of the roles of a replica ship. *The Great Circle: Journal of the Australian Association for Maritime History*, 35(1), 75–95.
<https://doi.org/10.3316/informit.538644489146921>.

Kerry Stokes Collection (Australian Capital Equity)

Private collection located in Perth, Western Australia. The collection is not open to the public but has exhibition spaces that can be accessed by arranged appointment, and often works collaboratively with other collections, curators and researchers (e.g. Bennett & Kelty, 2014).

The history of the VOC's operations in Southeast Asia is an area of collecting interest (Persak 2014); as well as early European contact with and exploration of Australia (especially contact with its western edge), including cartographic and shipwreck material.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The collection is possibly the largest of Western Australian Dutch shipwreck material outside the WA Museum and ANMM, but also includes shipwreck material from other salvaged VOC wrecks. These have been acquired through private purchase and auction, including the collections of Hugh Edwards and Robert Muir. The represented shipwrecks in the collection include:

- *Batavia* (1629).
- *Lastdrager* (1653) – signet ring.
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – cargo/Ballast (ceramics).
- The 'Binh Thuận Wreck' (1608) – cargo/Ballast (ceramics).

Other Relevant Collections

The private collection also extends to art works, manuscript charts, printed maps and globes, antiquarian books, manuscript journals, objects and ephemera that relate to, describe, or derive from VOC activity.

- Paintings and works on paper, for example:
 - [Bonaventura Peeters, Coastal landscape with sailors coming ashore and drinking water, c. 1645.](#)
- Antiquarian books/manuscripts, for example:
 - Louis Relian's manuscript journal, 1752.
 - Jetso van Vos's VOC ship's log book, c. 1794.
- Atlases, maps and charts, for example:
 - Vellum chart '(From the Cape of Good Hope to the Sunda Strait) annotated with tracks of the ship *Diemermeer*' by Isaac de Graaf, 1735.
 - Printed (Wall map of the East Indies), by Justus Danckerts, 1670-1710.
 - [Printed \(Map of the Moluccas Islands\) \[Spice Map\], by Petrus Plancius, 1617.](#)
 - Atlas *Theatrum Orbis*, by Abraham Ortelius, 1570.
- Objects, for example:
 - VOC copper paper weight for vellum charts, c. 1725.
 - VOC glass bottle, c. 1735.
- Personal archives (including photographs) – Hugh Edwards and Robert Muir.

Collection Access: No public portal. Collection is currently 98% documented and digitised. Managed using The Museum System.

An e-book /catalogue of VOC material in the Kerry Stokes Collection is currently in progress as part of this project.

Collection Data Sharing: Any access to collections and use/distribution of collection information will require a custom data access and sharing agreement.

References

Bennett, J., & Kelty, R. (with Art Gallery of South Australia & Art Gallery of Western Australia). (2014). *Treasure ships: Art in the age of spices*. Art Gallery of South Australia.

Persak, E. (2014). A celebration of manuscripts in the Kerry Stokes Collection. *The Australian Library Journal*, 63(1), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049670.2013.872551>.

Michael Abbott Collection of Trade Ceramics in Australia, Southeast Asian Ceramic Archaeology Laboratory (SEACAL), Flinders University

A donation of trade ceramics (c. 2300 items) collected by Michael Abbott to the Southeast Asian Ceramic Archaeology Laboratory at Flinders University.

Michael Abbott is an avid collector of Southeast Asian and Pacific cultural heritage and art. The collection is representative of ceramics from what is modern day China, Thailand, Vietnam and Indonesia. He has also made donations to multiple cultural heritage institutions across Australia, including the WA Museum and Art Gallery of South Australia.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The likelihood that this collection of c. 2300 objects holds items from VOC shipwrecks is high as they are believed to be primarily salvaged from Indonesian territorial waters (Riau Archipelago, Eastern Java, Bangka Belitung Islands and South Sulawesi). Their provenance is part of ongoing research (Polkinghorne, 2023; Polkinghorne et al., 2024).

Collection Access: none known.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

The donation is subject to the Australian Research Council Linkage Project 'Reuniting orphaned cargoes: Shared heritage of the Maritime Silk Route' (LP210200165) which is investigating the provenance of the items which includes shipwreck material.

References

Polkinghorne, M. (2023). Michael Abbott and the Southeast Asian Ceramic Archaeology Laboratory at Flinders University. In J. Bennett & R. Kelty (Eds.), *Interwoven journeys: The Michael Abbott collections of Asian art*. Art Gallery of South Australia, 124-129.

Polkinghorne, M., Pearson, N., Van Duivenvoorde, W., Nayati, W., Tahir, Z., Ridwan, N. N. H., Forrest, C., Tan, N. H., Popelka-Filcoff, R., Morton, C., Kowlessar, J., & Staniforth, M. (2024). Reuniting orphaned cargoes: Recovering cultural knowledge from salvaged and dispersed underwater cultural heritage in Southeast Asia. *Marine Policy*, 163, 106074.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106074wrak>.

[Powerhouse Museum](#)

The Museum is a public institution located in Sydney, New South Wales, exhibiting across several locations. The collection and programs are focused on the intersection of art, design, science and technology. The Museum originated as the Sydney Technological Museum in 1893.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Batavia* (1629) – [a single wine bottle](#), noted as ‘found washed up on a beach by George Oollingridge de Tourcey around 1922’. Note: originally part of the Royal Australian Historical Society (RAHS) collection, donated in 1981.
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656) – [three Spanish Eight Reales](#) coins are considered to originate from the wreck (‘Gilt Dragon’), purchased in the late 1960s.

Other Relevant Collections

- ‘VOC’ [coins](#) of various denominations minted in Batavia.
- A series of *Batavia* [artefact replicas](#) – one of the astrolabe designed by Brian Greig and four commemorative medals issued by the WA Museum with case and certificate.

Collection Access

- [Collection portal](#).

Collection Data Sharing: ANMM has made its data available on TROVE, the National Library of Australia’s collection aggregator.

- [Trove API](#): API key required. A good introduction and tools for using TROVE’s API are given by the [GLAM Workbench](#).
- Note: material does not appear in Commonwealth Underwater Cultural Heritage artefacts and shipwreck register: [Australasian Underwater Cultural Heritage Database](#).

Licensing: Collection description text is released under CC-Attribution-Non Commercial-No Derivative licence. Rights are reserved for collection images.

References

Powerhouse Museum. (n.d.). Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://powerhouse.com.au/>.

[Royal Geographical Society, South Australia](#)

A voluntary society founded in 1885 to advance the study and public awareness of geography and related disciplines, especially regarding South Australia.

Their [library](#) is one of the most significant collections of rare geographical books and manuscripts in Australia. It includes collections of historic books and cartography, and a relics and artefacts collection.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- Zeewijk (1727) (likely all sourced from Gun Island), including:
 - A buckle (note that of a Mr Giles mentioned in [The Advertiser, 1914, 7 July, p. 15](#)).
 - Key.
 - Bottle – probably item taken from Gun Island 1891 donated by Mr T E Barr Smith; ([The Advertiser, 1951, 24 January, p. 4](#)). Currently on display South Australian Maritime Museum.
 - Bottle fragments – likely those donated from the WA Museum and Art Gallery in 1913 ([The Journal, 1913, 27 June, p. 2](#)).

Other Relevant Collections

- Rare books, including:
 - Arnold Colom, [Zee-atlas, ofte water-wereldt: In houdende een Korte beschryvinge van alle de bekende zee-Kusten des aardtrycks. Nieuwelijcks uyt-ghegheven 1658](#) [Sea atlas of the water world: containing a brief description of all known sea coasts of the earth. Newly published 1658] (Amsterdam).
 - Nicholaes Visscher, [Atlas minor sive geographia compendiosa qua orbis terrarum per paucas attamen novissimas tabulas ostenditur](#) (1690).
 - A 1648 edition of Pelsaert's [Ongeluckige voyage van't schip Batavia](#).
 - Jean Piere Purry's published [Memoire sur le pais des cafres, et la terre de Nuyts](#) (proposal that the Dutch create a settlement in the 'Land of Nuyts').

Collection Access

- Library holdings can be searched either through their [online catalogue or finding aids](#) depending on the collection.
- Note: material does not appear in Commonwealth Underwater Cultural Heritage artefacts and shipwreck register: [Australasian Underwater Cultural Heritage Database](#).

References

Catalogue of Library Holdings. (n.d.). The Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://rgssa.org.au/library/catalogue-of-library-holdings>.

Interesting Relics. The history of the State. Discovery and Explorations. Many Brave Deeds Recalled. (1914, July 7). *The Advertiser*, 15. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article6424240>.

Out Among the People. (1951, January 24). *The Advertiser*, 4. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article45708741>.

Royal Geographical Society. (1913, June 27). *The Journal*, 2. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article200879144>.

Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. (n.d.). The Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://rgssa.org.au/>.

[Silentworld Foundation](#) (John and Jacqui Mullen)

Collections acquired by John and Jacqui Mullen focusing on the maritime discovery, mapping and history of Australia, especially the period 16-19th century. This extends to 'maps, paintings, manuscripts, shipwreck material, ephemera, coins and medallions, militaria and historical artefacts' related to the Dutch East India Company exploration, discovery, and trade over the period.

Collections are primarily purchased, and the Foundation engages in programmes of fieldwork, research and community engagement.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Batavia* (1629) – [bricks](#), coins, and a decoratively draped and framed trio of bast rigging rope, wooden trowel and slip nail.
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656) – coins.
- *De Liefde* (1711) – coin.
- *Zeewijk* (1727) – [bricks](#).
- *Rooswijk* (1740) – silver ingot.

Other Relevant Collections

- Art, such as view of '[roadstead of Batavia](#)' by Hendrik Kobell.
- Silver medal to commemorate the centenary of the VOC.
- Maps, for example:
 - a [VOC chart of Makassar, c.1700](#).
 - an antique print of 'Mar Di India', 1650.
 - [Spice Map](#) by Petrus Plancius, 1617.
- Example of a VOC devotional book 'Schat-Boeck der Verclaringen den Nederlandschen Catechismus,' 1694.
- Example of a [VOC Almanac](#), embellished with sealskin binding and silver clasps.
- [Ship model](#) of the *Batavia*.

Collection Access: part of the collections are made available through

- [eHive](#) – web-based CMS;
- Foundation [website](#).

Licensing: CC BY-NC-ND.

References

Welcome to the Silentworld Foundation. (n.d.). Silentworld Foundation. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://silentworldfoundation.org.au/>.

South Australian Maritime Museum, [Shipwreck Collections](#)

Maritime Museum located in the historic precinct of Port Adelaide, part of the History Trust of South Australia. The Museum preserves the oldest nautical collection in Australia, first established in 1872, and is focused on the maritime heritage of South Australia, including a substantial collection connected with Australian shipwrecks.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The shipwreck collection includes material from 17th century Dutch shipwrecks to the modern era. This includes:

- *Vergulde Draak* (1656) – Tusk (on display), also coins, bricks and cannon balls. These are currently being transferred from the South Australian Museum collections although these were apparently given to the SA History Trust in 2006/7 (History Trust of South Australia, 2007).
- *Zeewijk* (1727) [?] – A bottle from Gun Island is reported to have been donated to the ‘Port Museum’ in 1891 ([‘Latest News’](#), 1891).

Note: Scope of collection has been requested from museum.

Other Relevant Collections

- A bayonet blade (HT 1998.0230) in the collections was recovered from St Francis Island – an island associated with the 1627 voyage and possible landings of *Gulden Zeepard*.
- Gavan Berecny shipwreck collection – Artefacts reported to have been collected from shipwrecks before the introduction of the Historic Shipwrecks Act (1976). Set of c. 300-400 objects. Appears to have been part of a collection transferred from the Department of Environment and Heritage (who administer Maritime Heritage in SA) (History Trust of South Australia, 2006).

Collection Access

- [History Trust of South Australia online Collections](#). Note that no shipwreck artefacts yet available in digitised collections.
- Note: material does not appear in Commonwealth Underwater Cultural Heritage artefacts and shipwreck register – [Australasian Underwater Cultural Heritage Database](#).

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Wrecked! Tragedy and the Southern Seas](#), 2005.

References

History Trust of South Australia. (2006). Twenty sixth annual report of the History Trust of South Australia for the year ended 30 June 2006 [Annual Report]. History Trust of South Australia. <https://www.history.sa.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/annual-report-2005-06.pdf>.

History Trust of South Australia. (2007). Twenty seventh annual report of the History Trust of South Australia for the year ended 30 June 2007 [Annual Report]. History Trust of South Australia. <https://www.history.sa.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/annual-report-2006-07.pdf>.

Latest News (1891, December 14). *Evening Journal*, 2. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article198425844>.

Shipwreck Collection | Maritime Museum. (n.d.). South Australian Maritime Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://maritime.history.sa.gov.au/collections/>.

Wrecked! Tragedy and the Southern Seas. (n.d.). South Australian Maritime Museum. Retrieved August 13, 2024, from <https://maritime.history.sa.gov.au/events/wrecked-tragedy-and-the-southern-seas/>.

[Western Australian Museum \(WA Museum\)](#)

Public museum for the state of Western Australia. The Museum encompasses multiple sites, disciplines, and collections. The collection material related to the Dutch East India Company are held by the department of Maritime Heritage (formerly Maritime Archaeology and Maritime History), based at the WA Shipwrecks Museum, Fremantle.

The Museum is vested with the responsibility for the possession, and through this, the study, protection, and interpretation, of the VOC ships, and any items associated, that are located in Western Australia under the ANCODS Agreement (1972), [Maritime Archaeology Act 1973 \(WA\)](#), and the [Underwater Cultural Heritage Act 2018 \(Commonwealth\)](#) (note the WA legislation is currently under review).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Museum holds an extensive artefact assemblage recovered from four VOC shipwrecks and associated sites, and Cape Inscription – the site where Dirk Hartog and Willem de Vlamingh landed on the Western Australian coast and left inscriptions. The majority of material was recovered through investigation (research, survey and excavation) by the Museum, starting in the 1960s, but also through donation and returns of material acquired since the 19th century. These latter have come into the Museum collection in various ways, such as the Broadhurst donation in the early 20th century of material acquired during a period of Guano extraction on the Abrolhos Islands to what was then the ‘Perth Museum’, and declarations and returns during the 1993/1994 amnesty (Rodrigues, 2009, 2012) in association with federal maritime heritage legislation.

The current extent of material in the Museum’s public collection database is as follows (note numbers will change as research on the material continues and the public database is updated):

- Dirk Hartog landing (1616), and subsequent landing by Willem de Vlamingh (1697) (and the later French landing) – c. [50 records](#), note a further c. [320 records](#) from 2006 excavations (see [WA Museum overview](#)).
- *Batavia* (1629) – c. [6880 records](#).
- Beacon Island (*Batavia*) – c. [2380 records](#) and c. [1240 records](#) from different periods of investigation on the island (see [WA Museum overview](#)).
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656) (as ‘Vergulde Draeck’) – c. [2330 records](#).
- *Zuiddorp* (1712) (as ‘Zuytdorp’) – c. [1320 records](#).
- *Zeewijk* (1727) – c. [4350 records](#) (note these also include items from Gun Island).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – ceramic plates (part of Maritime History collection).

The material spans:

- Portions and items from the ships’ structures, fixtures and fittings, most notably a large portion of the hull of *Batavia* (Duivenvoorde 2015).
- The assortment of material that make up the ship inventory, such as cannons, Bartmann jugs, and pots and pans.
- Tools and equipment such as navigational instruments for the journey, but also fishhooks fashioned by survivors.
- Clothing and personal items such as belt buckles, buttons, book clasps, and dice.

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- Cargo and ballast, including elephant tusks, bricks, the stones for an arch/portico (known as Batavia archway), and a shipment of luxury silverware destined for the Mughal court. Most profuse in number is the specie, the silver coins brought on the ships to facilitate trade and economy in Batavia.
- Skeletal material from the victims of *Batavia* shipwreck and subsequent mutiny.
- Artefacts retrieved from Cape Inscription from the landings of Dirk Hartog and Willem de Vlamingh – most notably, [de Vlamingh's plate](#) (returned to Australia in 1947, and to WA in 1950).

There are three other VOC ships that could be located off the Western Australian coast, but no trace has yet been found: *Aagtekerke* (1726), *Ridderschap van Holland* (1694), and *Fortuin* (1724).

The Museum also holds a small reference collection of c. 150 items for Maritime Archaeologists involved in excavation in the Gulf of Thailand – the [Abbott Collection of Southeast Asian ceramics](#) donated in 1981 (Craig, 2013). The provenance of much of this collection is unknown and some items could be relevant to VOC activity (nb. [Michael Abbott Collection of Trade Ceramics in Australia](#)).

Other Relevant Collections

The investigation of the Western Australian shipwrecks has also resulted in the creation of a large associated archive and reference collection. These include:

- Two textiles stamped with VOC insignia (Maritime History Collection).
- Ship models (modern) – a Dutch fluyt, *Batavia*, *Edam*, *Sloeptie* (Zeewijk sloop), and *Zuiddorp* (note: models of *Eendracht* and *Duyfken* in the collection are on loan).
- Replica of the Dirk Hartog plate (nb. Rijksmuseum).
- Field work and artefact documentation such as day books, site and artefact drawings.
- A reference library of grey literature produced by, or in association with, the department and its fieldwork.
- Publications and modern maps.
- Data for 3D models of sites and objects.
- A large visual archive – mainly photographs taken during field work and of collection items.

Note: there is a modern full-scale replica of *Batavia* longboat located in Geraldton at the waterfront outside the Geraldton Museum. This is managed by the Batavia Coast Replica Boat Association.

Collection Access

Individual databases are managed for the different collection types, using in-house standards (e.g. codes for site, location, materials etc).

- [Artefacts database](#) (Maritime Archaeology shipwreck artefact database).
- [Department of Maritime Archaeology Report Series](#) (grey literature of relevant fieldwork/projects).
- [Numismatics](#) (coin collections from Maritime Archaeology expeditions) (note: Nomisma standard).
- [Library database](#) institutional archives pre-1960, publications.
- 3D models available through [SketchFab](#), e.g. Zeewijk wreck site.

There is currently no public database for the following and enquiries can be directed to the institution:

- Maritime History.
- Skeletal database.
- Visual archives – maritime archaeology photographs, video etc.
- Field work archives – day books, drawings, plans etc.

Note: the WA Museum in-house artefact catalogue also include ‘relics’ from Maritime Heritage sites that are in private hands reported under both Section 40 of the *Underwater Cultural Heritage Act 2018*, and under Section 17(1) of the *Western Australian Maritime Archaeology Act 1973*.

Site Register/Portal

- WA Museum [Shipwrecks database](#) and [interactive map](#).
- Commonwealth Underwater Cultural Heritage artefacts and shipwreck register: [Australasian Underwater Cultural Heritage Database](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- data.museum.wa.gov.au: CC-BY datasets (Note: these have not been updated since 2017).
 - Artefacts.
 - Numismatics.
 - Shipwrecks.
- data.wa.gov.au: datasets for location of shipwrecks and maritime archaeology sites. Up to date, license CC-BY.

Licensing: WA Museum website lists ©All Rights Reserved, Government of Western Australia. Data sharing arrangements required for any data and images that are not yet made available CC-BY – copyright licensing is managed through the Director of the relevant area of the Museum (WA Museum Intellectual Property Policy, Appendix 1.2).

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

The WA Museum has been involved with many projects researching the VOC sites of the Western Australian coast, and their objects, over the years, which have produced varied outputs. These include, but are in no way limited to:

- [Maritime Journals](#): Scanned pages, transcription, and translations of maritime journals from the Nationaal Archief series 1.04.02. The project is ongoing (Note also, Nationaal Archief machine learning transcription projects ‘De ijsberg zichtbaar maken’ and Globalise).
- [Strangers on the Shore](#): European and Asian shipwrecks around Western Australia's coastline where survivors may have had social contact with First Nations peoples (out of date).
- [ANCODS](#) (Agreement between Australia and the Netherlands Concerning Old Dutch Shipwrecks) Collection: collection data for the representative selection of the VOC shipwreck material that was initially allocated under the ANCODS agreement to the Netherlands, but was returned in 2010 so that the assemblages could remain together.

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- [Shipwrecks of the Roaring 40s](#): A maritime archaeological research project that aimed to reassess some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks (Green & Paterson, 2020). Included the [Beacon Island Visualisation](#), developed at Curtin HIVE which documents Beacon Island as it was in 2013, including the photogrammetric 3D reconstruction of graves of individuals from the Batavia, buried on the island after the ship was wrecked and following the uprising.
- [1616—Dirk Hartog](#): online exhibition for the anniversary of Dirk Hartog's landing on the West Australian coast.
- [Visualising unique 17th century Batavia silverware](#): 3D visualization/recordings of silverware, in partnership with University of Western Australia, Rijksmuseum, University of Amsterdam and Nationaal Archief.
- [Database of the people aboard the VOC ships Batavia \(1629\) and Zeewijk \(1727\)](#) (Ariese, 2012) – data content listed in appendices of report (current location/condition of computational database unknown).
- 'Shipwreck! discoveries from our earliest shipwrecks 1622-1797', January 1988-June 1989 (with Australian Bicentennial Authority, Museum of Victoria and Queensland Museum) (multiple venues).
- 'Voyages of Grand Discovery', 20 July-18 November 2007.
- 'Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World', 31 October 2016-23 April 2017.
- [Brickwrecks: Sunken ships in LEGO® Bricks](#), with ANMM, exhibited December 2021-November 2022 (multiple venues).

References

Ariese, C. (2012). *Databases of the people aboard the VOC ships Batavia (1629) & Zeewijk (1725): An analysis of the potential for finding the Dutch castaways' human remains in Australia*. WA Museum.

https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.16_people_aboard_the_voc_ships_batavia_and_zeewijk.pdf.

Agreement between Australia and the Netherlands Concerning Old Dutch Shipwrecks, and Arrangement [1972] ATS 18 (1972).

<https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/other/dfat/treaties/ATS/1972/18.html>.

Australia: Visualising unique 17th century Batavia silverware. (2019, September 2). DutchCulture.

<https://internationalheritage.dutchculture.nl/news/australia-visualising-unique-seventeenth-century-batavia-silverware>.

Craig, J. (2013). *Southeast Asian and Chinese Ceramics in the Shipwreck Galleries: The Abbott Collection Catalogue* (WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports 302). WA Museum.

https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.302_abbott_collection_0.pdf.

Duivenvoorde, W. Van. (2015). *Dutch East India Company (VOC) Shipbuilding: The Archaeological Study of Batavia and Other Seventeenth-Century VOC Ships*. Ed Rachal Series in Nautical Archaeology. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.

Green, J. N. (1989). *The loss of the Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie retourschip Batavia, Western Australia 1629: an excavation report and catalogue of artefacts*. BAR International Series 489. British Archaeological Reports.

Green, J., Gainsford, M., & Stanbury, M. (Eds.). (2004). *Department of Maritime Archaeology, Western Australian Maritime Museum. A compendium of projects, programmes and publications 1971-2003*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology.
https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.09_compendium_0.pdf.

Green, J., & Paterson, A. (Eds.). (2020). *Shipwrecks of the roaring forties: Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks*. UWA Publishing.

Green, J. N., & Zuiderbaan, L. H. (1977). *The loss of the Verenigde oostindische compagnie Jacht Vergulde Draeck, Western Australia 1656: an historical background and excavation report with an appendix on similar loss of the fluit Lastdrager*. British Archaeological Reports 36. British Archaeological Reports.

Hogarth, C. (2000). *Shipwreck: Discoveries from Our earliest Shipwrecks, 1622-1797*. International Cultural Corporation of Australia.

Ingelman-Sundberg, C. (1978). *Relics from the Dutch East Indiaman, Zeewijk, founded in 1727*. Western Australian Museum.

Maritime Archaeology Act 1973, WA (1973).
https://www.legislation.wa.gov.au/legislation/statutes.nsf/law_a477.html.

Maritime Archaeology Databases. (n.d.). Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/>.

McCarthy, M., Stanbury, M., & Jones, D. S. (2007). *Voyages of Grand Discovery* (M. McCarthy & V. Northey, Eds.). Western Australian Museum.

Parthesius, R., & Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten (Centre for International Heritage Activities). (2014). *Inventory and analyses of archival sources in the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives in the Netherlands in order to contribute to possible locations and identification of VOC shipwrecks off the Western Australian Coast* (WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports No. 310). Western Australian Museum Foundation; Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten.

Underwater Cultural Heritage Act 2018, Cth (2018).
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/C2018A00085/latest>.

Welcome to the Western Australian Museum. (n.d.). Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://visit.museum.wa.gov.au/>.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1974). *Vergulde Draeck. Catalogue of Artefacts. Illustrations*. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 1, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. [1974]. *Batavia Catalogue*. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 2, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1979). Catalogue of Dutch Relics. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 3, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1982). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 4, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1983). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 5, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1985). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 6, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, Stanbury, M., & Sawday, F. (1991). ANCODS 1991. Report and Catalogue of Artefacts. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 7, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (2002). ANCODS 2002. Report on the Dutch Shipwreck Collections. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 8, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum. (2016). *Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World*. Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum. (n.d.). *1616 Dirk Hartog*. Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <http://museum.wa.gov.au/explore/dirk-hartog>.

Cabo Verde

Museus de Cabo Verde – Museu de Arqueologia, and Museu de Arqueologia da Boa Vista

The Museu de Arqueologia in Praia was established in 2008 as part of the salvage projects conducted by Afrimar and Arqueonautas Worldwide between 1992 and 2002, beginning as a conservation and restoration centre for the raised materials ((Bettencourt et al., 2020, p. 2073). The Archaeology Museum of Boa Vista opened in 2023. Both museums exhibit artefacts from five shipwrecks off the coast of the islands: *Leimuiden* (1780), *Hartwell* (1787), *Lady Burgess* (1806), *Varandinha* (unknown) and *Santo André* (1856).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Leimuiden* (1780) – Scope of artefacts unclear as no public information. The Museum summarises the collections from the shipwrecks as encompassing: ‘collections of navigation instruments, ship's structure (window, rudder governor, pulley, pins, etc.), cannons and other war materials, assorted coins, amphorae and forms of sugar, ivory and bones, personal use (pocket watches, beads, cufflinks, buckles, manicure sets, pipes, tobacco, etc.), ceramic fragments, kitchen utensils, chains and handcuffs, as well as artefacts representing life on board the vessels (wine and cognac bottles, bottles with medicinal products, mortars, flasks, syringes and personal hygiene materials (toothbrushes, potty, jug etc.).’

Collection Access: none known.

References

Bettencourt, J., Dias, A., Lima, C., Chouzenoux, C., Fonseca, C., Pereira, D., Lopes, G., Coelho, I., Monteiro, J., Lima, J., Alves, M. E., Carvalho, P., & Silva, T. (2020). Arqueologia Marítima em Cabo Verde: Enquadramento e primeiros resultados do projecto concha. In *Arqueologia em Portugal. 2020 – Estado da Questão* (pp. 2071–2084). Associação dos Arqueólogos Portugueses.

Museus de Cabo Verde. (n.d.). Museu de Cabo Verde. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.museus.cv/en/home>.

Canada

Art Gallery of Greater Victoria

Art Gallery that focuses on the Pacific Rim, located in Victoria, Vancouver Island. Has a dedicated and extensive Asian Art collection.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [25 records](#), all ceramics.

Other Relevant Collections

Asian art that would have been part of the wider European trade and collection networks, such as Arita ware.

Collection Access: [eMuseum](#) collection portal.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

References

Art Gallery Greater Vic. (n.d.). Art Gallery of Greater Victoria. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://aggv.ca/>.

China

Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum

An Art Museum focused on the arts and cultural heritage of ancient and modern China, including an extensive collection of Asian ceramics.

Shipwreck material

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – ceramic.
- 'Cà Mau Shipwreck' (1725) – ceramic.

Collection Access: [Online portal](#).

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved, contact the institution for use of the collection images.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe](#) curated by Dr. Guanyu Wang, 2021-2022 [Online: [Google Arts and Culture](#)].

References

Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe. (n.d.). The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Faculty of Arts. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://arts.cuhk.edu.hk/web/index.php/news-and-events/enchanting-expeditions-chinese-trade-porcelains-across-globe>.

Guanyu Wang, & Art Museum, The Chinese University of Hong Kong. (n.d.). *Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe*. Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 6 August 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/story/rAXhy7Zg9ox7ow?hl=en>.

文物館 *Art Museum*. (n.d.). The Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.artmuseum.cuhk.edu.hk/en/>.

[Guangdong Museum](#)

Museum for the province of Guangdong which includes the important historical trading port of Macao. The Museum has a permanent exhibition that communicates the region's place as part of the 'Silk Road' and international trade. The Museum is also a specialist in China for the care of underwater cultural items.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- Unknown wreck – Reported by Nico Brinck (2020, 230) as having an 18-pounder cannon marked with the Hoorn chapter of the VOC that was found off the coast of Macao in the Gulf of Tonkin. Brinck suggests the cannon was possibly originally from *Westfriesland*, but transferred to another vessel when that ship was put out of service.

Collection Access: [Collection portal](#) – no translation available.

References

Brinck, N. (2020). *Kanonnen van Nederland: Nederlands geschut en andere oude kanonnen in Nederland* [Guns of the Netherlands: Dutch cannon and other old guns in the Netherlands] (2nd revised edition). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed.

广东省博物馆 [Guangdong Museum]. (n.d.). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.gdmuseum.com/cn>.

France

Monnaie de Paris

An active mint (The Paris Mint), a currency museum, and modern art museum. Features a historic collection of coins, Le Médailleur monétaire, from antiquity to the present from France and abroad.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – coins and ingots ([referred to as 'Trésor'](#)).

Collection Access: none known, but the institution does have a [Google Arts and Culture page](#).

References

Accueil Monnaie de Paris. (n.d.). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.monnaiedeparis.fr/en>.

Monnaie de Paris, Paris, France. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/monnaie-de-paris>.

[Musée Guimet/ Musée National des Arts Asiatiques](#)

French National Museum of Asian Art (Musée National des Arts Asiatiques), founded from the collections of Émile Guimet. The Museum was also allocated part of the Louvre collections.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Mauritius* (1609) – ceramics (Desroches 2001, 67).
- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – ceramics (Desroches 2001, 67).
- *Banda* (1615) – ceramics (Arnim 2003; Desroches 2001, 67; note also Ostkamp 2014).

Note: collection also holds items donated by Franck Goddio (MA 6376-6591: Desroches 2001, 67; Jarrige 2001, 121), owner of World Wide First, from wrecks in the China Sea. This includes items from the Spanish ship *San Diego* which sunk after a battle with the Dutch ship *Mauritius* in the Bay of Manila, 1600.

Other Relevant Collections

The Museum holds examples of south-east Asian, Chinese, Japanese, and Indian Art which were the subject of trade and collection by Europeans in the 17th and 18th centuries.

Collection Access: No online collection portal or data available.

References

Arnim, Y. von (2003). *'Kraak' porcelain from the shipwreck Banda (1615) recovered by Jacques Dumas in 1979*. Mauritius Museums Council; Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Desroches, J.-P. (2001). The maritime trade routes gallery in the Musée Guimet. *Orientations*, 32(1), 64–67.

Jarrige, J.-F. (2001). Activités du musée national des Arts asiatiques—Guimet. *Arts Asiatiques*, 56, 110–128.

Musée national des arts asiatiques-Guimet. (n.d.). Musée Guimet. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.guimet.fr/>.

Ostkamp, S. (2014). The Dutch 17th-century porcelain trade from an archaeological perspective. In J. van Campen & T. M. Eliëns (Eds.), *Chinese and Japanese porcelain for the Dutch Golden Age* (pp. 53–85). Waanders Uitgevers, in collaboration with Rijksmuseum Amsterdam; Gemeentemuseum Den Haag; Groninger Museum; Keramiekmuseum Princessehof.

[Musée National de la Marine, Port Louis, France](#)

National Maritime Museum of France, previously the Musée de la Compagnie des Indes, located in Port Louis. Some of the shipwreck collections were entrusted to the Museum from salvager Frank Goddio, and artefacts from the VOC-ship *Mauritius* were entrusted by the Elf-Gabon oil company and the Gabonese government (Musée national de la marine & De Thoisy-Dallem, 2002, p. 30). The wreck of the *Mauritius* was located off the coast of Gabon accidentally by the Elf-Gabon Petroleum company and excavated in 1986 by DRASSM (Département des Recherches Archéologiques Subaquatiques et Sous-Marines).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Mauritius* (1609) – cargo constituting blue and white Wanli period kraak porcelain, pepper, and zinc ingots, and ship armament, fixtures, and fittings, such as the [ship's bell](#) and various [cannon](#). A grain millstone and surgeon's trunk are also reported (Musée national de la marine & De Thoisy-Dallem, 2002, p. 29).

Collection Access: None known – a national collections portal is apparently in development.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- 'L'exposition Mauritius la mémoire engloutie', 16 March-11 September 1989 (Musée national de la Marine, Paris).
- 'Trésors d'océans: l'archéologie sous-marine sur la route des Indes', 22 June-15 December 2002 (Musée national de la Marine, Port Louis).

References

L'Hour, M. (n.d.). *Le Mauritius, 1609 (Gabon)*. Archéologie Sous-Marine, Ministère de La Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://archeologie.culture.gouv.fr/archeo-sous-marine/fr/le-mauritius1609-gabon>.

La route des Indes est pavée d'inaccessibles épaves. (2002, August 8). *Le Monde*, 19.

Duivenvoorde, W. Van. (2015). *Dutch East India Company (VOC) Shipbuilding: The Archaeological Study of Batavia and Other Seventeenth-Century VOC Ships*, (pp. 161–163). Ed Rachal Series in Nautical Archaeology. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.

L'Hour, M. (n.d.). *Le Mauritius, 1609 (Gabon)*. Archéologie Sous-Marine, Ministère de La Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://archeologie.culture.gouv.fr/archeo-sous-marine/fr/le-mauritius1609-gabon>.

L'Hour, M., Long, L., & Rieth, É. (1989). *Le 'Mauritius': La mémoire engloutie*. Casterman.

L'Hour, M., Long, L., & Rieth, E. (1990). The wreck of an 'experimental' ship of the 'Oost-Indische Compagnie': The *Mauritius* (1609). *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 19(1), 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1990.tb00235.x>.

Musée national de la marine, & De Thoisy-Dallem, A. (2002). *Trésors d'océans: L'archéologie sous-marine sur la route des Indes*. Musée national de la Marine.

Port-Louis. (n.d.). Musée National de La Marine. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.musee-marine.fr/en/our-museums/port-louis.html>.

Iceland

Skógar Museum

A folk museum located in southern Iceland. The Museum holds 18,000 items of regional folk craft exhibited across 3 museums and 6 historical buildings.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Wapen van Amsterdam* (1667) – A [painted lid from a wooden chest](#), which was used as a hymn board in a church. The location of the wreck of the ship is not currently known but it is known that the ship was historically salvaged.

Other Relevant Collections: none known.

Collection Access: no collections portal, but a curated selection is featured on their website.

References

A hymn board from the golden ship. (n.d.). Skógasafn Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.skogasafn.is/skogar-museum/artifacts/a-hymn-board-from-the-golden-ship/>.

Skógar Museum—Museum Iceland. (n.d.). Skógasafn Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.skogasafn.is/skogar-museum/>.

Indonesia

[Indonesia Marine Heritage Gallery, Kementerian Kelautan dan Perikanan/Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, Indonesia](#)

The Indonesian Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries is responsible for the management of shipwreck artefacts acquired through public/private partnerships for the salvage of shipwrecks in Indonesian waters, and seized artefacts from looting and illegal salvage. Some of these artefacts are exhibited at the Indonesian Marine Heritage Gallery, and artefacts seized by the government department are held in the Shipwreck Artefact Warehouse (Polkinghorne et al., 2024).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Gallery exhibits a very large collection of maritime cultural heritage for the region but Dutch, and European wrecks more broadly, are not mentioned. This suggests an emphasis on local/regional heritage. However, it is extremely likely that objects from VOC wrecks are amongst their collections due to the large number of ships known to have wrecked in Indonesian waters ('Shipwreck map on Indonesian waters', Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, 2018).

Collection Access

- No public collection portal/catalogue.
- Curated online material available through [Google Arts and Culture](#).

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Australian Research Council Linkage Project 'Reuniting orphaned cargoes: Shared heritage of the Maritime Silk Route' (LP210200165) which is investigating the provenance of orphaned ceramic collections.

References

Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/marine-heritage-gallery-indonesia>.

Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta (MHG). (n.d.). Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta (MHG). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://marineheritagegallery.wordpress.com/>.

Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries. (2018). *Shipwreck map on Indonesian waters* [Graphic]. Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia; Google Arts & Culture. <https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/shipwreck-map-on-indonesian-waters/tgE7tnzFujTEoQ>.

Polkinghorne, M., Pearson, N., Van Duivenvoorde, W., Nayati, W., Tahir, Z., Ridwan, N. N. H., Forrest, C., Tan, N. H., Popelka-Filcoff, R., Morton, C., Kowlessar, J., & Staniforth, M. (2024). Reuniting orphaned cargoes: Recovering cultural knowledge from salvaged and dispersed underwater cultural heritage in Southeast Asia. *Marine Policy*, 163, 106074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106074>.

Ireland

[National Museum of Ireland, Irish Archaeological Collection](#)

The National Museum's collections are exhibited across four locations/themes – Decorative Arts and History, Country Life, Natural History and Archaeology. The archaeology collection features items acquired through maritime archaeology, particularly in cooperation with the [Underwater Archaeology Unit](#) (UAU) of the National Monuments Service.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Zeepaard* (1665) – an assortment of ingots (lead and copper alloy), lead rings and musket balls, ceramic jars and pipes, a pewter candlestick and a stone slab. These have apparently been acquired from multiple investigations at the site from the 1970s (see record in National Monuments Service Register).
- Note: 'Blind Harbour Wreck' (1630-1699) may be a VOC or Dutch merchant ship of the same period.

Collection Access: none known. Enquire with institution.

Site Register/Portal

'[Wreck Viewer](#)' maintained by the National Monuments Service. Note also the service maintains an [archive](#) for documentation relating to the wrecks registered. *Zeepaard* is registered as W06923, and the possible VOC wreck 'Blind Harbour Wreck' is W11602.

References

Brady, K. (2017). The *Zeepaard* and the Blind Harbour wreck: Investigations of two 17th-century wrecks in Broadhaven Bay (County Mayo, Ireland). In J. Gawronski, A. Van Holk, & J. Schokkenbroek (Eds.), *Ships And Maritime Landscapes: Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Symposium on Boat and Ship Archaeology, Amsterdam 2012* (pp. 416–422). Barkhuis.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt20p56b6>.

Underwater Archaeology. (n.d.). National Monuments Service. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.archaeology.ie/underwater-archaeology>.

Welcome to the National Museum of Ireland. (n.d.). National Museum of Ireland. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museum.ie/en-ie/home>.

Wreck archive. (n.d.). National Monuments Service. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://www.archaeology.ie/underwater-archaeology/wreck-archive>.

Wreck Viewer. (n.d.). National Monuments Service. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://www.archaeology.ie/underwater-archaeology/wreck-viewer>.

Madeira

[Museu Quinta das Cruzes](#) and [Caso Colombo](#) – Museu do Porto Santo, Direção Regional da Cultura, Madeira

Museu Quinta das Cruzes is the first and central museum in Madeira, located in Funchal. Caso Colombo-Museum of Porto Santo is the Museum for the Island of Porto Santo, Madeira.

VOC ship *Slot ter Hoge* was wrecked to the north of Porto Santo and salvaged by Robert Sténuit. 10% of materials retrieved were offered to what was then the only museum on the islands – the ‘Funchal Museum’, the Museu Quinta das Cruzes. The material is part of the ‘Núcleo Arqueológico’ (Archaeological Cluster) collection and is now exhibited at the Museu do Porto Santo.

The Museu do Porto Santo exhibits the material raised from *Slot ter Hoge* in the context of Dutch, Spanish and Portuguese colonial competition over the islands and trade.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – 154 items (Esmeraldo, 2021). Includes coins and silver ingots, navigational instruments, tableware, buckles, lead weights, musket balls, a breechloading swivel gun, and tobacco pipes.

Collection Access: [Museus da Madeira online platform](#) – note that the shipwreck material does not seem to feature.

References

Columbus House—Museum of Porto Santo. (n.d.). Cultura Madeira. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://cultura.madeira.gov.pt/en/columbus-house-porto-santo-museum>.

Curtsinger, B., & Sténuit, B. (1975, August). The Treasure of Porto Santo. *National Geographic*, 148, 120–136.

Esmeraldo, A. M. B. (2021). *A caminho do oriente: Os vestígios do Slot ter Hooge (1724) na dinâmica da navegação da companhia holandesa das índias orientais* [Eastbound: The Remains of the Slot Ter Hooge (1724) Within the Dutch East India Company Navigational Dynamics] [Masters in Archaeology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global.

<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/caminho-do-oriente-os-vestigios-slot-ter-hooge/docview/3059426500/se-2>.

Museu Quinta das Cruzes. (n.d.). Quinta Das Cruzes Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://mqc.madeira.gov.pt/en/>.

Plataforma Online. (n.d.). Museus Da Madeira. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://museus.madeira.gov.pt/>.

Malaysia

Lukut Museum

Local historical museum in Kota Lukut, Port Dickson, Malaysia, associated with the 19th century Lukut Fort. A dedicated 'Nassau Gallery' presents a small collection of items from *Nassau* shipwreck (the majority of items are held by Muzium Negara – see listing in this document).

Nassau (1606) and *Middelburg* (1606) ships wrecked during the Battle of Cape Rachado, and they are located off the coast from Lukut on the Bambek Shoal, Straits of Malacca. *Nassau* was salvaged by Transea in cooperation with the Malaysian government.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Nassau* (1606) – artefacts from the 1995 excavations of the Dutch VOC warship *Nassau* in the 'Nassau Gallery' (full scope of material held has not been confirmed).

Collection Access: No online collection interface or collection data.

References

Duivenvoorde, W. Van 2015. *Dutch East India Company (VOC) Shipbuilding: The Archaeological Study of Batavia and Other Seventeenth-Century VOC Ships* (pp. 157–161). Ed Rachal Series in Nautical Archaeology. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.

Lukut Museum. (n.d.). Department of Museums Malaysia. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.jmm.gov.my/en/museum/lukut-museum>.

[Muzium Negara, Malaysia \(National Museum, Kuala Lumpur\)](#)

The National Museum of Malaysia, located in Kuala Lumpur. The Museum was a principal partner in the investigation of the VOC *Risdam* and *Nassau* wrecks.

Shipwreck material features in their '[Malay Kingdoms](#)' gallery showcasing ceramics found on wrecks; and 'Dutch' material features in their '[Colonial Era](#)' gallery. The full scope of holdings is unclear. Thousands of artefacts were raised from *Nassau* but information on their whereabouts and scope is scarce (OOI Keat Gin, 2015, p. 11). The shipwreck's excavation was undertaken with a permit for commercial salvage (Transea) and has not been fully published.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Nassau* (1606) – artefacts from the 1995 excavations, such as heavily damaged armament and artillery, burnt sections of vessel and fittings, and numismatics (Bound, 1998).
- *Risdam* (1727) – artefacts seized from looting at the site, and subsequent archaeological investigation. Summary in Green (1986) notes local storage jars, ingots of tin and lead, elephant tusks, sappanwood, Dutch bricks, a pulley block, and miscellaneous fragments of glass, porcelain and white and blue ceramics, Bartmann jugs and a shoe.

Collection Access: none known.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Malaysian Maritime Archaeology Exhibition, opened 15 November 2001.

References

Bound, M. (1997). The Dutch East Indiaman 'Nassau.' *Minerva*, 8(5), 28–32.

Bound, M., Ong Soo Hin, & Pickford, N. (1998). The Dutch East Indiaman 'Nassau', lost at the Battle of Cape Rachado, Straits of Malacca. In M. Bound (Ed.), *Excavating ships of war* (pp. 84–105). Anthony Nelson.

Brown, R. M., & Sjostrand, S. (2001). *Maritime archaeology and shipwreck ceramics in Malaysia*. Published on the occasion of the exhibition Malaysian Maritime Archaeology by Dept. of Museums & Antiquities in collaboration with Nanhai Marine Archaeology Sdn. Bhd.

Green, J. N. (1986). The Survey of the VOC fluit *Risdam* (1727), Malaysia. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 15(2), 93–104.

Green, J. N., & Gangadharam, E. V. (1985). The Survey of the V.O.C. Fluit *Risdam* (1727), Malaysia. WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports No. 25. WA Museum.

OOI Keat Gin. (2015). Maritime Treasures off Peninsula Malaysia. *Journal of Indo-Pacific Archaeology*, 36, 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.7152/jipa.v36i0.14910>.

Van Duivenvoorde, W. 2015. *Dutch East India Company (VOC) Shipbuilding: The Archaeological Study of Batavia and Other Seventeenth-Century VOC Ships* (pp. 157–161, 180–183). Ed Rachal Series in Nautical Archaeology. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.

Welcome to the National Museum of Malaysia. (n.d.). Muzium Negara. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.muziumnegara.gov.my/en>.

Mauritius

[Blue Penny Museum, Mauritius Commercial Bank](#)

Art and history museum named for its distinct stamp collection, located in Port Louis, Mauritius. The Museum was founded by the Mauritius Commercial Bank in 2001. Exhibitions include 'The Age of Discovery' and 'The Island Builders' regarding the navigation that led to the discovery of Mauritius and the colonial history of the island.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Banda* (1615) – exhibitions include ceramics retrieved from *Banda* (Arnim, 2003).

Other Relevant Collections

The Museum possibly holds documentary and cartographic material regarding 'discovery' and colonial periods on the island.

Collection Access: none known, and no photography is allowed of the collections.

References

Arnim, Y. von (2003). *'Kraak' porcelain from the shipwreck Banda (1615) recovered by Jacques Dumas in 1979*. Mauritius Museums Council; Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Blue Penny Museum | Art & History of Mauritius. (n.d.). Blue Penny Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://bluepenny.museum>.

Blue Penny Museum. (n.d.). *MoMAA Museum of Modern African Art*. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://momaa.org/directory/blue-penny-museum/>.

[National History Museum of Mauritius](#) and [Frederik Hendrik Museum](#), Mauritius Museums Council

The National History Museum at Mahebourg and the Frederik Hendrik Museum at the Vieux Grand Port Historic Site are both run by the Mauritius Museums Council.

The National History Museum focuses on the social and cultural history of Mauritius, in particular, the successive colonisation by the Dutch, French and English. The first-floor Dutch sections features ‘early maps of the Indian Ocean and Mauritius’ as well as artefacts from the shipwreck *Banda*.

The Frederik Hendrik Museum focuses on the historic site, which is recognised as a site of National Heritage, built on the ruins of the original Dutch Fort Frederik Hendrik and has been subject to archaeological investigations (Floore & Jayasena, 2003). The exhibition features artefacts from the 400 years of occupation and use of the site.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Banda* (1615) – blue and white Ming dynasty ceramics (von Arnim 2003) and a Portuguese Astrolabe.
- *Geünieerde Provinciën* (1615) [?] – wrecked with *Banda*, the ceramic is noted in Ostkamp (2014, p. 84) as consisting exclusively of shards. It is not clear whether Ostkamp is referring to is held by the National History Museum or in private hands.

Other Relevant Collections: historic artefacts from the excavation of the Dutch Fort Frederik Hendrik.

Collection Access: none known.

Note: [Stefania Manfio](#) has been creating an Underwater Cultural Heritage database for the Mauritius Government as part of her PhD research.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- A temporary exhibition organised for the Mauritius Institute’s centenary celebration included objects salvaged by Jacques Dumas from *Banda* and *Speaker* (a pirate ship) (Tirvengadam, 1983, p. 56).

References

Arnim, Y. von (2003). ‘*Kraak*’ porcelain from the shipwreck *Banda* (1615) recovered by Jacques Dumas in 1979. Mauritius Museums Council; Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Arnim, Y. von (2015, July). Le quadri-centenaire de la mort de Pieter Both et les vestiges du naufrage de sa flotte à Maurice. *Diodon. Bulletin du Mauritius Marine Conservation Society*, 36(1), 12–16.

Arnim, Y. von (2023). *Artefacts from the Banda, a Dutch East Indiaman wrecked at Mauritius in 1615, a shipwreck artefact catalogue*. Mauritius Museums Council and Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Floore, P. M., & Jayasena, R. M. (Eds.). (2003). Historical Archaeology of Fort Frederik Hendrik, a Dutch East India Company outpost at Mauritius: A report on the 1997-2003 excavation seasons. *Hollandia*, 37. Zaandijk, NL: Hollandia Archeologen. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26506.59841>.

Frederik Hendrik Museum. (n.d.). Mauritius Museums Council. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://mauritiusemuseums.govmu.org/mauritiusemuseums/?page_id=1822.

National History Museum. (n.d.). Mauritius Museums Council. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://mauritiusemuseums.govmu.org/mauritiusemuseums/?page_id=1843.

Ostkamp, S. (2014). The Dutch 17th-century porcelain trade from an archaeological perspective. In J. van Campen & T. M. Eliëns (Eds.), *Chinese and Japanese porcelain for the Dutch Golden Age* (pp. 53–85). Waanders Uitgevers, in collaboration with Rijksmuseum Amsterdam; Gemeentemuseum Den Haag; Groninger Museum; Keramiekmuseum Princessehof.

Tirvengadam, D. D. (1983). The *Saint-Géran*: From literary myth to museum object. *Museum International*, 35(1), 54–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0033.1983.tb00426.x>.

The Netherlands

Amsterdam Museum

Museum for the city of Amsterdam with over 100,000 objects, focusing on art and heritage. Includes archaeological material and collections from the VOC period, particularly the Amsterdam chamber of the VOC.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – ceramics including [a jug](#) and another [with concretion](#), and a sample of [peppercorns](#).
- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – a [Bartmann jug](#), another [with mercury](#), a [tin jug/tankard](#), a [tin dish](#), and [samples of mercury](#) from the wreck.
- *De Liefde* (1711) – [loading chambers](#) of cannon.
- *Hollandia* (1743) – a tin [beaker](#) and a [wine bottle](#).
- *Amsterdam* (1749) – [a glass](#) recovered in the 19th century from the wreck.

Note: possibility that some attribution of *Prinses Maria* and *Hollandia* confused as both ‘Scilly-eilanden schipbreuk’, e.g. contradiction between description and exhibition text for this [wine bottle](#).

Other Relevant Collections

- Ship model (historic) – [De Halve Maan](#).
- Replica shipwreck artefacts – [wine bottle](#) from *Amsterdam*, and [Astrolabes](#) from *Batavia*.
- Art – predominantly prints and paintings of VOC individuals, places and ships, including an [allegory of the Amsterdam Chamber of the VOC](#) painted for its 100th anniversary.
- VOC items/commissions – some bearing VOC insignia such as a [chalice glass](#) depicting the Admiraal de Ruyter.
- Armament – examples of VOC cannon.

Collection Access

- [Online collection portal](#).
- [Collectie Nederland](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: Content is copyright Amsterdam Museum. Majority of images are CC0 or Public Domain.

References

Amsterdam Museum. (n.d.). Amsterdam Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.amsterdammuseum.nl/>.

[Museum Batavialand](#)

A museum and experience park that celebrates and communicates the history, culture and mentality of the Dutch between land and sea. The Museum showcases the commercial activity of Flevoland and the Zuiderzee, and the related ongoing archaeological and conservation work. The Museum includes the Maritiem Archeologisch Depot, with small objects held in Lelystad and larger objects in Amersfoort.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- [Maritieme Vondsten](#)/Maritieme rijkscollectie collection – managed on behalf of the [Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed](#) (see listing in this document). Beyond the VOC ships, much of this collection features ships and boats of Flevoland found through the reclamation of the Wieringermeer and the Noordoostpolder, and therefore provide a wider context to the maritime industry of which the VOC was part.
- [‘Losse vondsten’](#) – c. 1,000 ‘loose finds’.

Other Relevant Collections

- Modern full-scale reconstruction of *Batavia*.
- Collection of [ship models](#) (modern).
- [Foto’s maritieme archeologie](#) – photographic archives documenting excavations, investigations, and finds, particularly of [Rob](#) and a few of [Amsterdam](#).
- Audio-visual archive – includes recordings of [Rob \(BZN3\)](#).
- [Scheepsarcheologische tekeningen](#) – archaeological drawings.
- Reference collections – literature on maritime archaeology of the 16th to 19th centuries.

Collection Access

- [Collectie Nederland](#): refine Dataprovider value to ‘Batavialand’.
- Audio-visual digitised by [Beeld & Geluid](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland [API](#): no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- Digital Heritage Network data register: data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.
 - [Archive](#)
 - [Books](#)
 - [Collections](#)
 - [Documents](#)
- [DANS](#) Data Station Archaeology: digitised documentation on specific maritime excavations held by Batavialand. Note their reference by location - either agricultural plot codes, or for those outside of Flevoland, city or other location name.

Licensing: data shared in Collectie Nederland is ‘In Copyright’.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Reconstruction of Batavia](#) (1985-1995).

References

Bezoek Batavialand, het museum van Flevoland, te Lelystad. (n.d.). Batavialand. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.batavialand.nl/>.

Maritime Archaeological Depot. (n.d.). Batavialand. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://www.batavialand.nl/kennis-en-collecties/maritiem-archeologisch-depot>.

De Nederlandsche Bank (DNB), [Nationale Numismatische Collectie](#)

A collection resulting from the combination of the collections of the National Museum of Coins and Medals (Rijksmuseum Het Koninklijk Penningkabinet), Dutch Mint Museum, and the Netherlands Bank collections as the Money and Bank Museum in 2004, but which were transferred back into the possession of the DNB after the closure of the Museum in 2013.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The collection holds approximately 4,400 items, mostly silver coins and ingots, from the following VOC ships.

- *Kampen* (1627)
- *Vergulde Draak* (1656)
- *Merestein* (1702)
- *De Liefde* (1711)
- *Zuiddorp* (1712)
- *Akerendam* (1725)
- *Vliegent Hert* (1735)
- *Rooswijk* (1740)
- *Hollandia* (1743)

Note: the collection should include a gold bar from *Leimuïden* (1770). It was stolen in 2000 from the Rijksmuseum Het Koninklijk Penningkabinet.

Other Relevant Collections

The DNB includes an extensive record of all moneys and medals issued and circulated in the Netherlands, including those under the authority of the VOC, and reference to forms of exchange in other countries, e.g. cowrie shells.

Collection Access

- [NNC collection database](#).
- [Collectie Nederland](#). Note that the provenance is not noted in portal description information, making search for shipwreck material difficult – e.g. search for ‘Rooswijk’ returns null, but ‘[before January 9, 1740](#)’ returns over 200 silver bars.
- The NUMIS database, also administered by the DNB, is a register of coin/hoard finds for the Netherlands.

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland [API](#): no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: In copyright.

References

Bijzonder geld: De Nationale Numismatische Collectie. (n.d.). De Nederlandsche Bank. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.dnb.nl/betalen/bijzonder-geld-de-nationale-numismatische-collectie/>.

[Groninger Museum](#)

A museum of art, design, and art history, with a collecting focus on Asian ceramics, located in Groningen, the Netherlands.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – a few blue and white ceramic items.
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – c. 180 records including a complete set of all ceramic types from *Geldermalsen* wreck, as well as broken pieces and sherds (Gaillard et al., 2019).
- ‘Hatcher Junk’ (1646) – c. 70 records of blue and white ceramic (‘Hatcher Collectie’).
- ‘Cà Mau Shipwreck’ (1725) – c. 45 records of ceramic (‘Collectie Cà Mau Chinees export-porcelain’).

Other Relevant Collections

- Artworks using sherds from *Geldermalsen* wreck by contemporary ceramicist [Diane KW](#) for the exhibition ‘At World's End’ (2014).
- A small number of general VOC period goods and art (textiles, portraiture, prints, a company chest) also feature as part of the art collections.

Collection Access

- [Collectie Groningen](#)
- [Collectie Nederland](#)
- [Aziatische Keramiek](#) Collecties

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: Rights reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [At World's End](#), 31 January – 27 April 2014.

References

Aziatische Keramiek—Platform voor liefhebbers van Aziatische Keramiek. (n.d.). Aziatische Keramiek. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.aziatiskeramiek.nl/>.

Groninger Museum. (n.d.). Groninger Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.groningermuseum.nl/en/>.

Clark, G. (2014, February 17). Diane KW: At World's End. *CFile - Contemporary Ceramic Art + Design*. <https://cfileonline.org/exhibition-diane-kw-worlds-end/>.

Gaillard, K., Berg, E. van den, & Keramiekmuseum Princessehof (Eds.). (2019). *Gezonken schatten: vondsten uit scheepswrakken van de maritieme zijderoute 800-1900 = Sunken treasures: discoveries in shipwrecks from the maritime silk road 800-1900*. Waanders Uitgevers.

Griffith, L. & Diane KW. (2014, February 17). Leza Griffith Interviews Diane KW about At World's End. *CFile - Contemporary Ceramic Art + Design*. <https://cfileonline.org/interview-leza-griffith-interviews-diane-kw-worlds-end/>.

Hille van Dieren Collection, [Wrakkenmuseum](#) (Wreck Museum De Boerderij)

Shipwreck museum on the island of Terschelling, the Netherlands, based on the personal collection of the owner and wreck diver Hille van Dieren. There is a focus on the Island of Terschelling, but artefacts from VOC ships do feature as well.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Rob* (1640) – lead linked shot, tap, whetstone, parcelled rope, blue-and-white porcelain plates, tin plates, glass onion bottles (partial), tin cup, tin spoon, ‘vuurtest’ and fragments of French Santoigne green-glazed earthenware, wooden lid of a possible chart tube, and tool handles.
- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – wooden awl/tool handle, Bartmann Jug and lead munition.
- *Merestein* (1702) – golden button and coins.
- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – pipe masher.
- *Akerendam* (1725) – a golden ducat.
- *Vliegende Hert* (1735) – coins, including [a golden ducat](#), coin concretion, onion bottle and lice comb.
- *Rooswijk* (1740) – silver bar.
- *Hollandia* (1743) – coins.
- *Amsterdam* (1749) – replica ointment jar.
- *Brederode* (1785) – coins.

Note: communication with Hille van Dieren suggests that he has coins from many of the discovered VOC shipwrecks.

Collection Access: none known.

References

Wrakkenmuseum Terschelling. (n.d.). Wrakkenmuseum Terschelling. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://wrakkenmuseum.nl/>.

[Keramiemuseum Princessehof \(Princessehof Leeuwarden, Nationaal Keramiemuseum\)](#)

The national ceramics museum for the Netherlands, dedicated to the appreciation and value of ceramics across the world, with collections across 'East and West' and all time periods. Founded by Nanne Ottema in 1917 (note also Ottema-Kingma Stichting listed in this document).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

Shipwreck items and VOC period traded ceramics feature as part of the scope of collecting but are not overtly visible in the description of the collection.

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – a few ceramic items.
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – a few ceramic items (also described as 'Nanking Cargo').
- *Hatcher Junk* (1646) – a few ceramic items.

Other Relevant Collections

A small number of general VOC period ceramics that would have been the target of trade for or collection by the European market, some with monogram.

Collection Access

- [Online collections](#): note search by wreck not effective.
- [Collectie Nederland](#): better for provenance search.
- [Aziatische Keramiek](#) Collecties.

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Gezonken Schatten](#) / Sunken Treasures, 2019-2020.

References

Aziatische Keramiek—Platform voor liefhebbers van Aziatische Keramiek. (n.d.). Aziatische Keramiek. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.aziatischekeramiek.nl/>.

The Princessehof. (n.d.). Keramiek Museum Princessehof. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://princessehof.nl/undefined>.

Gaillard, K., Berg, E. van den, & Keramiemuseum Princessehof (Eds.). (2019). *Gezonken schatten: vondsten uit scheepswrakken van de maritieme zijderoute 800-1900 = Sunken treasures: discoveries in shipwrecks from the maritime silk road 800-1900*. Waanders Uitgevers.

[Kunstmuseum Den Haag](#)

An art museum located in The Hague with diverse collections, especially regarding modern and contemporary art, and an Asian ceramic collection.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Amsterdam* (1749) – [glass wine bottle](#) (Object number: 1005175).

Other Relevant Collections

- VOC commissioned art and furnishings, for example, [box with VOC monogram](#), manufactured Batavia).
- Items that were the subject of trade and collection, such as [Indonesian Silver](#) and Asian ceramics. Note: no provenance information in the online collections to suggest any of the Asian ceramics have come from shipwreck sites.

Collection Access

- [Online collection portal](#)
- [Aziatische Keramiek](#): Asian ceramics only.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: no clear statement. Assume All Rights Reserved.

References

Aziatische Keramiek—Platform voor liefhebbers van Aziatische Keramiek. (n.d.). Aziatische Keramiek. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.aziatischekeramiek.nl/>.

Kunstmuseum Den Haag—Hét museum voor moderne kunst in Nederland—Te Den Haag. (n.d.). Kunstmuseum Den Haag. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.kunstmuseum.nl/nl>.

[Maritiem Museum Rotterdam/Maritime Museum Rotterdam](#)

Maritime Museum in the port of Rotterdam with collections relevant to the ‘six centuries of Dutch maritime history.’ Boasts ‘Over a million objects from Dutch maritime history from the end of the 15th century to today.’

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – holds several bronze [‘knechtschift’](#) wheels/disks (rigging sheave?) from the wreck.
- *Lastdrager* (1653) – two bronze [map dividers](#) (kaartpasser), and a number of [spring shot](#) (artillery).
- *Zuidorp* (1712) – coins: a [Tweestuiverstuk](#) and a [schelling](#).
- *Geldermalsen* (1750) – boxed [porcelain plate](#).

Other Relevant Collections

- Impressive collection of maps/charts and manuscript documents/published accounts, including:
 - [Corpus Christi Collection](#): VOC charts, including those by Joan Blaeu.
 - Coastal profiles painted by Victor Victorszoon from the De Vlamingh expedition, e.g. [Kustprofiel westkust van Australië](#).
 - An impressive collection of wereldkaart ‘wall maps’, including [Willem Blaeu’s 1645 World Map](#) that improves Willem Jansz’s by giving the detail of Tasman’s discoveries.
 - A first edition, vellum bound, Jan Huygen van Linschoten’s *Itinerario* – known as the ‘Key to the East’ for the information it made available about the Portuguese to the Dutch.
- Ship models (historic), including:
 - 18th century [Padmos/Blijdorp model](#), likely used as an ornament for the VOC
 - historic model of [Vergulde Draak](#) (17th/18th century).
- Artworks depicting VOC people, ships and places, and descriptions of their activities and encounters, including:
 - Depiction of the [Company Yard at Batavia](#).
 - Prints from Cornelis de Bruins published travel account, which include depictions of a kangaroo, and a [‘Zuidlander’](#) who was one of four who were in Batavia in 1706 and then returned to their country.
- Examples of [tableware](#) and furnishings, and belongings of or for VOC individuals, such as an [inscribed tobacco tin](#) in memory of VOC skipper Jan Huijssen.
- Note: [photographs of salvage operations in 1963](#) depict ‘Australian divers show coins that have surfaced, which may come from the wreck of the Dutch ship *Vergulde Draak*’.

Collection Access

- Online [database](#) (Adlib): tad glitchy for filtering/refining searches.
- Collections also exhibited on [Google Arts and Culture](#).

Collection Data Sharing: no bulk data export available.

Licensing: no statements provided. Presume All Rights Reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- 'How we ditched the Dutch: De kaping van de laatste VOC-vloot', 7 October 2017-3 June 2018.
- 'De Kleurrijke Wereld van de VOC' (The Colourful World of the VOC), 16 March-15 September 2002.
- Project [Verborgten Kaart](#) [Hidden Map] – possible VOC chart used to bind Johannes van Keulen's 1753 atlas 'De nieuwe groote lichtende zee-fakkels' (with the Rijksmuseum).

References

Akveld, Leo M., and Els M. Jacobs. *De Kleurrijke Wereld van de VOC : Nationaal Jubileumboek VOC, 1602-2002* [The Colourful World of the VOC: National Anniversary Book VOC, 1602-2002]. Bussom, Netherlands: Thoth, 2002.

Maritiem Museum Rotterdam—Ontdek de enorme invloed van de maritieme wereld op ons dagelijks leven. (n.d.). Maritiem Museum Rotterdam. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://maritiemmuseum.nl/>.

Project 'Verborgten kaart': Versmelten van de wetenschappen. (n.d.). Maritiem Museum Rotterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://maritiemmuseum.nl/onderzoek/project-verborgen-kaart>.

[Museon Omniversum](#)

A multi-disciplinary collection of three departments focusing on 'Culture', 'Nature' and 'Technology', located in The Hague.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – [Silver Spanish 'mat'](#) from Mexico.

Other Relevant Collections: Numismatic collections feature coins with VOC insignia.

Collection Access

- 'Collectiesite Museon' [Online platform](#)
- [Collectie Nederland](#)

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: No clear statement, assume All Rights Reserved.

References

Museon-Omniversum. (n.d.). Museon Omniversum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museon-omniversum.nl/>.

[Museum Joure](#)

A manufacturing museum – located on a former industrial estate in Joure. The four manufacturing focuses or ‘routes’ of the Museum are coffee and tea of Douwe Egberts, Frisian clockmaking, a metalware factory, and a print shop showcasing early twentieth century book-making techniques. The presence of shipwreck material in this collection seems tied to the exhibition of coffee and tea in relation to Douwe Egberts.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – ceramic tea pot and tea cups with saucers.

Collection Access

- [Collectie Nederland](#)

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: Rights are reserved.

References

Museum Joure, daar maak je het! (n.d.). Museum Joure. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museumjoure.nl/en/>.

[Nederlands Zilvermuseum, Schoonhoven](#)

A museum in Schoonhoven, the ‘silver city’, that specialises in the collection and exhibition of silver, with a permanent collection of Dutch silverware dating from 1600 to the present.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Bredenhof* (1752) – [three silver bars](#).

Collection Access: [Collectie Online](#).

Collection Data Sharing: Rights are reserved.

References

Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven. (n.d.). Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://zilvermuseum.com/>.

Zilverbaren van de VOC. (n.d.). *Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven*. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://zilvermuseum.com/bezoek/zilverbaren-van-de-voc/>.

[Ottema-Kingma Stichting \(Private Collection\)](#)

A collection originally created by Nanne Ottema and Grietje Kingma. The Foundation aims to collect and make available objects and collections that are important in some way to Friesland, the Netherlands.

The collection is almost entirely loaned out to public collections for exhibition so there may be overlap between what is listed here and in other collections, e.g. Keramiekmuseum Princessehof.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – a couple of ceramic items (currently loaned to Keramiekmuseum Princessehof).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – a few ceramic items (currently loaned to Keramiekmuseum Princessehof).
- *Hatcher Junk* (1646) – c. 35 records of ceramic (currently loaned to Keramiekmuseum Princessehof).
- ‘Vüing Tàu shipwreck’ (1690) – at least one goblet (currently loaned to Keramiekmuseum Princessehof).

Other Relevant Collections

- Prints (e.g. [print depicting Dejima](#) and another of [Surat](#)) and maps (e.g. [map of Jaffna](#)) depicting VOC ships and places.
- Ceramics traded by the VOC or made for the VOC (with [VOC monogram](#) or subject).
- Examples of linen traded to Europe.
- The Jan de With (VOC commander) [ivory flower ship](#) sourced from Canton.

Collection Access: [Collection database](#) – usefully notes which institutions the collections are currently loaned to.

Collection Data Sharing: None known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved, see [colophon](#).

References

OKS - Ottema-Kingma Stichting. (n.d.). OKS - Ottema-Kingma Stichting. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.oks.nl/>.

[Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed \(RCE\) – National Cultural Heritage Agency, Netherlands \(CHAN\)](#)

Government department that is part of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. Involved in legislation implementation, regulations and heritage policy, as well as developing applicable knowledge and providing advice on national monuments, archaeology and moveable heritage, including Maritime Heritage.

Since 1993, the National Museums are independent, and the National Collections (Rijkscollectie) are loaned to these museums. In this way the National Collections of the Netherlands are managed by institutions but owned by the State. The National Collections and content data shared by RCE therefore overlaps with that of Netherlands institutions which house and manage the collections.

The Rijkscollectie scheepsarcheologie – also known as Maritieme vondsten and Maritiem rijkscollectie – is one such national collection. While it is listed here, it is important to note that this collection is currently housed and managed by Museum Batavialand, Lelystad (see listing in this document).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Rijkscollectie scheepsarcheologie collection comprises over 30,000 shipwreck artefacts accumulated through maritime archaeological investigations across the Netherlands and on Dutch ships globally. VOC shipwrecks represented in the collection include:

- *Rob* [BZN3] (1640) – [4 records](#) including remains of a cannon support.
- *Rooswijk* (1740) – currently only [256 records](#). Study and documentation of collection from excavations are ongoing (artefacts transferred to Lelystad from the UK November 2023 and still undergoing conservation and analysis).
- *Buitenzorg* (1770) – [122 records](#), notably parts of vessel, fixtures and fittings. Also armament and artillery, cargo/ballast, and clothing & personal items (especially shoes).
- *Amsterdam* (1749) – wood (dendrochronological) samples; note also that items from the activity of the Stichting VOC-schip Amsterdam are currently in the custody of the Faculty of Archaeology, University of Leiden and will join the collection at Lelystad when storage facility upgrades complete.

Note: there is also a collection of c.1000 loose finds ([Losse vondsten](#)).

VOC shipwreck objects that were acquired through salvage agreements (a past practice that is no longer supported by RCE) are held and exhibited by other national institutions. Therefore, while they technically form part of the Rijkscollectie scheepsarcheologie, they are not part of the Batavialand/Lelystad material (Maritieme rijkscollectie, Museum Batavialand) and therefore not included here.

Other Relevant Collections

- Reference library and archives.
- [Reports](#) and [Theses](#).

Collection Access

- [Collecties RCE portal](#): search across RCE library, archaeological reports, and collections (photos, plans, prints and maritime finds). Collections are not digitised – no preview.
- [Collectie Nederland](#): Batavialand ‘Maritieme vondsten’ and ‘Foto’s maritieme archeologie’ collections.
- [Beeldbank](#)/Image bank: photographs and drawings of heritage, including many items from shipwrecks.
- [Het Geheugen](#): a selection of maritime items from the Rijkscollectie scheepsarcheologie photographed and made available as collection ‘[Verzonken schatten](#)’. This is a static, standalone set of collection data.

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland [API](#): no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- Digital Heritage Network data register: ‘Maritieme Archeologische Rijkscollectie’ OAI-PMH API and SPARQL endpoint.
 - [Articles](#)
 - [Books](#)
 - [Technical drawings](#)
 - [Photographs](#)
 - [Finds](#)

Licensing: Data is ‘In Copyright’ and an agreement is required for use.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [MACHU](#): Maritime Cultural Heritage Underwater GIS interface for the location of shipwrecks and associated data, at first focused on the Netherlands, but now including Dutch shipwrecks elsewhere in the world. Registration required for access.
- [MaSS](#): Mapping maritime heritage. International Dutch maritime heritage site GIS (shipwrecks through to drowned landscapes), partnering with Nautical Archaeological Digital Library. Data available through API.
- [Pinas/Witsen Scheepsbouw](#): Inspired by Nicolaes Witsen’s *Aeloude en Hedendaegse Scheepsbouw en Bestier* which described a ‘pinas van 134 voeten’ in detail. This project produced a 3D model of a ‘Pinas’ as a tool for identifying parts of 17th century Dutch ships, with all parts able to be viewed individually in detail.
- [The RCE Thesaurus](#): thesaurus developed and maintained for the consistent description of cultural heritage across RCE activities, specifically focused on archaeology, cultural heritage and registration of monuments (in Dutch).
- 3D models of [Maritime Heritage artefacts](#), made available using Sketchfab.
- [Rooswijk1740](#) project and [online exhibition](#): Includes [Rooswijk Wreck Visual Trail](#), created by UK-contractor MSDS Marine in cooperation with ArtasMedia and CyanSub – an animated self-led ‘tour’ on web-browser allowing the user to click through annotated

points of interest, which gives access to 3D models (embedded Sketchfab) and visual media (including multibeam imagery) from the on-site investigation of areas and objects.

- [Wrecks in Documents](#) (with Huygens ING): referenced dataset of ships that are wrecked in the waters around Texel.
- Wrakkentelling: Regularly updated report of the historic Dutch shipwrecks around the world, including dedicated section for VOC wrecks. [Latest version 2022](#).
- [DANS Data Station Archaeology](#): data repository for Dutch archaeology.
- [Maritiem Portal](#) (with Huygens ING): a portal/information hub for maritime-historical organizations. The site can be searched, or browsed by subject/topic such as '[Collections](#)', '[Exhibitions](#)', '[Publications](#)', and '[Dissertations](#)'.

References

Manders, M., van Dissel, A., Brouwers, W., Fink, M., Spoelstra, J., de Hoop, R., Heijink, M., Lemmers, A., Heitz, A., & de Vroomen, O. (2022). *Wrakkentelling: Een kwantitatief onderzoek naar historische Nederlandse scheepswrakken in de wereld* (Revised). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2022/01/01/wrakkentelling-2022>.

Rijksdienst Cultureel Erfgoed [Cultural Heritage Agency]. (n.d.). Rijksdienst Cultureel Erfgoed. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://english.cultureelerfgoed.nl/>.

Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Huygens Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis, & Quist, T. (2018, June 18). *De Rooswijk, een virtuele tentoonstelling* [The Rooswijk, a virtual exhibition] [Exhibits]. Huygens Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis. <http://rooswijk.huygens.knaw.nl/>.

[Rijksmuseum](#)

The National Museum of the Netherlands, located in Amsterdam. Predominantly an art collection, with a focus on art history including the applied arts of Europe and Asia, but also the history of the Netherlands from the Middle Ages.

A seeming anomaly from the predominant focus on aesthetic material is the collection of VOC shipwreck material, collected in the 1970s and 1980s. These were acquired to complement the privileged or institutional VOC collections with a more holistic snapshot of their operations and people involved (Rijksmuseum, 1980), as well as to ensure that the material being salvaged from wrecks was at least somewhat represented in Dutch institutions at a time when there was no Government appetite for claiming them as heritage (Brugge, 2018).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Rijksmuseum has acquired shipwreck artefacts from nine VOC *retourschips* and one intra-Asian vessel through agreement with salvers in the 1970s and 1980s before the change in relevant policy and legislation towards the protection of Underwater Cultural Heritage, or through donation and purchase.

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – [c. 1100 records](#), notably ceramic and other cargo, such as pepper.
- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – [c. 40 records](#), an assortment of ship parts, ballast, tableware, lead plate and armament/artillery.
- *Merestein* (1702) – [c. 30 records](#), across ship inventory, armament/artillery and clothing/personal effects – quite fragmentary.
- *De Liefde* (1711) – [a single dukaton](#) (coin).
- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – [4 records](#) for a chest with silver bars.
- *Vliegent Hert* (1735) – [c. 500 records](#), an assortment of vessel fittings/fixtures, ship inventory, tools and equipment, clothing and personal items, and cargo/ballast, and some skeletal remains. Much fragmentary.
- *Boot* (1738) – [2 records](#) for paint wood.
- *Hollandia* (1743) – [over 3,000 records](#) across an assortment of vessel fittings/fixtures, ship inventory, tools and equipment (particularly fine example of a set of drawing instruments in a case), clothing and personal items, and cargo/ballast (note: Gawroński et al., 1992).
- *Zeelelie* (1795) – [6 records](#) of cargo/ballast (roofing tiles) and ship inventory (pots). However, some ceramic material may be mixed up with that of the *Witte Leeuw* (see results from this [search](#)).
- ‘Hatcher Junk’ (1646) – [blue and white ceramics](#) (these are part of the [Royal Asian Art Society in the Netherlands](#) Collection, on loan to the Rijksmuseum since 1952).

Other Relevant Collections

- The [Dirk Hartog Plate](#): left at Inscription Point in Western Australia, retrieved by Willem de Vlamingh.
- Art, such as:
 - Portraiture of VOC individuals.
 - Depictions of VOC assets, people and places, such as the drawings from the [Album of Jan Brandes](#).

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- Commissions, such as the [work of Pieter Cornelius de Bevere](#) commissioned by Joan Gideon Loten as Governor of Ceylon from 1752 to 1757.
- Applied arts, such as:
 - Goods commissioned by VOC or individuals/families employed by or associated with VOC, e.g. [set of plates](#), [chest of nine bottles](#).
 - Goods representative of VOC trade, or ‘Company Art’ and curios – the works of art and items from Asia that came to the Netherlands, not necessarily by or for the VOC but facilitated by the Company’s activity in Asia (Campen, et al. 2011), e.g. [ceramics](#), [metalwork](#), and [textiles](#).
- Models of VOC ships (historic), such as of [Prins Willem](#) and [Mercurius](#), as well as places, such as a 19th century large model of [Deshima](#) Island.

Collection Access: <https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/search>. At the time of finalising this report, the Museum was in the process of transitioning from Rijkstudio to the ‘Collection Online’.

100% of the collections are reported as documented and available online, though not all have accompanying images.

Collection is also available through [Europeana](#) and [RCE Netherlands Collections](#) portal.

Collection Data Sharing

- [Rijksmuseum Data Services](#) – note this information was current at the time of finalising this report but the transition to the Collection Online will affect options/functionality as it is built on a new infrastructure.
 - API – only basic information about each object and results returned up to 100 at a time but limited to 10,000, in json. Allows search using same parameters as ‘advanced search’ in Rijkstudio.
 - Harvest – full data export using OIA-PMH API (xml format in lido, EDM or DC).
 - Download – full dataset but with varying richness depending on metadata standard (basic DC-xml; rich EDM-rdf/turtle; rich LIDO-xml; basic csv).
- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: The Rijksmuseum operates an Open Data policy. CC0 license – see [data policy](#).

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- ‘[Closer examination of shipwreck finds](#)’, 2018 (Brugge, 2018).
- Project to [conserve metal objects](#) from shipwrecks in partnership with Nationaal Archief, University of Western Australia, Western Australian Maritime Museum, University of Zadar.
- ‘[Dutch Shipbuilding from the 17th to the 19th century: material cultures and global influences](#)’, supported by the Mellon Foundation.
- ‘De Nederlandse ontmoeting met Azië, 1600–1950’ [The Dutch encounter with Asia, 1600-1950], October 2002.

- ‘Holland en Japan, 400 jaar handel’ [Holland and Japan, 400 years of trade], 11 February-25 May 2009.
- ‘Prijs der zee. Vondsten uit wrakken van Nederlandse Oost-Indiëvaarders uit de zeventiende en achttiende eeuw in de verzameling van de afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis van het Rijksmuseum’, 6 February-3 August 1980.
- ‘Azië > Amsterdam. Luxe in de Gouden Eeuw / Asia in Amsterdam: The Culture of Luxury in the Golden Age’, with the Peabody Essex Museum, 17 October 2015-17 January 2016.
- ‘Slavery: the story of João, Wally, Oopjen, Paulus, van Bengalen, Surapati, Sapali, Tula, Dirk, Lohkay’, 5 June-29 August 2021.

References

- B. K. [Bas Kist], J., & Sténuît, R. (1977). De ‘Witte Leeuw’. De schipbreuk van een schip van de v.o.c. In 1613 en het onderwateronderzoek naar het wrak in 1976. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 25(4), 163–178.
- Brugge, J. ter. (2018). *Wrakvondsten in het Rijksmuseum: Evaluatie en koersbepaling voor de toekomst* [Notitie van de afdeling geschiedenis]. Rijksmuseum.
- Campen, J. van, Hartkamp-Jonxis, E., & Rijksmuseum. (2011). *Asian splendour: Company art in the Rijksmuseum*. Walburg Pers.
- Corrigan, K., Campen, J. van, Diercks, F., Blyberg, J. C., Peabody Essex Museum, & Rijksmuseum (Netherlands) (Eds.). (2015). *Asia in Amsterdam: The culture of luxury in the Golden Age*. Peabody Essex Museum ; Rijksmuseum.
- Gawroński, J., Kist, B., & Stokvis-Van Boetzelaer, O. (1992). *Hollandia compendium: a contribution to the history, archeology, classification and lexicography of a 150 ft. Dutch East Indiaman (1740-1750)*. Rijks Museum; Elsevier.
- Kist, J. B. (1975). Iets over een achttiende-eeuwse draaibas. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 23(2), 99–99.
- Kist, J. B. (1989). Sifflet van zilver, Nederland(?), vóór 1613. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 37(3), 194–197.
- Pijl-Ketel, C. L. van der. (1989). Een olifanten-kendi afkomstig uit het vondstcomplex van de Oostindiëvaarder de ‘Witte Leeuw’, China, vóór 1613. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 37(3), 198–200.
- Rijksmuseum. (1980). *Prijs der zee. Vondsten uit wrakken van Nederlandse Oost-Indiëvaarders uit de zeventiende en achttiende eeuw in de verzameling van de afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis van het Rijksmuseum*. Rijksmuseum.
- Rijksmuseum, hét museum van Nederland*. (n.d.). Rijksmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/nl>.
- Sint Nicolaas, E., & Smeulders, V. (with Rijksmuseum). (2021). *Slavery: The story of João, Wally, Oopjen, Paulus, van Bengalen, Surapati, Sapali, Tula, Dirk, Lohkay*. Atlas contact Rijksmuseum.
- Stevens, H., & Rijksmuseum. (1998). *Dutch enterprise and the VOC, 1602-1799* (S. Herman, Trans.). Walburg Pers for Stichting Rijksmuseum Amsterdam.

Tentoonstelling Afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis: Prijs der Zee: Vondsten uit wrakken van Oostindiëvaarders: 6 februari -1 augustus 1980. (1979). *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 27(4), 212–213.

Van der Pijl–Ketel, C. L., ed. (1982). *The Ceramic Load of the Witte Leeuw (1613)*. Amsterdam: Rijksmuseum.

[Scheepvaart Museum \(Maritime Museum, Netherlands\)](#)

The Dutch national maritime history collection, located in Amsterdam, with a focus on the long and continuing connection of the Dutch and the sea. The Museum features prominently a reproduction of VOC ship *Amsterdam* (opened to the public April 1991) docked outside the Museum building which is used as an exhibition space for the history of the VOC. In 1992 the Museum opened 'Company Hall' – a dedicated space to the history of the VOC (Jacobs, 1991) which features an extensive collection of art, tableware and furnishings, cartography, maritime instruments, ship models, and archives and manuscripts from their collections that reference the VOC and its activity.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The collection contains a modest amount of shipwreck material across a number of wrecks, demonstrating a preference for navigation tools and equipment, such as sounding leads, as well as cannon, pieces of ship structure, and examples of food provisions kept onboard.

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – [1 record](#) for a 'kwadrant of hoekmeter' for use with artillery, no image.
- *Banda* (1615) – [1 record](#) for an astrolabe attributed to *Banda* (see Castro et al. 2020 Marine Astrolabes Catalogue no. 56).
- *Lastdrager* (1653) – 10 records, which include 8 Spanish coins, [a navigation divider](#) and part of an astrolabe.
- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – 7 records, which include lead weights (e.g. [sounding lead](#)) and navigation dividers.
- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – 1 record, [a folding ruler](#).
- *Vliegende Hert* (1735) – 96 records (under 'Vliegend Hart'), the majority items retrieved during the 1988 campaign of Rex Cowan. Includes a [6 pound cannon](#), [fragments of the ship](#), and assorted artefacts across clothing and personal effects, ship inventory, navigation instruments, and artillery.
- *Hollandia* (1743) – 37 records (use 'wrak Hollandia' to search), across assorted artefacts including examples of [silver](#), [pewter](#), and [tin](#) tableware, a [VOC insignia](#) from the cap of a grenadier, assorted lead weights, navigation tools/instruments (including a [sharpening stone](#) for a compass pin), the compass rings from a globe, and a couple of shoe buckles.
- *Amsterdam* (1749) – 56 records (use 'Amsterdam 1749' to search), across assorted artefacts including a good example of a [brass cartridge holder](#), animal remains from what must have been food stores for the voyage, some human remains ([foot bones](#)), and concretions containing fragments.
- *Buitenzorg* (1760) – 6 records (use 'VOC Buitenzorg' to search), including a cartridge holder, a four handled jug, copper plate from the body of the ship, cannonball, and rope.
- *Bredenhof* (1785) – 1 record, [a sounding lead](#).

Other Relevant Collections

Extensive collections that relate to maritime history, and therefore, to the VOC.

- Artwork and technical drawings of ships and places, including objects such as tobacco boxes and [containers](#).
- Tableware and furnishings for the VOC – such as ship chests and glassware.

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- Maps and charts – including, [for example](#), several nautical charts of the Indian Ocean by Isaak de Graaf showing the west coast of Australia, another by [Joan Blaeu](#), and an impressive collection of ‘Wereldkaart’ from the period.
- Manuscripts and published accounts, such as the [scheepsjournaal](#) of the *Zeepaard* and the *Canton*.
- Ship models (historic) of Dutch East Indiamen.
- Commemorative medals and plates.

Collection Access

- Collections accessible through the Museum’s ‘[digitale collectie](#)’: over 350,000 objects and 60,000 books all registered in the database, only c. 50% currently digitised. Note system is slightly glitchy.
- Collections can also be searched through [Maritiem Digitaal](#).
- Het Geheuden: showcases several aspects of the collections, such as [17th century ‘Atlassen’](#), and a selection of [objects](#).

Collection Data Sharing: no data sharing available for this collection.

Licensing: Data appears to be All Rights Reserved, with photographs freely available for download for personal use and research only.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [VOC-ship Amsterdam](#), built 1985, and located at the Museum since 1991.
- ‘De Kleurrijke Wereld van de VOC’, 16 March-27 October 2002.
- ‘Blaeu’s wereld in kaart: meestercartograaf in de Gouden Eeuw’, 14 April 2017-30 September 2018.
- ‘Cartografie & Curiosa’, 10 May 2019-30 December 2025.

References

Akveld, L. M., & Jacobs, E. M. (2002). *De kleurrijke wereld van de VOC: Nationaal Jubileumboek VOC, 1602-2002 [The colourful world of the VOC: National Anniversary Book VOC, 1602-2002]*. Thoth.

Jacobs, Els M. and Nederlands Scheepvaart Museum. *In Pursuit of Pepper and Tea: The Story of the Dutch East India Company*. Zutphen, Amsterdam: Walburg Pers for Nederlands Scheepvaart Museum, 1991.

Het Scheepvaartmuseum | The National Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Het Scheepvaartmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.hetscheepvaartmuseum.com/>.

[Stichting Texels Museum: Museum Kaap Skil](#)

Maritime Museum focused on the island of Texel and the ‘Texel Roads’ – one of the main Dutch anchorages for ships heading to sea between 1500 and 1900. The Museum features information and artefacts from the many shipwrecks of the Wadden Sea.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The collection contains a representation of artefacts from the many shipwrecks located in the Wadden Sea (including unidentified and non-VOC 17th century armed merchants such as BZN2, BZN9, BZN12). These give insight and context to the complex activity of which the VOC was a part, but only one identified VOC wreck features:

- *Rob* (1640) (also known as Burgzand Noord 3/BZN3) – [29 records](#) including a cannon, gunpowder, brandy bowl, oil jar, and numerous coins.

Note: Shipwreck BZN8 ([2 records](#)) was thought to be the *Lelie*, but this is no longer the case (Manders & Kuijper, 2015, p. 146).

Other Relevant Collections

- Scale model of the Texel Roads (Reede van Texel) in the 17th century featuring a plastic ship model of *Amstelland* (1665) and *Oranje*.

Collections portal: <https://www.collectietexelsmuseum.nl/>. Dutch only.

Collection Data Sharing: collections portal seems to have options for pdf and xls export of data records, but permissions appear to be required.

Licensing: No licensing information listed on website – presume All Rights Reserved.

References

Manders, M., & Kuijper, W. (2015). Shipwrecks in Dutch Waters with Botanical Cargo or Victuals. In C. Bakels & H. Kamermans (Eds.), *Excerpta Archaeologica Leidensia* (pp. 141–172). Leiden University.

Stichting Texels Museum. (n.d.). Stichting Texels Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.texelsmuseum.nl/>.

[Wereld Museum Amsterdam, Leiden and Rotterdam \(National Museum of World Cultures\)](#)

The Wereld Museums are the result of what were four separate institutions, the Tropenmuseum, Afrika Museum, Museum Volkenkunde (collectively the Stichting Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen), and Rotterdam's Wereldmuseum (*New Name*, 2023). Their collections of material culture feature or embody 'a human story' from locations around the world, such as coins, artworks, sculpture, and jewellery, including contemporary works of art. Much of this material is from or collected through Dutch colonial interests, including the activity of the VOC, which is reflected upon in their current exhibition 'Onze Koloniale Erfenis' and a current programme of research and repatriation.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – [Jar](#).
- 'Hatcher Junk' (1646) – ceramics: a [bowl](#), and a [table bowl](#).

Other Relevant Collections

Notwithstanding much of the Wereld Museum collections reflect or connect in some way to the activity of the VOC due to the contact and influence the VOC had with cultures across the world (for better or worse), material that is more directly 'VOC' includes:

- Art/prints, such as:
 - [Japanese print of a Dutch merchant, Javanese servant and a Cassowary](#).
 - [Drawings of Jakarta/Batavia by Elias van Stade](#) in the early 18th century, one of which is noted as captioned by Joan van Hoorn, VOC Governor-General 1704-1709.
 - [Painting, 1689, of the camp of VOC Ambassador Johannes Bacherus](#) visiting the traveling court of Mughal emperor Aurangzeb.
- Cartography, such as:
 - The [Mercator-Hondius edition \(1613\) of the 1606 Petrus Plancius map of Ceylon/Sri Lanka](#).
 - Maps by [Willem Blaeu](#).
 - [Map c. 1685 of Africa](#) by Frederik de Wit.

Note that much material collected by the VOC administration in Batavia were passed to the Royal Batavian Society of Arts and Science (archives for this group are held in ANRI – see listing in this document). Many of these items were then transferred to the Netherlands in the twentieth century, and the Wereld Museum received several consignments between 1873-1936 via the Koloniaal Museum, Haarlem (Duivenvoorde et al., 2019, p. 40).

Collection Access

- The Wereld Museums have [a joint collection platform](#) for all museum locations.
- A selection from their collections is made available through [Google Arts & Culture](#).

Collection Data Sharing: a basic collection metadata export to .xlsx file is available through the collection platform.

Licensing

- Digitisation is generally made [CC-BY-SA](#) unless Public Domain or within third-party copyright.
- No clear information regarding reuse of collection data.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Onze Koloniale Erfenis \[Our Colonial Inheritance\]](#), current exhibition.

References

Duivenvoorde, W. van, Wesley, D., Litster, M., Wonu Veys, F., Nayati, W., Polzer, M., McCarthy, J., & Jansen, L. (2019). Van Delft before Cook: The earliest record of substantial culture contact between Indigenous Australians and the Dutch East India company prior to 1770. *Australasian Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, 43, 27–49.

Flores, W., & Modest, W. (2024). *Onze koloniale erfenis* [Our colonial heritage]. Lannoo; Wereldmuseum Amsterdam.

Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen, Amsterdam, Netherlands. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/tropenmuseum>

New name: Wereldmuseum. (2023, October 4). Wereldmuseum Leiden. <https://leiden.wereldmuseum.nl/en/about-wereldmuseum-leiden/press/press-releases/new-name>

Stichting Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen en de Stichting Wereldmuseum Rotterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://collectie.wereldmuseum.nl/#/query/f2185a0b-61e9-41a4-8eed-6533d80c1f11>

Wereldmuseum: Amsterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Amsterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://amsterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

Wereldmuseum: Leiden. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Leiden. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://leiden.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

Wereldmuseum: Rotterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Rotterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://rotterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

[Zeeuws Archief \(Zeeland Archive, Middelburg\)](#)

Archive for the province of Zeeland, that also holds a small collection of objects and artworks. The collections suffered from WW2 bombings and related fires.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Vliegent Hert* (1735) – [golden dukat](#).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [stoneware jug](#), three [Blanc de Chine](#) figurines.

Relevant Series

See the Zeeuws Archief guide to the VOC Collections '[Archiefstukken over de VOC in het Zeeuws Archief \(GIDS23\)](#)' (Doe et al., 2001).

A Parthesius and Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten [report](#) (2014) summarises the main relevant series as follows:

- Surviving archives relate to the 18th century and deal with governance matters and 'Contracts of Correspondence' (bestowing of attractive administrative roles/functions within VOC).
- Four logs of company ships from the beginning of the 18th century:
 - Daily-register from a journey made by the *Orion* from Japan to Batavia, 1714-1716 (ZA, VH 183).
 - The travel reports of *Raadhuis van Middelburg*, 1717-1719 (ZA, VdF 7).
 - The journal of *Noordbeek* on its journey from Batavia to 'het Vlie' in 1718 (ZA, VH 184).
 - Fragment of the journal kept on the flute ship (fluitschip) *Samaritaan* during its journey from Gamron to Cochin in 1729 (ZA, VH 185).
- List of ships wrecked between 1721 and 1741 (missing ships not included) (ZA, MPTvP 263).

Other Relevant Collections and Series

- Family archive of Recueils van Citters (5 inventory numbers amounting to one metre).
- Family archive of Mathias-Pous-Tak van Poortvliet (240 documents concerning the VOC).
- Ship model – 17th century model of [VOC-ship Prins Willem](#).

Collection Access: [online catalogue](#).

Collection Data Sharing: Inventories for archive series, where prepared, can be downloaded as EAD through their '[Open Data](#)' service.

Licensing: Majority of material is made available CC0 unless copyright is held by a third party.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [VOC-handel met Ceylon](#), 12 February 2018-23 April 2020. A photograph exhibition resulting from retracing the historic route that VOC merchant Joris van Spilbergen took in 1602 from Batticaloa to the royal city of Kandy, as well as photographs of 'Dutch Period' items in what was then Ceylon.

- [Scheurboek & Scheepsbesluit. Leven aan boord van een VOC-schip](#), 5 July 2002-11 January 2003. Exhibition demonstrating what life on board a VOC ship would be like.
- [Zeeland en Japan. Eilanden in contact](#), 18 September 2000-3 February 2001. Exhibition commemorating 400 years of trade relations between the Dutch and Japan.

References

Doe, F. van der, Loo, I. J. van, & Schwartz, J. H. F. (Eds.). (2001). *Archiefstukken over de VOC in het Zeeuws Archief (GIDS23)*. Zeeuws Archief. <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/zoekgids/archiefstukken-over-de-voc-in-het-zeeuws-archief/>.

Parthesius, R., & Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten (Centre for International Heritage Activities). (2014). *Inventory and analyses of archival sources in the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives in the Netherlands in order to contribute to possible locations and identification of VOC shipwrecks off the Western Australian Coast* (WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports No. 310). Western Australian Museum Foundation; Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten.

Zeeuws Archief. (n.d.). Zeeuws Archief. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/>.

[Zeeuws Maritiem muZEEum/Zeeland Maritime Museum](#)

Maritime museum of Zeeland, located in Vlissingen. This is a municipal museum for the area – the collections of the former Stedelijk Museum were transferred to the Museum in 2002. The Museum recognises the role ‘water’ has played in the development of the region. Collection includes a very large collection of VOC shipwreck material.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Kampen* (1627) – [62 records](#), which include much fragmentary material across ship inventory and parts of the ship, and personal items, such as buckles, pins and beads.
- *Vliegende Hert* (1735) – [3136 records](#), which include material across parts of the vessel and furnishings, ship inventory, tools and equipment, clothing and personal items and cargo/ballast. Very large collections of single types of things include buckles, lice combs, wine bottles, and fishing net weights. Some very good examples of smuggled money.
- *Reigersbroek* (1738) – [a single record](#) of cowrie shells.
- *Rooswijk* (1740) – [860 records](#), which includes many examples of limited types, such as sabres, knives/blades, pen holders, candle snuffers, curtain rings, spoons, musket balls. A couple of examples of silver bars.
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [57 records](#), including much fragmentary material across ship inventory and personal items which are quite the contrast to the predominantly ceramic collections from this wreck held elsewhere.
- *Bredenhof* (1753) – a [single silver bar](#).
- *Woestduin* (1779) – a [coffee pot and a porcelain fish](#).

Other Relevant Collections

The collections refer to the history of Zeeland/Middelburg generally, which was one of the VOC chambers. Artworks and [ships models](#) in particular directly reference VOC ships, such as a [‘portrait’ of the Slot ter Hoge](#).

Collection Access

The muZEEum does not host its own collection platform, but its collections are available through two aggregate projects. Unfortunately search results do vary slightly if you use one or the other.

- [Maritiem Digitaal](#)
- [Collectie Nederland](#)

Collection Data Sharing

- Collectie Nederland: [API](#) no key required (default json in EDM and DC). No API documentation – but allows same search parameters as within html interface. Can specify number of rows returned (has difficulty over 200).
- [Digital Heritage Network data register](#): data sourced from the RijksData OAI-PMH API in EDM-DC, with SPARQL endpoint.

Licensing: All data available through Collectie Nederland for the muZEEum is tagged as ‘In Copyright’

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Wind in de zeilen](#) [Wind in the sails], 7 September 2020-30 June 2021.
- Note exhibitions at the former Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen:
 - 'T Vliagent Hart 1729-1735: op zoek naar een gezonken schip, 1983.
 - Schatten van het 'TVliagent Hart, 1984.
 - De Zeeuwse VOC boven water, 10 jaar onderzoek naar scheepswrakken, 1992.

References

muZEEum. (n.d.). Maritiem Museum Zeeland. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.muzeem.nl/english>

Weber, W. (2006). A Dutchman no longer knows his own past, the 'tVliagent Hart collection therefore seems to have been hidden in the MuZEEum. In M. Pieters, G. Gevaert, J. Mees, & J. Seys (Eds.), *Colloquium: To sea or not to sea—2nd international colloquium on maritime and fluvial archaeology in the southern North Sea area, Brugge (Belgium), 21-23 September 2006: Book of abstracts* (pp. 87–88). Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ). <https://www.vliz.vlaanderen/en/imis>

[Zeeuws Museum](#)

A history and art museum located in Middelburg, in the historic Middelburg Abbey complex. The collections date back to the establishment of the Royal Zeeland Society of Arts and Sciences in the 18th century (which are held on loan).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [11 records](#), including the [ship's bell](#) gifted by Michael Hatcher (Edwards, 2000), porcelain figurines and bowls, and onion wine bottles.
- *Bredenhof* (1753) – a [cluster of coins](#).
- *Woestduin* (1779) – a [porcelain fish](#).

Other Relevant Collections

- Art, for example:
 - A [17th century painting of Fort Zeelandia](#) on Formosa.
 - [Portrait of Stephanus Versluys](#), a VOC Governor of Ceylon (a map of which is depicted pointedly under his staff in the portrait).
 - six anonymous 18th-century wallpaper paintings from the former VOC building in Middelburg (Zeeuws Museum, 2022).
- Coins and medals, for example:
 - A [first centenary of the VOC 'penning'](#).
 - [Cowrie shells](#) (used as currency for the trade in slaves).
- Ship models, and a model of the port area of Middelburg.
- Items that relate to the VOC Chamber Middelburg, such as:
 - A [seal stamp](#) of the VOC Chamber of Middelburg.
 - A [silver scabbard](#) for a sword.
- A [VOC façade stone](#), dated 1616.
- Examples of traded/imported/commissioned goods, for example,
 - A [plate](#) depicting the VOC-ship *De Vrijburg*.
 - [Kraak](#) porcelain.
- 'Collected' goods from VOC/WIC and other colonial endeavours, for example, [an ivory decorative hair comb from Sri Lanka](#) acquired by Captain Boekhout, a VOC commander.

Collection Access: the Museum has a [collections search](#) on their website. Only part of the collections are digitised.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All rights appear reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- A 2009 three-part mini-series for Vietnamese television by Danish artist collective Superflex, called 'Porcelain', related to the public auction of cargo from the Portuguese ship *San Jago*, seized by three Zeeland ships in 1602. Trailer and series on [Vimeo](#).
- 'This is Zeeland', current.

References

Edwards, H. (2000). *Treasures of the deep: The extraordinary life and times of Captain Mike Hatcher*. HarperCollins Publishers.

Zeeuws Museum—In Middelburg—Discover Zeeland. (n.d.). Zeeuws Museum. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsmuseum.nl/en>

Zeeuws Museum. (2022). *Zeeuws Museum Collection Evaluation*. Zeeuws Museum. https://www.zeeuwsmuseum.nl/en/about-the-museum/organisation/what-we-do/cw_engels.pdf

New Zealand

Te Papa Tongarewa (Museum of New Zealand)

National Museum of New Zealand, with collections across art, culture and natural history with a specific focus on New Zealand and the Pacific Islander cultures.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [53 records](#) of ceramic, including tea bowls, saucers, and teapots.

Other Relevant Collections

- Historical and art collections contextualising the European contact with New Zealand and Pacific Islands, such as:
 - [Hemisphere pour voir Les Terres/ Meridional plus distinctement Australes, Guillaume De L'Isle, 1714, France](#) – Depicts the mapping conducted by Tasman 1642-3 and 1644.
 - [Mar del Zur Hispanis Mare Pacificum, Johannes Janssonius, 1650, Amsterdam](#) – Depicts the earliest published European chart of the Australian coast.
- Note also modern legacy of Abel Tasman captured in [some collections](#), such as stamps and currency.

Collection Access

- [Collections Online](#)
- [DigitalNZ](#)

Collection Data Sharing: Collection [API](#).

Licensing: Te Papa has an [open-license policy](#), unless copyright of art/images are held by a third-party.

References

Te Papa. (n.d.). Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://tepapa.govt.nz/>.

Norway

[Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum](#) (Bergen Maritime Museum)

The Museum focuses on Norwegian Maritime History, with a particular focus on merchant shipping and Bergen. Formerly known as the Bergen Shipping Museum. The foundational collections were across ship paintings, models, instruments, maps and photographs.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Akerendam* (1725) – [38 records](#), mostly coins, and artillery, glass sherds, buttons and a belt buckle, bone cutlery handles, and a couple of metal pots.

Collection Access

- [DigitaltMuseum](#)

Collection Data Sharing

- DigitaltMuseum [API](#): a key is required.

Licensing: No clear statement, assume All Rights Reserved.

References

Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum. (n.d.). Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sjofartsmuseum.museumvest.no/>

[Universtitetet i Oslo Myntkabinettet \(University of Oslo Coin Cabinet\)](#)

A coin and medals collection established by the University of Oslo in 1817. It contains over a quarter of a million items from across the world and history. The collection is managed within the Kulturhistorisk Museum.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Akerendam* (1725) – also known as the ‘Runde Treasure’. The collection received approximately 20% of the coins recovered from the salvage of the *Akerendam* at Runde Island after it was found by three private divers in 1972, and excavated by the Norwegian Maritime Museum. The collection is predominantly ducats from 1724 (pers. comm. Prof. Håkon Roland, Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, 2 July 2024).

Collection Access

- [UniMus collection portal](#) – note that digitisation of collections is ongoing and at the time of writing the *Akerendam* collection is not yet available in the online catalogue.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- The University of Oslo’s Coin Cabinet Exhibition [[online](#)], 1995.

References

The Coin Cabinet—Museum of Cultural History. (n.d.). University of Oslo. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.khm.uio.no/english/collections/coin-cabinet/index.html>

Rønning, B. R. (1974). Myntene fra *Akerendam*. In L. Petterson & A. Thowsen (Eds.), *Sjøfartshistorisk årbok 1973* (pp. 124–128). Bergens sjøfartsmuseum.

Universtitetet i Oslo Myntkabinettet & Dokumentasjonsprosjektet. (n.d.). *Norwegian coins through 1000 years*. Myntkabinettets Elektroniske Myntutstilling [University of Oslo’s Coin Cabinet Exhibition]. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://www.dokpro.uio.no/umk_eng/utstill.html

Portugal

Macau Museum (Macau Scientific and Cultural Centre)

A museum of Chinese artefacts and artworks in Lisbon. Collection mainly focuses on the 16th and 17th centuries – the period of cultural contact and trade between Portugal and Macau, but also includes a general Chinese art collection.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – the collection appears to have at least one ceramic item, [a bottle](#), from the shipwreck.

Collection Access: no collection portal, but does have a presence on [Google Arts and Culture](#).

References

Macau Museum. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/museu-do-centro-cientifico-e-cultural-de-macau>.

Macau Scientific and Cultural Centre. (n.d.). *Centro Científico e Cultural de Macau*. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.cccm.gov.pt/en/>.

Saint Helena

Museum of St Helena

A local museum supported by the local Heritage Society, that broadly curates and cares for historic items related to the community on the island. A small number of finds from *Witte Leeuw*, wrecked off the coast in St James Bay and salvaged by Robert Sténuît, are located in the Museum.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – According to the Museum (pers. comm. Adam Sizeland, Museum of St Helena, 30 May 2024) they hold:
 - Ceramic: kraak porcelain, bellarmine jugs and martaban jars.
 - Some metallic items such as pewter cutlery, iron cooking pots and lead shot.
 - A bronze cannon acquired from the British Royal Air Force's dive team who conducted an expedition on the site.

Collection Access: none known, contact museum.

References

The Museum of St Helena Island. (n.d.). The Heritage of St Helena. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museumofsainthelena.org/>.

News. Western Hemisphere, St Helena. (1977). *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 6(3), 257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1977.tb01018.x>.

Sténuît, R. (1978, October). The sunken treasure of St. Helena. *National Geographic Magazine*, 154(4), 562–576. National Geographic Virtual Library.

Sierra Leone

Sierra Leone National Museum

A museum focusing on the history and culture of Sierra Leone.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

Items from a shipwreck off Banana Island were deposited at the Museum, first by a Mr Chris Konarski and then by the group Wyprawy Wrakowe – the latter identified the wreck as the *Diemermeer* (Reichert et al., 2018).

- *Diemermeer* (1747) – ‘shipwreck finds’ including ceramic fragments, a [gold ring](#), unidentified metallic objects, e.g. [piece of brass](#), and [lead sheeting](#).

Collection Access: collection available through [eHive](#).

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

References

Reichert, R., Scheijde, A., Wytykowski, P., & Zajder, R. (2018). *Sierra Leone 2014. Final Report of the Flag No. 160 Two Expeditions*. Wyprawy Wrakowe. <https://wyprawywrakowe.pl/en/final-report-of-the-two-sierra-leone-expeditions/>.

Sierra Leone Heritage. (n.d.). Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <http://www.sierraleoneheritage.org>.

Sierra Leone National Museum. (n.d.). eHive. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://ehive.com/collections/6125/sierra-leone-national-museum>.

Singapore

[Asian Civilisations Museum \(ACM\)](#)

Singapore national museum of Asian antiquities and decorative art which focuses on the historical connections within Asia across culture, religion and civilisations. This includes art and artefacts related to maritime trade (featuring in particular the ‘Tang’ or ‘Belitung’ shipwreck) and the collective experience of European colonialism and empire across Southeast Asia.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [ceramic](#).
- ‘Hatcher Junk’ (1646) – [ceramic](#).
- ‘Vŭng Tâu shipwreck’ (1690) – [ceramic](#).

Other Relevant Collections

The Museum features much of the art and artisanal crafts targeted for trade and/or collection by Europeans both within and from the Asian continent, as well as art and manuscripts documenting that period. Examples include:

- [Stoneware jars](#) found in shipwreck cargoes.
- [Manuscript plan of the bay and town of Nagasaki](#), depicting Dejima Island.
- [Qing dynasty plate](#) depicting the VOC coat of arms.
- [Japanese export porcelain](#) depicting a drunk Dutchman on a barrel.
- [An inrō with netsuke](#) depicting a Dutchman on one side and a Dutch ship on the other.
- [‘Hong Bowl’](#) which depicts the ‘hongs’ or trading companies of Western merchants at Canton (Guangzhou).
- [City plan of old Batavia](#), c.1660.

Collection Access: [‘Roots’](#), the National Heritage Board’s national collections portal.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Maritime Trade Gallery](#), current permanent exhibition.
- [Port Cities: Multicultural Emporiums of Asia, 1500-1900](#), 4 November 2016–19 February 2017.

References

Asian Civilisations Museum. (n.d.). Asian Civilisations Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/acm/>.

Lee, P., Andaya, L. Y., Watson Andaya, B., Newton, G., & Chong, A. (2016). *Port cities: Multicultural emporiums of Asia, 1500-1900*. Asian Civilisations Museum.

Maritime Trade. (n.d.). Asian Civilisations Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/acm/galleries/maritime-trade/maritime-trade>.

[National Museum of Singapore](#)

A National Museum of Singapore focuses on the history and development of Singapore, which includes the period of European merchant trade and colonialism in Southeast Asia, and the period of competition between the British and the Dutch. The Museum and collections started as the Raffles Library and Museum in 1849.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Rooswijk* (1739) – [Silver bar](#).

Other Relevant Collections

- Manuscript, document and published materials reflecting Dutch and VOC colonial and trading activity in the region, such as:
 - [Map depicting the 1603 confrontation between the Dutch and Portuguese in the Straights of Singapore](#).
 - [Manuscript with instructions and information for VOC officers arriving in Batavia and the Cape](#).
 - 5 volumes of *Oud en nieuw Oost-Indiën*, by [Francois Valentijn](#), a former employee of VOC who served as a minister of the Dutch Reformed Church.
 - Johan Nieuhoff's [L'Ambassade de la Compagnie Orientale des Provinces Unies vers l'Empereur de la Chine](#) – account of the first VOC embassy to China.

Collection Access: '[Roots](#)', the National Heritage Board's national collections portal.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

References

National Museum of Singapore. (n.d.). National Museum of Singapore. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/nationalmuseum/>.

South Africa

BayWorld Museum

Natural and Cultural history of the Nelson Mandela Bay region, including the shipwrecks along the coast. Formerly known as the Port Elizabeth Museum.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Reigersdaal* (1747) – SAHRA report that the collection holds items.

Collection Access: none known.

References

Bayworld, Port Elizabeth. (n.d.). Bayworld. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.bayworld.co.za/>.

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briega Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

[Bredasdorp Shipwreck Museum, South Africa](#)

A local museum originally independently run, but now run by the province – Western Cape Government, with a single curator working across multiple collections.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Museum features a broad representation of shipwrecks from the Southern Cape, with items, including ceramics and cannon, supposedly from the following wrecks. SAHRA report that the collection holds items from:

- *Merestein* (1702).
- *Schonenberg* (1722).
- *Middenrak* (1728).
- *Reigersdaal* (1747).
- *Middelburg* (1781).

Collection Access: No online collection interface or collection data.

References

Shipwreck Museum. (n.d.). Western Cape Government. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.westerncape.gov.za/facility/shipwreck-museum>.

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Brieg Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

East London Museum

A natural and cultural history museum located in East London, South Africa, originating from a local Museum Society in the 1920s. The Museum includes a display on the maritime history of the area – in particular the wreck of the Portuguese ship *Atalaia*.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

SAHRA report that the collection holds items from two VOC shipwrecks – nature of these items is not known.

- *Huis te Crayestein* (1698)
- *Bennebroek* (1713)

Collection Access: none known. The Museum has suffered some thefts and this may be impacting how they advertise/communicate their collections.

References

East London Museum. (n.d.). East London Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.elmuseum.za.org/East-London-Museum/>.

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briege Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

Vernon, G. (2001). Who gets the ‘treasure’? The role of the East London Museum in shipwreck salvage with special reference to the *Grosvenor*. *South African Museums Association Bulletin*, 27, 66–67.

[Hout Bay Museum](#)

A small provincial museum, assisted by the Western Cape Department of Cultural Affairs and Sport, located to the south of Cape Town on Hout Bay, focusing on promoting the area's culture and history – including shipwrecks.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

SAHRA report that the collection holds items from:

- *Huis te Crayestein* (1698)
- *De Vis* (1740) [?] – reported to have a small cannon and an unmarked cannon salvaged at different times from area of this wreck.

Collection Access: none known.

References

Hout Bay Museum. (n.d.). Hout Bay Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://houtbaymuseum.co.za/>.

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briege Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

[Iziko Museums of South Africa](#)

Central organising body of over 2 million objects that make up the national collections, exhibited across multiple sites in Cape Town, South Africa, including culturally significant built heritage sites. Relevant built heritage sites for the period of VOC colonial administration and/or ownership/construction include:

- [Slave Lodge](#).
- [Groot Constantia Manor House](#).
- Koopmans-de Wet House.
- Old Town House.
- Rust en Vreugd.
- Castle of Good Hope (note: site is not managed by Iziko, but items from Iziko, and other institutions, are exhibited).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The [shipwreck collections](#) began due to the Former National Monuments Council legislation requirement that 50% of items from salvage operations had to be deposited at a museum, but this system did not work well. Current legislation protects underwater cultural heritage (National Heritage Resources Act, No. 25 of 1999). Maritime and underwater heritage is managed by SAHRA (South African Heritage Resources Agency), [Maritime and Underwater Cultural Heritage \(MUCH\)](#) and under legislation artefacts recovered from these sites under permit are deposited with the national collections.

- *Oosterland* (1697) and *Waddinxveen* (1697) – the largest collections held, acquired from the excavation of the two wrecks overseen by Bruno Werz in the 1990s.
 - Ceramics studies on the *Oosterland* were completed by Jane Klose (Klose n.d.; Klose 2000) – her card catalogue is held by the Museum.
 - List of materials available on request from Jaco Boshoff. Boshoff notes the *Waddinxveen* collections include a multitude of shoes.
- *Huis te Crayestein* (1698) – site subject to extensive salvage and treasure hunting from the 19th century. Museum holds a small collection of material salvaged in the 1960s, including specie, pewter spoons, clay pipes and lead caps.
- *Merestein* (1702) – small, varied, collection of items from salvage in the 1960s. Most of the material salvaged from the wreck was privately auctioned (Marsden, 1976).
- *Bennebroek* (1713) – some ceramics.
 - Museum holds Jane Klose’s records of the ceramic material from the wreck (Klose 2000; 2003).
- *Reigersdaal* (1747) – small, varied, collection from the 1960s. The site was badly treasure hunted.
- *Bredenhof* (1753) – partial silver ingot (purchased).
- *Nieuw Rhoon* (1776) – vessel structure excavated from reclaimed land and held by the Museum (Lightley, 1976).
 - Also known as the Civic Centre Wreck – identification as *Nieuw Rhoon* uncertain, but likely a VOC ship.
 - The City Council also acquired some material, but its current location is unknown.

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- *Middelburg* (1781) – ceramic material recovered in the 1960s from three separate salvers.
 - Documentation and digitisation in progress by Jaco Boshoff.
- *Brederode* (1785) – small collection of ceramics (Klose 2000) and a bell.
 - Deep sea investigation 1999/2000 inspected by Jaco Boshoff.
 - Wreck is well protected by depth of site – holds potential for future research.

Note: SAHRA reports Iziko holds material from the *Middenrak* (1728) and *Rodenrijs* (1737), but this is not verified by the Museum (some material reported to be from the *Rodenrijs* is more likely from the *Waddinxveen*).

Other Relevant Collections

- Historical material and archaeology of the VOC period (nb. Schrire, 2014, p. 232) that relates to:
 - History and development of Table Bay.
 - Artefacts and documentation associated with Slave Lodge and Church Square (note: '[Slavery in South Africa](#)' research and collections focus).
 - Artefacts from the excavation of the Castle of Good Hope – excavated by Gabeba Abrahams, University of Cape Town, and now held by Iziko (Schrire, 2014, p. 245). Collections excavated by H. N. Vos and held by the Stellenbosch Museum are slated to go to Iziko.
- 16th-18th century art collection:
 - Michaelis Collection and art collection of Dutch and Flemish artists. Primarily exhibited at the Old Town House.
 - William Fehr Collection of objects and art contains VOC material.
- Works on Paper, particular William Fehr Collection, which documents people and landscapes of early colonial South Africa.

Collection Access: no online collection portal.

- A limited selection of art is curated and available on [Google Arts & Culture](#).
- Consult with [Jaco Boshoff](#) for shipwreck artefact collection.

Collection Data Sharing: none. Digitisation of collections is in progress, such as from *Middelburg* (1781), but publication/platform for this data is required.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Slave Wrecks Project, with Smithsonian National Museum of African and American History and Culture, <https://global.si.edu/projects/slave-wrecks-project>.

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Brieger Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

Iziko Museums. (n.d.). Iziko Museums of South Africa. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.iziko.org.za/>.

Klose, J. E. (n.d.) 'The 'Oosterland' (1697), Table Bay, Cape Town, South Africa'. Historical Archaeology Research Group. Cape Town: Department of Archaeology, University of Cape Town [Unpublished catalogue].

Klose, J. (2000). Oriental ceramics retrieved from three Dutch East India Company ships wrecked off the coast of southern Africa: *Oosterland* (1697), *Bennebroek* (1713) and *Brederode* (1785). *Transactions of the Oriental Ceramic Society*, 64, 63–81.

Klose, J. E. (2003) 'The Peter Sacks wreck. Believed to be the 'Bennebroek' (1713). A catalogue of ceramics salvaged from a wreck of the Kieskamma River, South Africa'. Historical Archaeology Research Group. Cape Town: Department of Archaeology, University of Cape Town [Unpublished catalogue, 2003].

Lightley, R. A. (1976). 'An 18th Century Dutch East Indiaman, Found at Cape Town, 1971'. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 5(4), 305–16.

Marsden, P. (1976). 'The Meresteyn, Wrecked in 1702, near Cape Town, South Africa'. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 5(3), 201–19.

Schrire, C. (2014). *Historical Archaeology in South Africa: Material Culture of the Dutch East India Company at the Cape*. Left Coast Press, Inc.

Schuit, H. G., Bull, D., & Holtrop, M. (2017). *Shared Heritage in Museums in South Africa: Opportunities for Collaboration - Publicatie* (Shared Cultural Heritage). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2017/01/01/shared-heritage-in-museums-in-south-africa-opportunities-for-collaboration>.

Werz, B. E. J. S., & Klose, J. E. (1994). Ceramic analysis from the VOC Ship *Oosterland* (1697). *The South African Journal of Science*, 90(10), 522–526.

MuseuMAfricA

Public museum run by the City of Johannesburg. The collection largely focuses on the cultural history of South Africa, emerging from the combination of the City of Johannesburg's individual institutions in the early 1990s.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

Reported (by SAHRA) to have material from:

- *Merestein* (1702).
- *Middelburg* (1781).

Other Relevant Collections: contains material regarding the Dutch/VOC colonial periods in South Africa.

Collection Access: none known.

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briege Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

Schuit, H. G., Bull, D., & Holtrop, M. (2017). *Shared Heritage in Museums in South Africa: Opportunities for Collaboration - Publicatie* (Shared Cultural Heritage). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2017/01/01/shared-heritage-in-museums-in-south-africa-opportunities-for-collaboration>.

[SA Fisheries Museum](#)

Small museum focused on the history of the fishing industry on the South African West Coast, from whaling in the 17th century. The Museum was formerly located in Hout Bay, but is now located at Velddrif.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

SAHRA reports that the Museum has material from one VOC ship:

- *Reigersdaal* (1747).

Collection Access: none known.

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briega Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

SA Fisheries Museum. (n.d.). SA Fisheries Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://safisheriesmuseum.co.za/index.html>.

[Simon's Town Museum](#)

Local Historical Society run museum within 'The Residency' – a winter residence of the VOC Governor at the Cape. The institution collects and exhibits the local and cultural history of the people of Simon's Town, in particular their connections with the VOC and the Royal Navy.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Museum holds material from the following wrecks, including cannon, according to research conducted by SAHRA.

- *Merestein* (1702)
- *Reigersdaal* (1747)
- *Middelburg* (1781)

Collection Access: none.

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briege Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

Simon's Town Museum. (n.d.). Simon's Town Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.simonstownmuseum.org.za/>.

South African Heritage Resources Agency (SAHRA)

The government authority responsible for the protection and registration of South Africa's cultural heritage. The Maritime and Underwater Cultural Heritage Unit protect and manage the shipwrecks off the South African coast (including maintaining a register of all known locations), as well as maintain site inspections, monitoring, and applications to access the sites, and answer public enquiries related to the sites.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Meteren* (1723) – handful of bricks and lead sheeting.

Site Register/Portal

Shipwreck locations are registered in <https://sahris.org.za/> (note purposefully inaccurate for protection of sites).

Other Relevant Collections

- archives of reported private collections of shipwreck material that were registered as part of an amnesty associated with the introduction of heritage legislation (*National Heritage Resources Act* (No. 25 of 1999)).
- Oral Histories collected as part of the 'Modern Oral History: Dutch Wrecks in South Africa' project. These are conversations with divers, salvors and treasure hunters from the 60s to 90s. Note: information from these oral histories has been incorporated into ship records in MaSS.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: CC-BY-SA license for site register.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Modern Oral History: Dutch Wrecks in South Africa, 2015-2020 (with Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed as part of the Maritiem Erfgoed Internationaal).

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briège Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

SAHRA. (n.d.). South African Heritage Resources Agency. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.sahra.org.za/>.

SAHRIS. (n.d.). South African Heritage Resources Information System. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sahris.org.za/>.

[South Africa Naval Museum](#)

Museum established in the South African Navy's base, formerly the base of the British Fleet, in Simon's Town. The Museum site includes use the former Dutch Store House building. Collections focus specifically on the SA Navy.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

SAHRA reports that the Museum has material from one VOC ship:

- *Reigersdaal* (1747) – cannon.

Collection Access: none known.

References

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briegie Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives [Unpublished Report].

Welcome to the SA Naval Museum. (n.d.). SA Naval Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sanavymuseum.co.za/>, <https://sanavymuseum.co.za/>.

University of Cape Town, [Department of Archaeology](#)

The University became involved in teaching and managing archaeological collections as a result of excavations in the early 80s. This included the research of *Oosterland* (1697) and *Waddinxveen* (1697) by Bruno Werz, and several colonial period sites – not least the Castle of Good Hope. The University manages several laboratories in association with these activities, including a Historical Archaeology Laboratory and Archaeological Materials Laboratory.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Oosterland* (1697) and/or *Waddinxveen* (1697) - A small reference collection of sherds, etc., collected when Bruno Werz was a member of the department are part of the teaching collections.

Other Relevant Collections

The University also retains many collections from archaeological activity – see Shrire (2014).

Collection Access: none. Contact department.

References

Department of Archaeology. (n.d.). University of Cape Town. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://science.uct.ac.za/department-archaeology>.

Shrire, C. (2014). *Historical archaeology in South Africa: Material culture of the Dutch East India Company at the Cape*. Left Coast Press, Inc.

[De Wetschhof Estate](#)

Wine estate in the Robertson Wine Valley, South Africa.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Reigersdaal* (1747) – two cannons: Tubby Gericke, one of the salvers of the *Reigersdaal*, offered two of the cannons to Danie de Wet ([Facebook](#)). The cannons are located either side of the building on the estate that houses the De Wetschhof visitors' centre.

Collection Access: none.

References

De Vries, G., & Hall, J. (2001). *The Muzzle Loading Cannon of South Africa: A technical study*. Cannon Association of South Africa.

Sri Lanka

[Maritime Museum, Galle Fort, Department of National Museums, Sri Lanka and the Maritime Archaeology Unit, Sri Lanka](#)

The Maritime Museum and Maritime Archaeology Unit (MAU) of Sri Lanka are both located in Galle Fort. The relationship between the Maritime Archaeology Unit and the National Museums, and who is the custodian of the UCH artefacts, is unclear. Information regarding both are therefore presented here.

The establishment of a Maritime Museum, in a 17th century Dutch warehouse, was associated with the first maritime survey of the harbour in 1992, and the subsequent Galle Harbour Project and discovery and excavation of the wreck of *Avondster* over the following decade. This activity included capacity building in the areas of maritime archaeology and conservation in Sri Lanka, with a Maritime Archaeology Unit (MAU) and conservation laboratories established alongside the Museum (c. 2000) (note international and national support at different times from – in no particular order – Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands in Colombo, Central Cultural Fund, Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology, Maritime Heritage Trust, Sri Lanka Sub Aqua Club, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka Navy, Department of National Museums, University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam Historical Museum, Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology, Western Australian Government, and Australian Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade). Unfortunately, the 2004 Tsunami decimated the Museum, MAU and conservation laboratories, and many cultural heritage items and infrastructure were lost or damaged, but the MAU and Maritime Museum have both been able to rebuild and continue operations – the Museum reopening in 2009.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Avondster* (1659) (GH Site L) – about 2/3 of retrieved materials from the wreck were lost as a result of the tsunami. See catalogue by Bonke et al. (2007) regarding scope of collections.
- *Hercules* (1661) (GH Site F) – cannon from what is believed to be the wreck of *Hercules* retrieved during the Galle Harbour Project.

Note that some items may also be exhibited in the Galle National Museum and stored in Galle Fort.

Other Relevant Collections

The National Museums of Sri Lanka also hold material regarding the VOC colonial period, such as in the [Dutch Museum](#) in Colombo situated in a 17th century Dutch Urban house built by Thomas Van Rhee, the Dutch Governor of Sri Lanka 1692-1697. The National Museum Library may also be a potential source of cartography and print collections.

Collection Access: no online collection portal.

Site Register/Portal

A [National Shipwreck Database](#) supported by the Central Cultural Fund is maintained by the [Maritime Archaeology Unit](#).

Collection Data Sharing: no data sharing.

Licensing: unknown.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Sri Lankan-Australian maritime archaeological research and training project, 1992-1993.
- Galle Harbour Project, 1996-1997.
- *Avondster* project, 1999-2004: see [Maritime Lanka](#): maritime archaeology & history of Sri Lanka (last updated 2012).

Note: the distinctions between some of these projects is not clear because of continuing personnel and aims.

References

Bonke, H., Parthesius, R., & Pijl - Ketel, C. van der (Eds.). (2007). *Artefacts catalogue Avondster site 1998-2004: the Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman that was wrecked twice in Ceylon*. Centre for International Heritage Activities.

Devendra, S. (2002). Dutch Shipwrecks in Galle: The Avondster Project. In S. Kelegama & R. Madawela (Eds.), *400 Years of Dutch-Sri Lanka Relations, 1602-2002*. Institute of Policy Studies of Sri Lanka.

Devendra, S., & Muthucumarana, R. (2015). Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka: Twenty five years old and a new beginning. In S. Tripathi (Ed.), *Shipwrecks Around the World: revelations of the past* (pp. 381–424). Delta Book World.

Green, J. N. (1998). *The Australian-Sri Lanka-Netherlands Galle Harbour Project 1992-1998*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology.

Green, J., & Devendra, S. (1993). Interim report on the joint Sri Lanka-Australian maritime archaeology training and research programme, 1992–3. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 22(4), 331–343. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1993.tb00429.x>.

Green, J. N., & Devendra, S. (1994). *Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka: The Galle Harbour Project, 1992*. Archaeology Department of Sri Lanka; Central Cultural Fund; West Australian Maritime Museum; Postgraduate Institute of Archaeology.

Green, J., Devendra, S., & Parthesius, R. (Eds.). (1998). *Sri Lanka Department of Archaeology report on the joint Sri Lanka - Australia - Netherlands Galle Harbour Project 1996 - 1997: archaeology, history, conservation and training*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.04_galle_harbour_project.pdf.

Green, J., Millar, K., & Devendra, S. (1993). *Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka, the Galle Harbour Project-1993: an interim report* (No. 65; WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports). WA Museum. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.065_galle_harbour.pdf.

Green, J., & Parthesius, R. (1998). *Papers from the Seminar 'Galle—A Port City in History: 15 November 1997, Galle'*. Sri Lankan Department of Archaeology; Australian National Centre for Excellent in Maritime Archaeology; Western Australian Maritime Museum; University of Amsterdam. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.02_galle_a_port_city.pdf.

Manders, M. (2006). The In Situ Protection of a Dutch Colonial Vessel in Sri Lankan Waters. In R. Garnier, D. Nutley, & I. Cochran (Eds.), *Underwater Cultural Heritage at Risk: Managing Natural and Human Impacts* (Heritage at Risk Special Edition, pp. 58–60). ICOMOS.

<https://www.icomos.org/public/risk/2006/20manders2006an.pdf>.

Maritime Archaeology Unit. (n.d.). Central Cultural Fund. <https://mau.ccf.gov.lk/>.

MaritimeLanka. (n.d.). Maritime Asia. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from

<https://maritimeasia.ws/maritimelanka/index.html>.

Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Department of National Museums.

https://www.museum.gov.lk/web/index.php?option=com_regionalm&task=regionalmuseum&id=8&lang=en.

National Shipwreck Database of Sri Lanka. (n.d.). Central Cultural Fund. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://nsd.ccf.gov.lk/index.php>.

Parthesius, R. (2002). Het wrak van VOC-schip Avondster in de haven van Galle (Sri Lanka): Een potentiële bron van kennis over de Europese expansie in Azië. In M. H. Bartels, E. H. P. Cordfunke, & H. Sarfatij (Eds.), *Hollanders uit en thuis: archeologie, geschiedenis en bouwhistorie gedurende de VOC-tijd in de Oost, de West en thuis ; cultuurhistorie van de Nederlandse expansie* (pp. 61–70). Verloren.

Parthesius, R. (Ed.). (2007). *Excavation report of the VOC-ship Avondster (1659). The Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman that was wrecked twice in Ceylon*. Centre for International Heritage Activities.

<https://mass.cultureelerfgoed.nl/documents/00000041.pdf>.

Parthesius, R., Millar, K., Devendra, S., & Green, J. (Eds.). (2003). *Sri Lanka Maritime Archaeological Unit report on the Avondster Project 2001-2002*. Amsterdams Historisch Museum.

https://www.maritimeasia.ws/maritimelanka/avondster/Avondster_2001-02.pdf.

Parthesius, R., Millar, K., & Jeffery, B. (2005). Preliminary Report on the Excavation of the 17th-Century Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman Avondster in Bay of Galle, Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 34(2), 216–237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.2005.00056.x>.

United Kingdom

The British Museum (BM)

A National Museum based in London, England, established through a 1753 act of UK parliament. The collection is international in scope, across all expressions of human material culture.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The British Museum collections contain VOC shipwreck material in the two distinct areas of metal ingots and Asian ceramics.

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613) – a [zinc ingot](#).
- *Kampen* (1627) – [two lead boat-shaped ingots](#), stamped.
- *Haarlem (Nieuw Haarlem)* (1647) – a [Bartmann jug](#) and a [sherd of blue underglaze porcelain](#).
- *Waddingsveen* (1697) – a [tin bar ingot](#), and [six copper ingots](#).
- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724) – two silver bars (as ‘[Slotter Hooge](#)’).
- *Hollandia* (1743) – [lead ingot](#).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – selection of [ceramics](#).
- *Bredenhof* (1753) – two [silver bars](#).
- ‘[Hatcher Junk](#)’ (1646) – ceramic.
- ‘[Cà Mau Shipwreck](#)’ (1725) – ceramic.

Note also [items from wrecks and dredging in Table Bay \(Cape Province, South Africa\)](#).

Other Relevant Collections

- Art collections, particularly Prints and Drawings of maritime themes, for example:
 - Prints and drawings of VOC ships [by Wenceslaus Hollar](#).
 - Prints and drawings of [Willem van de Velde I \(or II\)](#).
 - Satire comparing [British and Dutch merchants, 1749](#).
- Department of money and medals – examples of VOC issues of coin and ingots.
- Asian art for the European market – collection strengths include Japanese arts and Chinese ceramics, both of which reflect various aspects of interaction and trade with Europe, such as:
 - VOC personal commission, for example, a [carved ivory plaque](#) with family crests.
 - Institutional commissions or trade of ceramics, for example, a [VOC monogrammed Japanese Arita ware plate](#) and an [apothecary’s bottle](#).
 - Furnishings, for example, [lacquered cabinets](#).
 - VOC Collections, for example, [Engelbert Kämpfer](#) was a physician for the VOC in the Persian Gulf and Japan, and his collection was acquired by Hans Sloane.

Collection Access: British Museum’s [Collection online](#) includes ‘over 4.5 million objects in 2 million records.’ What proportion of the entire collection this represents is not apparent but there is a [recent commitment to document entire collection](#) (The British Museum, 2023).

Collection Data Sharing: export from collections portal possible in CSV.

Licensing: Data is made available CC BY-NC-SA, but collection images are subject to individual licenses.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- ‘Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World’, with WA Museum, 31 October 2016-23 April 2017 (exhibited WA Museum only).
- ‘[Collecting and Empire](#)’ trail, part of a wider project to better acknowledge the way the British Museum collections are tied to European colonialism and Empire.

References

British Museum. (n.d.). The British Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.britishmuseum.org/>.

British Museum. (2023, 18 October). *British Museum sets out plans to digitise fully the collection* [Press Release]. [https://www.britishmuseum.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/British Museum sets out plans to digitise fully the collection.pdf](https://www.britishmuseum.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/British%20Museum%20sets%20out%20plans%20to%20digitise%20fully%20the%20collection.pdf).

Collecting and empire. (2020, August 21). *The British Museum*. <https://www.britishmuseum.org/blog/collecting-and-empire>.

Craddock, P. T., and D. R. Hook. ‘Ingots from the Sea: The British Museum Collection of Ingots’. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 16, no. 3 (August 1987): 201–6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1987.tb00587.x>.

Craddock, Paul, and Duncan Hook. ‘An Economic History of the Post-Medieval World in 50 Ingots: The British Museum Collection of Ingots from Dated Wrecks’. *The British Museum Technical Research Bulletin* 6 (2012): 55–68.

Western Australian Museum. (2016). *Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World*. Western Australian Museum.

Hastings' [Shipwreck Museum](#) (Nautical Museums Trust)

A museum and associated trust founded in 1986 by Dr Peter Marsden. His aim was to establish a museum specifically for the care and preservation of maritime archaeological heritage, particularly parts of vessels. The Museum has a dedicated 'Amsterdam Gallery' as the location of the wreck of *Amsterdam* (1749) is nearby, and Peter Marsden performed excavations in response to damage to the site in 1969-70. The Museum also features wrecks from the English Channel.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Prinses Maria* (1686) – a [hand grenade](#) donated by Rex Cowan.
- *Hollandia* (1743) – Spanish '[pieces of eight](#)' coins.
- *Amsterdam* (1749) – finds from the 1969-70 excavations of the wreck that were not sent to the Netherlands, including 'wine glasses, buttons, pewter cups', and skeletal remains.

Collection Access: no known online collection interface or collection data.

References

Marsden, P. (1972a). The wreck of the Dutch East Indiaman *Amsterdam* near Hastings, 1749: An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 1(1), 73–96.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1972.tb00677.x>.

Marsden, P. (1972b). The Wreck of the Dutch East-Indiaman *Amsterdam*. *The Mariners Mirror*, 58(1), 5–26. <https://snr.org.uk/the-wreck-of-the-dutch-east-indiaman-amsterdam/>.

Marsden, P. (1973). The Investigation of the Wreck of the *Amsterdam*. In D. J. Blackman (Ed.), *Marine archaeology: proceedings of the twenty-third symposium of the Colston Research Society held in the University of Bristol, April 4th to 8th, 1971* (pp. 483–492). Butterworths.

Marsden, P. (1974). *The wreck of the Amsterdam*. Hutchinson.

Marsden, P. (1978). A reconstruction of the treasure of the *Amsterdam* and the *Hollandia*, and their significance. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 7(2), 133–148.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1978.tb01057.x>.

Marsden, P., & Butler, T. (2019, March 15). *Shipwreck Museum* [Interview Transcription]. The Mapping Museum research project, Bishopsgate Institute.

<https://www.bishopsgate.org.uk/collections/shipwreck-museum>.

Nautical Museums Trust Limited. (n.d.). *Shipwreck Museum*. Shipwreck Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://shipwreckmuseum.co.uk/>.

[Isles of Scilly Museum](#)

Museum that showcases the culture, landscape and history of the Isles of Scilly, which includes many shipwrecks. Thanks to the Isles of Scilly Museum for responding to our enquiries.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *Hollandia* (1743) – coins, gun flints, brass reamer, sword guard, gun side plates, money weights, lead pot, stoneware jugs, glass bottle in concretion, spoons, forks, cutlery/knife handles, ingot (lead?).

Other Relevant Collections: two wooden bowls made from Lignum Vitae salvaged from *Hollandia*, made by Steve Hardling.

Collection Access: no online portal. Collection known through contact with the Museum.

References

Isles of Scilly Museum. (n.d.). Isles of Scilly Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.iosmuseum.org/>.

[Royal Armouries](#)

Public collections of arms and armour of the UK now based at the Royal Armouries Museum in Leeds, but also managing and exhibiting through Fort Nelson, near Portsmouth, and the Tower of London.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- Zeewijk (1727) – [Swivel gun \(XIX.238\)](#) found on Gun Island during the survey of the Beagle on 24 April 1840. The gun was originally presented by Captain J. C. Wickham to the Royal United Service Museum, and then transferred to this collection. The item is currently exhibited at Fort Nelson.

Other Relevant Collections

Several other examples of armoury related to the VOC are in the collections, such as items manufactured for the European market and traded through the VOC in Japan.

Collection Access: [Online collection portal](#).

Collection Data Sharing: None known.

Licensing: Largely [copyright](#) is retained by the Royal Armouries, though some material may come under Crown Copyright and or a CC-BY license.

References

Green, J. (2020). The Zeewijk Story and the Missing Second Wreck. *Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, 15(4), 333–364. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-020-09268-8>.

Royal Armouries, National museums of arms and armour. (n.d.). Royal Armouries. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://royalarmouries.org/>.

[Royal Collection Trust](#)

A very large and diverse collection encapsulating the collections and interests of the British royal family, and the items that furnish the royal households in the UK.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- *De Liefde* (1711) – [coins](#).

Other Relevant Collections

A small number of items, such as [paintings](#) and books, directly about or related to the VOC, such as [a VOC Almanac bound in sheep's leather](#). European merchant trade goods also represented, which could be from British or Dutch East India Company trade, such as this [Japanese cabinet](#).

Collection Access: [Online collection portal](#).

References

Royal Collection Trust. (n.d.). Royal Collection Trust. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rct.uk/>.

[Royal Museums Greenwich](#)

The Royal Museums Greenwich encompasses the Royal Observatory, National Maritime Museum, Queen's House and the Cutty Sark. The collections centre on the discovery and understanding of the sea and space, and Britain's endeavours in these areas.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- Zeewijk (1727) – [Three blown glass bottles](#) (GGG0222-224) found on the Abrolhos Islands during the survey of the Beagle on 24 April 1840, donated by John Lort Stokes. One has an affixed label '4 Dutch bottles' but only three are in the online catalogue.
- A knife ([REL0726](#)) recovered from the cargo hold of 'a Dutch East Indiaman' wreck – wreck not specified however (museum has been contacted for comment).

Other Relevant Collections

Collections of material by/for the VOC, or document/describe VOC places, people and assets, also the competition between the British and the Dutch mercantile and colonial endeavours.

- Art, for example,
 - Maritime scene by Abraham Storck c. 1705 '[Shipping off Amsterdam](#)'.
 - [Drawing](#) of the Pepper Wharf and 'Wappen van Hollandt' (1653) by Reinier Zeeman/Nooms.
- Maps, for example, [charts from Jacob Colom](#)'s *Atlas of werelts-water-deel en des selfs zee-custen*, 1663.
- Medals, for example, centenary of the [VOC commemoration medal](#).
- Archives, for example, [De Heldwoitemade VOC-Ship bill of sale Dec 1782](#).
- Ship models, for example, the 18th century model of [Zeven Provincien](#).
- [Replica gunner's tallystick](#) made 1974 from an original found on the *Batavia* wreck.

Collection Access: [Collection portal](#) across Objects, Archives and Library.

Collection Data Sharing: [Terms and Conditions](#) on site refers to an API but no link or information provided.

Licensing: Collection description is generally made available under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs (CC BY-NC-ND) licence, but some images and content may differ (e.g. Crown Copyright). See [Terms and Conditions](#).

References

Royal Museums Greenwich. (n.d.). Royal Museums Greenwich. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rmg.co.uk/>.

[Shetland Museum and Archives](#)

Local museum for the Shetland Islands, formerly known as the Zetland County Museum or Lerwick Museum. Thank you to curator Jenny Murray for answering our enquiries.

Artefacts raised from the *De Liefde* from the 1965-8 salvage (Bax and Martin 1974) and *Kennemerland* expeditions (1971-1987) were placed under the care of Tom Henderson (who did the conservation work) at the Shetland Museum and Archives. While the items raised from the *Kennemerland* remained at the Museum, many of the items from the *De Liefde* were later removed and either kept by their finders or sold at auction, with only some remaining with the Museum.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

Colin and Paula Martin are currently preparing material for publication. The following is derived from some of the currently available information kindly made available by them:

- *Kennemerland* (1664) – no significant portions of the vessel, but representative collections across ship inventory, clothing & personal items, tools & equipment, and cargo/ballast. Notable items include:
 - A sailmaker’s needle-case.
 - Shot-moulds.
 - Two pocket sundials.
 - Coins from what must have been personal/contraband (the specie is not represented due to its historic salvage from the site).
 - Inscribed tobacco boxes.
 - A set of pewter golf club heads.
 - Jewellery.
- *De Liefde* (1711) – bronze swivel gun, ornate silver sword-hilt, barrel spigots, brass pipe-stampers, wine glass stems.

Other Relevant Collections

- Keith Muckelroy’s [photographs and notes on the finds from *Kennemerland*](#).
- Note that the collection also holds material from the *Drottningen af Swerige* (Swedish East Indiaman).

Collection Access

- No online collection portal for objects.
- Shetland Archives [Catalogue](#) – material is not digitised.
- Shetland Museum and Archives [Photo Archive](#).
- Note also: archives held by [RCAHMS](#), accessible through CANMORE.

References

Bax, A., & Martin, C. J. M. (1974). *De Liefde*. A Dutch East Indiaman lost on the Out Skerries, Shetland, in 1711. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 3(1), 81–90.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1974.tb00861.x>.

- Dobbs, C. T. C., & Price, R. A. (1991). The Kennemerland site. An Interim Report. The sixth and seventh seasons, 1984 & 1987, and the identification of five golf clubs. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 20(2), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1991.tb00305.x>.
- Forster, W. A., & Higgs, K. B. (1973). The Kennemerland, 1971 An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 2(2), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1973.tb00518.x>.
- Martin, C. J. M. (1987). Pipes from the Dutch East Indiaman Kennemerland, 1664. In P. Davey (Ed.), *The Archaeology of the clay tobacco pipe: Vol. 10. Scotland* (pp. 211–224). B.A.R.
- Martin, C. & P. Martin. (2018). Record of Work Carried out on the Finds from the Wreck of the Dutch East Indiaman *Kennemerland* (1664), Out Skerries, Shetland. Data Structure Report. Historic Environment Scotland, March 2018 [Unpublished Report].
- Martin, P. (2020a, February 18). Shipwrecks in Shetland Part 1. Shetland Museum & Archives. <https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/blog/shipwrecks-in-shetland> .
- Martin, P. (2020b, May 4). Shipwrecks in Shetland Part 2. Shetland Museum & Archives. <https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/blog/shipwrecks-in-shetland-part-2>.
- Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1974). The second season of work on the Kennemerland site, 1973 An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 3(2), 257–268. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1974.tb00882.x>.
- Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1977). The Kennemerland site: The third and fourth seasons 1974 and 1976, An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 6(3), 187–218. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1977.tb01006.x>.
- Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1979). The Kennemerland site: The fifth season, 1978. An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 8(4), 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1979.tb01137.x>.
- Price, R., Muckelroy, K., & Willies, L. (1980). The Kennemerland site: *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 9(1), 7–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1980.tb01266.x>.
- Shetland Museum & Archives. (n.d.). Shetland Museum & Archives. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/>.

[Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum \(Maritime Archaeology Trust\), Isle of Wight](#)

Museum established in 1978 by, and from the collections of, [Martin Woodward](#), a commercial diver and maritime enthusiast, and who recreationally dived on the wrecks off the Isle of Wight. The Museum has been run by the [Maritime Archaeology Trust](#) since 2017.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

Martin Woodward (pers. comm. 30 January, 2024) stated that he ‘dived all these sites and personally recovered the artefacts’.

- *Kampen* (1627) – [coins](#), pocket watches, lead seal.
- *Prinses Maria* (1686).
- *Loosdrecht* (1719) – [sliding link shot](#). Note: MaSS notes this wreck has not been formally identified whereas [Historic England](#) notes found 1980.
- *Vliegende Hert* (1735).

Note: Dutch Astrolabe recovered 1986 by Woodward from St Catherine’s Point, Isle of Wight (Castro et al., 2020, no. 57).

Other Relevant Collections

3D models of some of the artefacts have been made and posted by the Trust on [Sketchfab](#).

Collection Access: No online collection interface or collection data.

References

Castro, F., Jobling, J., Budsberg, N., Loewen, B., & Dieulefet, G. (2020). *Marine Astrolabes Catalogue* (ShipLAB Report 16.3). J. Richard Steffy Ship Reconstruction Laboratory, Texas A&M University. <https://www.academia.edu/download/63768183/SLR16.3-Astrolabes20200628-54641-p73cil.pdf>.

Historic England Research Records: Loosdrecht. (n.d.). Heritage Gateway. https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/Gateway/Results_Single.aspx?uid=22e698c8-4161-45e6-bd74-cee1b93282c4&resourceID=19191.

Maritime Archaeology Trust. (n.d.). Maritime Archaeology Trust. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://maritimearchaeologytrust.org/>.

The Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum. (n.d.). The Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://museum.maritimearchaeologytrust.org/>.

[Shipwreck Treasure Museum](#) (formerly Charlestown Shipwreck and Heritage Centre), Cornwall

This museum, established originally from the private collection of Richard and Bridget Larn, boasts 'Europe's largest private collection' of c. 8,000 finds from c. 150 wrecks.

Note that the current owner, Tim Smit (Smit Associates Ltd and The Merchants of Charlestown), has listed the Museum and collection for sale and has not ruled out selling the collection separately if necessary (Adams, 2024).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

According to personal communication with the Museum, the collection contains material from the following VOC shipwrecks:

- *Witte Leeuw* (1613).
- *Kampen* (1627).
- *Slot ter Hoge* (1724).
- *Hollandia* (1743).
- *Geldermalsen* (1752).

Collection Access: No online collection interface or collection data.

References

Adams, G. K. (2024, August 22). Fears for collection as shipwreck museum is put up for sale. Museums Association. <https://www.museumsassociation.org/museums-journal/news/2024/08/fears-for-collection-as-shipwreck-museum-is-put-up-for-sale/>.

Larn, R., & Butler, T. (2019, March 13). *Charlestown Shipwreck Museum* [Interview]. Mapping Museum research project, Bishopsgate Institute. <https://www.bishopsgate.org.uk/collections/charlestown-shipwreck-museum>.

Shipwreck Treasure Museum. (n.d.). Shipwreck Treasure Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://shipwreckcharlestown.co.uk/>.

[Victoria and Albert \(V&A\) Museum](#)

The Victoria and Albert Museum, based in Kensington, London, showcases art and design from across the globe and throughout history.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

A [significant collection](#) of ceramics retrieved from shipwrecks as part of their East Asia collections. The collection is largely from three South China Sea wrecks. VOC related material includes:

- 'Cà Mau Shipwreck' (1725) – c. [345 records](#) of ceramic.
- *Geldermalsen* (1752) – [ceramic dancing figures](#).

Other Relevant Collections

Examples of Dutch and VOC traded items from the period, and depictions/art. Examples include:

- [Silver button](#) depicting a 17th century Dutch merchant ship.
- [Portrait of the Dutch/VOC Governor of Trincomalee](#), 1780.
- Artworks by [Willem van de Velde, the Elder](#).

Collection Access: [V&A Explorer](#) gives access to collections online.

Collection Data Sharing

- Search results exportable as CSV or JSON from V&A Explorer.
- [API](#) available.

Licensing: Non-commercial use is encouraged with appropriate acknowledgement of V&A and any third-party rights holders. Commercial use restricted – see [Terms & Conditions](#).

References

Shipwrecked ceramics. (n.d.). Victoria and Albert Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.vam.ac.uk/articles/shipwrecked-ceramics>.

V&A - The family of art, design and performance museums. (n.d.). Victoria and Albert Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.vam.ac.uk/>.

Vietnam

Bảo tàng lịch sử Quốc gia (Vietnam National Museum of History)

National Museum responsible for the investigation, collection and care of documents and artefacts related to the Vietnam's history. The Museum has participated in at least 5 shipwreck excavations of the 15th-18th century (Cu Lao Cham in the Central Province of Quang Nam, Binh Chau 1, Binh Chau 2 in Quang Ngai, Binh Dinh in the Central Province of Binh Dinh and Binh Thuận in the South-Central Province of Binh Thuận).

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

The Museum holds material from many sunken merchant vessels which were recovered from the East Sea. According to exhibition descriptions, this includes ceramics/glassware; clothing & personal items; human & animal remains; tableware & furnishings.

The only shipwreck named in the collections associated with the VOC is the

- 'Binh Thuận' (1608) – a vessel transporting cargo for the Dutch, including a large number of ceramics.

Other Relevant Collections: unknown.

Collection Access: none known.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- Di Sản Từ Những Con Tàu Cổ [Maritime Secrets from Ancient Shipwrecks], 18 January-18 May 2019 (now touring).

References

Bảo tàng lịch sử Quốc gia [Vietnam National Museum of History]. (n.d.). Bảo Tàng Lịch Sử Quốc Gia [Vietnam National Museum of History]. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://baotanglichsu.vn/en>.

Huyền, T. (2019, June). Di sản từ những con tàu đắm / Sunken treasures. *Heritage*, 36–41.

[Bảo Tàng Tỉnh Bà Rịa - Vũng Tàu \(Ba Ria - Vung Tau Provincial Museum\)](#)

Provincial Museum for the region of Vũng Tàu, located in Ba Ria, Vietnam.

VOC Shipwreck Artefacts

- 'Vũng Tàu shipwreck' (1690) – unknown extent of collections. Ceramics are exhibited as part of the [third floor exhibitions](#) 'Antiquities salvaged from the waters of Ba Ria - Vung Tau'.

Other Relevant Collections: holds material from several other shipwrecks that relate to intra-Asian trade.

Collection Access: none known.

References

Bảo Tàng Tỉnh Bà Rịa - Vũng Tàu [Ba Ria - Vung Tau Museum]. (n.d.). Bảo Tàng Tỉnh Bà Rịa - Vũng Tàu [Ba Ria - Vung Tau Museum]. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.baotangbrvt.org.vn/>.

VOC Collections – other

This section lists collections notable for material by, for, of or about the VOC and its activity, and individuals attached to the VOC. The collections/institutions listed here largely feature art, bibliographic, cartographic and manuscript collections.

Note that many fantastic resources that catalogue and describe archive/manuscript and map collections already exist. Some of the more comprehensive are listed here for your reference, and those regarding specific collections are listed with their entry in this report.

Blak, G. L. (2007). [*Archives of the Dutch East India Company \(VOC\) and the Local Institutions in Batavia \(Jakarta\)*](#). Brill.

Dutch sources on South Asia: c. 1600-1825.

- Gommans, J., Bes, L., & Kruijtzter, G. (2001). [*Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 1. Bibliography and Archival Guide to the National Archives at the Hague \(the Netherlands\)*](#). Manohar Publ.
- Bes, L. (2007). [*Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 2. Archival Guide to the Repositories in the Netherlands Other than the National Archives*](#). Manohar Publishers & Distributors.
- Bes, L., & Kruijtzter, G. (2015). [*Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*](#). Manohar.

Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie

- Brommer, B. (2009). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. V. Afrika/Africa*](#). (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Diessen, R. van, & Nelemans, B. (2008). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. IV. Ceylon*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Gommans, J. J. L., Bos, J., & Kruijtzter, G. (2010). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. VI. Voore-Indië, Perzië, Arabisch Schiereiland/India, Persia, Arabian Peninsula*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Gommans, J. J. L., & Diessen, R. van. (2010). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. VII. Oost-Azie, Birma tot Japan/East Asia, Burma to Japan*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Knaap, G. J. (2007). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. II. Java en Madoera/Java and Madura*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Roever, A. G. de, & Brommer, B. (2008). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. III. Indische Archipel en Oceanië/Malay Archipelago and Oceania*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Schilder, G., Moerman, J., Ormeling, F., Brink, P. van den, & Ferwerda, H. (2006). [*Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. I. Atlas Isaak de Graaf/Atlas Amsterdam*](#) (1st ed). Atlas Maior.

Parthesius, R., & Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten [Centre for International Heritage Activities]. (2014). [*Inventory and analyses of archival sources in the Dutch East India Company \(VOC\) archives in the Netherlands in order to contribute to possible locations and identification of VOC shipwrecks off the Western Australian Coast*](#) (WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports 310). Western Australian Museum Foundation; Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten.

Schilder, G. (2010). *Sailing for the East: History & catalogue of manuscript charts on vellum of the Dutch East India Company (VOC), 1602-1799*. Hes & De Graaf.

'Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Company Archives and Research' (TANAP) project, Nationaal Archief, and partners (see section 'Projects and Resources' below).

Australia

Commonwealth Bank Map Collection

A map collection acquired by a private bank operating in Australia. The collection relates to the European imagining of the ‘Southland’, and period of European discovery and charting of Australia.

Relevant Collections

- ‘[Terra Australis Cognita – Dutch Discoveries](#)’ – maps that depict the initial Dutch charting of the Australian coast, featuring works by Willem Blaeu, Hendricus Hondius, Robert Dudley (depicting the charting of Jan Carstensz), and Jodocus Hondius.
- ‘[Dutch Sea Charts](#)’ – features works by Joan Blaeu, Melchisédech Thevenot (incorporates all Dutch knowledge at 1696 before Cook), Nicolaas Visscher, and Pieter Goos.

Collection Access: a curated selection of the collection is made available on their website.

Licensing: website shows © 2024 Commonwealth Bank of Australia, but note that the maps themselves are in the Public Domain.

References

Shaping Australia. (n.d.). Commonwealth Bank. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.commbank.com.au/about-us/shaping-australia.html>.

[The National Library of Australia](#)

National Library for Australia, located in Canberra. The library's collection focuses on documentary resources of national significance, which extends to non-Australian materials, and encompasses books/published accounts, cartographic material, manuscripts, ephemera, and art.

Relevant Collections

- Extensive cartographic collections (1.6 million items, with all pre-1900 maps digitised), for example:
 - [\[Manuscript map on vellum of the Indian Ocean showing routes between the Cape of Good Hope and the Sunda Strait\]](#), Isaak de Graaf.
 - [\[Uitslaande kaart van den Maleischen Archipel, de Noord- en West-kusten van Australië, 1690-1714\]](#), Isaak de Graaf.
 - [Caert van't Landt van d'Eendracht ...](#) , Hessel Gerritsz, 1627.
 - [\[Chart of the Malay Archipelago and the Dutch discoveries in Australia\]](#), Hessel Gerritsz, 1618.
 - [Der Hollaendisch-Ostindianischen Compagnie weltberuhmte Haupt-Handels und Niederlags-Stadt Batavia ...](#) , 1762.
 - [\[De slag van Bantam te water geschiet/The naval battle of Bantam\]](#), 1608 – note: depicts the *Duyfken*.
 - [De zee-atlas ofte water-waereld](#), navigational aids of Hendrick Doncker, 1659.
 - Two manuscript charts by Gerard van Keulen - De Vlamingh's exploration of the Western Australian coast.
 - MAP RM 751 - [T Zuid landt ontdekt door Willem de Vlaming in den Maande van Jan an February 1697 met t Yagt de Geelvink de Hooker de Nijptang ent Galjoot t Weseltje](#).
 - MAP RM 752 - [T Zuid land ontdekt door Willem de Vlamingh in de Maande van Jan an Febrii 1697 met t Yagt de Geelvink de Hooker de Nijptang ent Galjoot 't Weseltje](#).
- Books/published accounts, for example:
 - Published account of De Vlamingh's voyage to Australia – '[Journaal wegens een voyagie, gedaan op order der Hollandsche Oost-Indische Maatschappy in de jaaren 1696 en 1697 door het hoekerscheepje de Nyptang, het schip de Geelvink, en het galjoot de Wezel, na het onbekende Zuid-land, en wyders na Batavia](#)', 1701.
 - 'Ongeluckige voyagie, van't schip Batavia, nae Oost-Indien ...', both the [1648](#) edition and 'the uncommon Utrecht edition' [1649](#) which contains an additional account.
 - '[Der edlen Ost-Indianischen Compagnie der vereinigten Niederlande gewesenen commandirenden Officiers auf der Insul Lethy, Neu-vermehrte Ost-Indianische Reise-Beschreibung ...](#)', 2nd edition, 1751 – early 18th century account of VOC employee Ernst Christoph Barchewitz which includes a description of Cape Town, the fort and garden of the Dutch East India Company, and of Banda and Leti (the Moluccas). Barchewitz bought slaves for the VOC.
- Art, for example, a '[Portrait of Abel Tasman, his wife and daughter](#)', [Jacob Gerritsz Cuyp].

Other Relevant Collections

- [Dutch pamphlet collection](#) (1567-1852) – some items reference the Dutch East India Company.
- [Australian digitised newspapers](#) – includes instances of public discourse/reporting on VOC, Dutch shipwrecks and finds along the coast, and public sentiment regarding these. Majority of newspapers digitised until 1950 which is known as the ‘copyright cliff’. Fulltext searchable through TROVE.

Collection Access

- Online [Catalogue](#).
- Catalogue and digitised holdings (out of copyright) also available through [TROVE](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- [Trove API](#): API key required. A good introduction and tools for using TROVE’s API are given by the [GLAM Workbench](#).

Licensing

- No clear statement on reuse of collection metadata.
- Copy and re-use of material from the Library's collections is welcome within the scope of Australian Copyright Act 1968 and any special requirements, such as culturally sensitivities.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- ‘Changing Coastlines’, 1993-1994 (exhibited across National Library of Australia, Australian National Maritime Museum and Western Australian Museum).
- [‘South Land to New Holland: Dutch Charting of Australia 1606-1756’](#), 2006 [online].
- ‘Mapping our world: terra incognita to Australia’, 7 November 2013-10 March 2014.

References

Council of Australian State Libraries (CASL), & National Library of Australia. (2006, September 6). *South Land to New Holland: Dutch Charting of Australia 1606–1756*. National Library of Australia. <https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20060906040101/http://www.nla.gov.au/exhibitions/southland/index.html>.

National Library of Australia. (n.d.). National Library of Australia. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.nla.gov.au/>.

National library of Australia (Ed.). (2013). *Mapping our world: terra incognita to Australia*. National Library of Australia.

Richards, M., & O’Connor, M. (Eds.). (1993). *Changing Coastlines. Putting Australia on the World Map 1493-1993*. National Library of Australia. http://www.nla.gov.au/sites/default/files/changing_coastlines.pdf.

[State Library of New South Wales](#)

Public library for the state of New South Wales, Australia, located in Sydney. While the primary focus of the library's collections is to document and reflect the history of New South Wales, its collections also provide a wider national and international context to these collections, including European encounters with Australia and the wider region.

Relevant Collections

- Cartography, for example:
 - [‘Carten dese landen Zin ontdeekt bij de compangie ontdeckers behaluen het norder deelt van noua guina ende het West Eynde van Java...’](#), Abel Janszoon Tasman 1644 – also known as the [‘Tasman Map’](#).
 - Two charts on vellum by Isaac de Graaf, 1739: [‘Staet Sunda’](#) and [‘Batavia en Bantam’](#).
 - [[Chart of the Malay Archipelago and the Dutch discoveries in Australia](#)], Hessel Gerritsz, 1618.
 - [[Chart of the Indian Ocean, 1677](#)], Joan Blaeu II. On vellum – shows a number of annotations in pencil of a plotted course (chart has been trimmed due to historical reuse as book).
 - [‘Charte universelle de tout le monde 1628’](#) – the first printed world map to include the Dutch exploration of the Gulf of Carpentaria.
 - [[Timor and\] Lesser Sunda area](#), c. 1652. On vellum – Portuguese sailing chart of Flores and Timor Sea. Depicts Dutch and Portuguese presence and sphere of influence in the region e.g. VOC flag shown at Koepang taken in 1652, Portuguese flag depicted at Lifau.
 - Note: the impressive [Dixson Map Collection](#).
- Published accounts, for example:
 - [‘Leyds veer-schuyts praetjen ...’](#) 1630 – account of the wreck of *Batavia*, published 15 years earlier than the Pelsaert account (‘Ongeluckige voyagie’).
 - [‘A Voyage to New Guinea, and the Moluccas...’](#) by Captain Thomas Forrest – undertaken while spying on the VOC for the benefit of the British.
- Manuscript collections, both original archival material and transcriptions/copies of material in the Nationaal Archief and British Library, for example:
 - The Huydecoper/Huijdecoper copy of Abel Tasman’s Journal: [‘Extract Uittet Journael vanden Scpr Commandr Abel janssen Tasman, bij hem selffs int ontdecken van't onbekende Zuyjdlandt gehouden’](#), 1642-1643. (Note: contains a copy of Gerritz’s map which details the *Gulden Zeepard* voyage and mapping of the south coast of Australia, captained by Francois Thijssen ([[Chart of the Malay Archipelago and the Dutch discoveries in Australia](#)] above).
 - Vellum bound manuscript [‘Vopen Hermanssoon van Amsterdam - seiglende naar Oost Indien int Jaer ons Heeren 1613, dit Stuermans Bouck, schip Mauritius, 1614’](#) – a handbook of seamanship with tables and charts, some in colour.
 - [Ulrich Gerhard Lauts manuscript extracts](#) on Dutch 17th century explorers including Abel Janz. Tasman and Maarten Gerritsz. Vries.

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- Copy of British Library (India Office Library, London) [transcripts from archives at the Hague](#) taken in the 19th century of documents dated 1600-1699 concerning the history of the Dutch in the East Indies (relating mainly to points of contact with the English).
- [Pieter Nuyts papers](#).

Collection Access

- Collection [Catalogue](#).
- Select items also available through [Google Arts and Culture](#).
- Also searchable through the National Library of Australia's collection aggregator, [TROVE](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- Records can be downloaded as CSV from collection catalogue.
- [Trove API](#): API key required. A good introduction and tools for using TROVE's API are given by the [GLAM Workbench](#).

Licensing

- Collection data shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Australia license (they also ask that any projects using their data 'Share Alike').
- Licensing of images/digitisation varies.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- ['The Voyages of Discovery: The Great South Land'](#) [online].
- ['First sight: the Dutch mapping of Australia, 1606-1697'](#), 6 March-4 June 2006.

References

Brunton, P., & State Library of New South Wales. (2006). *First sight: the Dutch mapping of Australia, 1606-1697*. State Library of New South Wales.

https://www2.sl.nsw.gov.au/archive/events/exhibitions/2006/firstsight/docs/firstsight_guide.pdf.

State Library New South Wales. (n.d.). State Library New South Wales. <https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/>.

State Library of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/state-library-of-new-south-wales>.

State Library New South Wales. (n.d.). Voyages of Discovery: the Great South Land. State Library New South Wales. <https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/stories/voyages#!/st/0>.

[State Library of Western Australia](#)

The State Library of Western Australia builds, preserves and shares documentary and reference collections for the education and recreation of Western Australians. Its collections record and reflect the State's rich heritage and history, including prominent Western Australian's and their achievements.

Relevant Collections

- Cartography – original cartographic and nautical charts by or recording the findings from early Dutch and French exploration, such as:
 - [‘Tabula Indiæ Orientalis et regnorum adjacentium’](#), 1726.
 - ‘Polus Antarcticus’ – hemispherical map centred on the South Pole to the Tropic of Capricorn. All four states show evolution of mapping of the Australian coastline.
 - [‘First state’](#), Hendricus Hondius, c. 1637 – shows Australia prior to the discoveries of Tasman in 1642 and 1643-44.
 - [‘Second state’](#), Ioannes Ianssonius, c.1645.
 - [‘Third state’](#), Ioannes Ianssonius, 1650 – includes several new discoveries.
 - [‘Fourth state’](#), 1700 – includes the discoveries of parts of New Zealand and Tasmania .
 - [‘Oosterdeel van Oost Indien’](#), Arnold Colom, c. 1658.
 - [‘Typus orbis terrarum’](#), Latin text edition, 1632 – small section of the WA coastline marked ‘t'Land van Eedracht’ from Dirk Hartog's 1616 voyage.
 - [‘Het Westelykste Gedeelte van 't Land vande Eendragt of Nova Hollandia’](#), Keulen, Johannes van, 1753 – detailed map of the coast of WA after Willem de Vlamingh's manuscript chart of his exploration voyage 1696-1697.
 - [‘Paskaerte zynde t'oosterdeel van Oost Indien’](#), Pieter Goos, 1666 – marks known shipwrecks.
 - [‘Hondius World Map’](#) – the earliest printed map to show the recent Dutch explorations on the West Coast of Australia.
- Ephemera/archives relating to interaction and research of the Dutch encounter with the Western Australian coast, such as:
 - [Phillip Playford's papers](#) – registered discoverer of *Zuiddorp* wreck (nb. Broomhall, 2016).
 - [Henrietta Drake-Brockman's papers](#) – research/writing of *Batavia* wreck and mutiny.
- Books & Journals, such as:
 - The [‘Ongeluckige voyagie, van 't schip Batavia, nae de Oost-Indien’](#), 1647 edition donated to the Victoria Public Library (former name of State Library) by F. C. Broadhurst whose firm worked on the Abrolhos Islands since 1883.
 - Account of de Vlamingh's journey to the Southland – [‘Journaal wegens een voyagie, gedaan op order der Hollandsche Oost-Indische Maatschappij in de jaaren 1696 en 1697 door het hoekerscheepje de Nyptang, het schip de Geelvink, en het galjoet de Wezel, na het onbekende Zuid-land, en wyders na Batavia’](#), 1701.
- Oral histories of individuals involved in the research, 'discovery' and excavation of VOC shipwrecks off the Western Australian coast including:
 - [William Thomas Newbold](#) (Zeewijk).

VOC Collections – Scoping Report

- [Phillip Playford](#) (Zuiddorp).
- [Max Cramer](#) (Batavia).
- [Tom Pepper](#) (Zuiddorp).
- [Hugh Edwards](#) (Batavia/Zeewijk).
- [Clive Daw](#) (Zuiddorp).
- [Frederick Morrison Blood](#) (Zuiddorp).
- [Jeremy Green](#) (WA Museum – Batavia, Zeewijk, Zuiddorp and Vergulde Draak).
- [Garry James McGrath](#) (Batavia).
- [Spags Burnett](#) (Batavia).

Collection Access: [Online 'encore' catalogue](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- SLWA makes datasets available through data.wa.gov.au.
- Datasets can be requested by [contacting the Library](#).

Licensing

- Unless otherwise stated, copyright resides with the State of Western Australia, and any use should be within that permitted under the Australian Copyright Act 1968.
- Datasets are made available CC-BY.

References

State Library of Western Australia. (n.d.). Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://slwa.wa.gov.au/>.

Austria

Österreichische Nationalbibliothek

The Austrian National Library with historical collections spanning back to the 14th century.

Relevant Collections

- Cartography, such as:
 - ['Atlas Blaeu - Van der Hem'](#) – a large collection accumulated by Amsterdam lawyer Laurens van der Hem (1621-1678) which were added to Joan Blaeu's 'Atlas Maior'. It is notable for the four volumes of manuscript material originally made for the VOC, and includes:
 - Johannes Vingboons reproduction of the [Duyfken mapping of Cape York](#).
 - [Manuscript chart](#), c. 1670 – represents the extent of the voyages of *Pera* and *Arnhem* as part of the Carstensch. expedition to Cape York.
 - The so-called '[Eugene map](#)' – an overview of Tasman's journeys and mapping of south-coast of Tasmania and New Zealand.
 - Charts/maps related to the voyage of [Abel Tasman](#), such as Isaac Gilsemans' mapping of Tasmania from Tasman's voyage.

Collection Access

- Online [catalogue](#).
- Digitised collections can be browsed through [ÖNB Digital](#).

Collection Data Sharing: No bulk export.

Licensing: reuse allowed with attribution, unless third party copyright applies. See [Terms of Use](#).

References

Österreichische Nationalbibliothek - Startseite. (n.d.). Österreichische Nationalbibliothek. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.onb.ac.at/>.

Belgium

KBR

The National Library of Belgium which combines the collections of the Biblioteèque Royale de Belgique and Koninklijke Bibliotheek de Belgique.

Relevant Collections

- [Collection of manuscripts either gathered or written by VOC-skipper Wouter Thomasz van Dijk 1704-1734](#). Contains an anonymous account of *Zeewijk* wrecking, possibly derived from Adriaan van der Graaf's journal.
- Dutch portolan map [Oost-Indische pas-caart: nieulycks beschreven door Iacob Aertsz. Colom](#), c. 1635 (note – similar extent of Australian coast as in the SLNSW Hessel Gerritz map [[Chart of the Malay Archipelago and the Dutch discoveries in Australia](#)] [[cartographic material](#)]).

Collection Access: [KBR General Catalog](#) – links provided through catalogue to digitised collections.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: KBR Reserves All Rights – Copyright links to reproduction request form.

References

KBR • Royal Library of Belgium. (2024, June 14). KBR. <https://www.kbr.be/en/>.

Finland

[A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection](#), Kansalliskirjasto Nationalbiblioteket (National Library of Finland, University of Helsinki)

Impressive collection of cartography, as well as geographical literature, travel accounts and rare books.

Relevant Collections

- Cartography attributed to, for example,
 - [Jonssonius Johannes](#).
 - [Joan Blaeu](#) ('[Portolan of the Atlantic Ocean](#)', 1697).
 - [Pieter Goos](#) ('[Oost Indien: wassende-graade paskaart](#)', 1650).
 - [Hendricus Hondius](#).
- Books/Journals, for example,
 - 'Schouten's Journal': '[Journael oft Beschryvinghe van de Reyse 1615-1617](#)'.
 - An account of the Fluyt Arion's shipwreck: '[De droevige schipbreuk van het fluitschip den Arion, op de reize uit Japan naer Batavia](#)'.
 - '[Journal of an East Indies Voyage](#)' by Willem Ysbrantsz Bontekoe van Hoorn.

Collection Access

- National Library's [Search Service](#).
- Digitised maps from the A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection on [Doria](#).

Collection Data Sharing: select records can be exported to a number of formats.

Licensing: Content, both digitised and collection description, is free to use as long as it is not effected by a third-party license, see [Terms and Conditions](#).

References

A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection. (n.d.). Kansalliskirjasto Nationalbiblioteket [National Library of Finland]. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/en/collections/e-nordenskiold-collection>.

The A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection in the Helsinki University Library. Annotated Catalogue of Maps made up to 1800. (1979–1995). Vol. I-III. Compiled by Ann-Mari Mickwitz, Leena Miekkaavaara and Tuula Rantanen. Vol. IV. Compiled by Tuula Rantanen. Vol. V:1–2. By Cecilia af Forselles-Riska. Helsinki.

France

[Bibliothèque Nationale de France](#)

The National Library of France focuses on the documentary heritage of the nation.

When Napoleon conquered the Netherlands in the late 18th century, many valuable Dutch documents, such as maps, were seized and transferred to the Dépôt de la Marine. Some of this material was either not returned or copied and returned. Today, these maps are mostly in the Bibliothèque Nationale as part of the collections of the ‘Service hydrographique de la Marine’.

Relevant Collections

- Cartography, for example:
 - A large collection of ‘portolan’ nautical charts ‘[Cartes marines sur parchemin](#)’, for example, ‘[Pays-Bas et Batavia](#)’ – nautical charts on parchment produced by the Dutch schools (from 1450 to 1737).
 - Maps collected/acquired by the [Service hydrographique de la Marine](#).
 - [17th Century Dutch maps](#) – including those attributed to
 - [Hessel Gerritz](#), e.g. ‘[Mar del Sur. Mar Pacifico](#)’ oldest known map showing Cape York as charted by the Duyfken in 1606.
 - [Pieter Goos](#).
 - [Johannes Van Keulen](#).
 - the [Blaeus](#).
 - [18th Century Dutch maps](#).
- Books/Journals, for example, [Johan Nieuwhof], ‘[Journaal van zommige voorvallen, inde voyagie vande E. Heeren Pieter de Goyer en Jacob Keyser, ambassadors, aande grootmachtige keizer van Chyna en Tartaryen, India Jaaren 1655, 56 & 1657](#)’, 1659 – personal account and drawings of the Embassy of the Dutch East India Company in China, which contributed to the publication of ‘Het Gezantschap der Nederlandtsche Oost-Indische Compagnie aan den grooten Tartarischen Cham, den tegenwoordigen Keizer van China...’

Collection Access

- BnF [Library Catalogue](#).
- Digitised collections available through [Gallica](#).

Collection Data Sharing

- [BnF Data](#) – allows search for particular entities (e.g. authors, places, subjects) and export of related data.
- [BNF API Portal](#) and Datasets (French only) - access to various sources of data about collections managed by BnF through API or curated datasets.

Licensing: content is licensed for free and open use provided that the source (BnF / Gallica) is acknowledged unless the material is subject to third-party copyright.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- 'L'Âge d'or des cartes marines: Quand l'Europe découvrait le monde', 23 October 2012-27 January 2013 (and [online](#): BnF, Délégation à la diffusion culturelle, Éditions multimédias, 2012).

References

Bibliothèque Nationale de France. (2012). *L'Âge d'or des cartes marines. Quand l'Europe découvrait le monde* [Exhibits]. Bibliothèque Nationale de France. <https://expositions.bnf.fr/marine/index.htm>.

Bibliothèque Nationale de France. (2024, September 3). BnF - Site institutionnel. <https://www.bnf.fr/>.

Foncin, M., Destombes, M., & La Roncière, M. de. (1963). *Catalogue des cartes nautiques sur vélin conservées au département des Cartes et plans*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France.

Hervé, R., Hugonnard-Roche, H., & Pognon, E. (1974). *Catalogue des cartes géographiques sur parchemin conservées au département des Cartes et plans*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France.

Hofmann, C., Richard, H., & Vagnon, E. (2012). *L'âge d'or des cartes marines: quand l'Europe découvrait le monde* [exposition, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris, 23 octobre 2012-27 janvier 2013]. Seuil Bibliothèque nationale de France.

Germany

Peter Tamm Collection, Internationales Maritimes Museum, Hamburg

A museum that was founded by the private collection of Peter Tamm, with a particular focus on maritime shipping. Exhibition on the West and East India Trading Companies features on 'deck 2' of the Museum.

Shipwreck Artefacts

- Armament – [Nico Brinck's overview of Dutch Cannon](#) identifies the collection as holding 'several large mortars' salvaged off the coast of South Africa, and another bearing the mark of the Zeeland chamber of the VOC (Brinck, 2020, p. 78, 287).
- Arqueonautas collection – The private salvage firm Arqueonautas donated their study collection of 2,300 objects from numerous shipwrecks to the Museum. The shipwrecks are mainly in the region of Cape Verde and Mozambique. [According to a 2022 post](#) by the Museum the collection is across boat parts, navigation equipment, coins, weapons, and personal items such as jewellery. The donation also included a large amount of documentation, scientific texts, plans, articles, photos and films from the firm. The Museum intends to publish the collection as a book.

Other Relevant Collections

- Ship models – the majority are from the modern period.
- Dutch maritime painters, for example, Hendrik Cornelisz Vroom and Jan Porcellis (see exhibition '[Spiegel der Welt](#)' [Mirror of the World]).
- Published works 16th-20th centuries – well-known explorers and voyages of discovery were a collecting focus.

Collection Access: none known. [An online digital archive is in progress.](#)

References

Brinck, N. (2020). *Kanonnen van Nederland: Nederlands geschut en andere oude kanonnen in Nederland* [*Guns of the Netherlands: Dutch cannon and other old guns in the Netherlands*] (2nd revised edition). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed.

<https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2020/01/01/kanonnen-van-nederland>.

Dauchez, D. M. (2022, March 31). *Die Arqueonautas Studiensammlung im Maritimen Museum*. Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/2022/03/die-arqueonautas-studiensammlung-im-maritimen-museum/>.

Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. (n.d.). Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/>.

Spiegel der Welt. (n.d.). Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/spiegelderwelt/>.

Hungary

[Országos Széchényi Könyvtár](#) (National Széchényi Library, Budapest)

National Library in Hungary, with extensive cartographic collections in part from the 1802 donation of maps and atlases (around 6,000 items) by Count Ferenc Széchényi (the namesake of the Library).

Relevant Collections

- The [Count Ferenc Széchényi](#) collection, including:
 - The nautical chart '[Nieuwe Pascaert van Oost Indien](#)', Ionnes van Keulen (c. 1710).
 - [TK 1665 – a portolan nautical chart of the Indian Ocean by Hessel Gerritz c. 1621](#) – earliest depiction of Australia's west coast (catalogue description).
 - [TK 1666 – a portolan nautical chart of the Atlantic Ocean by Hessel Gerritz c. 1623](#).

Collection Access

- The library manages [several different catalogues and databases](#) for its collections.
- Digitised collections available through the [Hungaricana - Közgyűjteményi portál](#) – see for example [OSK Map collections](#).

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved, contact OSK library.

References

Országos Széchényi Könyvtár. (n.d.). Országos Széchényi Könyvtár. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://oszk.hu/en>.

India

State Archives of West Bengal (Kolkata)

The State Archives for the Government of West Bengal.

Relevant Series

- Dutch *pattas* 'land holdings' 1702-1825 – concerning land leased by the VOC at Chinsura (the Dutch headquarters in Bengal).

Collection Access: [apparently digitised](#), and held by the Nationaal Archief (could not be sourced).

References

Bes, L. (2012). Gold-Leaf Flattery, Calcuttan Dust, and a Brand New Flagpole: Five Little-Known VOC Collections in Asia on India and Ceylon. *Itinerario*, 36(1), 91–106.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0165115312000381>.

Bes, L., & Kruijzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

Digitisation of Dutch Landownership Documents Finished. (n.d.). DutchCulture. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://dutchculture.nl/digitisation-dutch-landownership-documents-finished>.

Holdings. (n.d.). Directorate of State Archives, Kolkata, West Bengal. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://sadte.wb.gov.in/index.php/holdings>.

[Tamil Nadu Archives \(Chennai, India\)](#)

Archive for the documents of administrative and social importance of the Tamil Nadu State. Formerly the Madras Record Office.

Relevant Series

- ‘Stack 7’ – Records of the East India Company (1670-1857): Archives of the VOC Establishments in Malabar (item nos. 1-1633), Coromandel (nos 1612-1621 and 1634-1642), Surat (nos 1643-1672) and Bengal (nos 1673-1763) and Legal Successors.

Collection Access

- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventory of these ‘Dutch Records’ (in Dutch and English).

Collection Data Sharing

- Part of the collection has been digitised and can be viewed through the Nationaal Archief, series [1.11.06.11](#).

Licensing: none stated.

References

Bes, L., & Krutzler, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

Nationaal Archief, Den Haag, Digitaal Duplicaat: Nederlandse bezittingen in India: Archieven aanwezig in de Tamil Nadu Archives te Chennai, 1.11.06.11. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/archief/1.11.06.11>.

Tamil Nadu Archives and Historical Research. (n.d.). Tamil Nadu Archives and Historical Research. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://tamilnaduarchives.tn.gov.in/WEB/EN/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

Indonesia

[Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia \(ANRI\) – Indonesian National Archives](#)

The National Archives of Indonesia, located in Jakarta.

Relevant Series

[‘Archive of the Governor-General and Councillors of the Indies \(Asia\), the Supreme Government of the Dutch United East India Company and its successors \(1612 - 1811\)’](#): the archives of the VOC from ‘Batavia Castle’, the former headquarters of the VOC in Asia. The archive holdings are substantial, though they have suffered some decay and disorder. These comprise, primarily:

- The dagregisters (daily registers).
- Resolutieboeken (resolution books).
- Bilagen resolutieboeken (appendices to the resolution books).
- Brieven inlandse vorsten (letters with regional monarchs).

Other Relevant Series

There are also local private and public institutions in Batavia and elsewhere in Indonesia related to the activity of the VOC, for example:

- The archives of Banda (1613-1891) which was a popular spice growing region with VOC administration for a time.
- Archives of Riouw (1621-1913) which include VOC archives transferred from Malacca.
- Archives of the Royal Batavian Society of Arts and Sciences (1778-1962), established by a former VOC employee towards the end of the VOC administration.

Collection Access

- [Sejarah Nusantara](#) is the portal resulting from the digitisation and public access project of the main VOC archives from Batavia Castle. This was the result of the [Digital Archive System at ANRI \(DASA\)](#) project.
 - Inventory published and available as [pdf](#).
 - Inventory data export available in [Xml](#) (Entered using open source archival description tool ICA-AtoM, export format: Encoded Archival Description) in Dutch, Indonesian and English.
- Main archives website – <https://anri.go.id/> – pdfs of series inventories.
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): inventories.

Collection Data Sharing

- [‘Harta Karun’](#) – transcription and translation of selected archival materials.
- Digitised or digitalised VOC archives from Batavia Castle (digital scans only available through log-in).
 - Digital scans [General Resolutions of Batavia Castle 1613-1810](#) (Archival Series 853 ... 1182, 4486, 4487).

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- [Appendices to General Resolutions 1686-1811](#) (Incomplete) – browsable and searchable list (with digital scan) or CSV export (Dutch with archive cross ref.). Contains data for ship names, individual names and place names referred to.
- Transcribed index of [Realia 1610-1808](#) (Resolutions of the meetings of the Supreme Government of the VOC in Asia) – browsable and searchable list or CSV export (Dutch with archive cross ref).
- [The Placards of Batavia Castle 1602–1808](#) – pdf of published volumes and searchable list or CSV export (Dutch with published volume cross ref).
- Digital scans [Daily Journals of Batavia Castle 1624-1806](#) (Archival Series 2457... 2623). Note pdfs of published volumes made available through [Hathi Trust and imbedded reader on site](#).
- [Marginalia to the Daily Journals 1659-1807](#) – transcribed, collated and annotated from all volumes, browsable and searchable list or CSV export (Dutch with archive cross ref). Contains data for ship names, individual names and place names referred to.
- [Diplomatic Letters 1625-1812](#) – browsable index for diplomatic letters with published volume cross reference and digital scan or CSV export; index by place (source or destination) or individual also available.
- Digital scans of [Corpus Diplomaticum 1595-1799](#) – browsable index and CSV export of content in the six volume *Corpus Diplomaticum Neerlandico-Indicum* published between 1907 and 1955 by Mr J.E. Heeres and Dr F.W. Stapel. Index by place and individual also available.
- [Digital scans of maps](#) and inventory compiled by Dr. Frederik de Haan (1905-1922) – CSV export also available.

Licensing: Collection content data (indexes etc) are made available with a CC-BY-NC-SA license from the Sejarah Nusantara website or on the [Corts Foundation DASA](#) project site.

References

Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia. (n.d.). <https://anri.go.id/>.

Bes, L., & Kruitzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

Blak, G. L. (with Dijk, F. van, & Kortlang, D. J.). (2007). *Archives of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and the Local Institutions in Batavia (Jakarta)*. BRILL. <https://sejarah-nusantara.anri.go.id/media/userdefined/pdf/BRILLVOCinventaris.pdf>.

Sejarah Nusantara. (n.d.). Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia. <https://sejarah-nusantara.anri.go.id/archive/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

Japan

Japan National Museums

The Japan National Museums' collections are exhibited across the [Tokyo National Museum](#), [Kyoto National Museum](#), [Nara National Museum](#), [Kyushu National Museum](#) and Museum of the Imperial Collections, Sannomaru Shozokan. Each institution has a slightly different focus.

Shipwreck Artefacts

- *De Liefde* (1600) – the 'hekbeeld', a statue of Erasmus, taken from the ship when it was plundered (on permanent loan from the Ryuko-in in Sano City, Tochigi Prefecture – see Brinckmann, 2008).

Other Relevant Collections

- Cartography, for example:
 - A [Japanese nautical chart in European style](#).
 - A [Blaeu wall map](#).
 - Maps by Jodocus Hondius.
- Art and works on paper depicting the VOC, for example, a [Depiction of a Dutch Ship](#), Edo Period, Hayashi Shihei.
- Objects made for trade or commission by the Dutch, for example:
 - [Imari Plate](#) with 'VOC' emblem.
 - A [Portable Sewing Box](#), decorated with Japanese lacquer.

Collection Access: [ColBase](#) (Integrated Collections Database of the National Institutes for Cultural Heritage, Japan) is a collective search across Japan's National Museums.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: Reuse allowed with citation, unless limited by third party copyright. See [Terms of Use](#).

References

Brinckmann, H. (2008, November 12). *Erasmus/De Liefde*. Under auspices of the Japan-Netherlands Society, Tokyo National Museum. https://habri.jp/uk/contents/erasmus_de_liefde.html.

ColBase: Integrated Collections Database of the National Institutes for Cultural Heritage, Japan. (n.d.). ColBase. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://colbase.nich.go.jp/?locale=en>.

Kyoto National Museum. (n.d.). Kyoto National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kyohaku.go.jp/eng/>.

Kyushu National Museum. (n.d.). Kyushu National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kyuhaku.jp/>.

Nara National Museum. (n.d.). Nara National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.narahaku.go.jp/english/>.

Tokyo National Museum - Tohaku. (n.d.). Tokyo National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.tnm.jp/>.

Malaysia

[Arkib Negara Malaysia](#)

National Archives of Malaysia, which hold in custody and preserve the documentary material and archives pertaining to the nation's history and that of the State.

Relevant Series

The majority of the VOC archives from the VOC government in Malacca are now held elsewhere (Fernando, 2005). These include:

- British Library – Dutch Records from Malacca in the India Office Records ('Malacca Political Council, Court of Justice, and Orphan Chamber' (c1685-1835), R/5.
- ANRI – Archives of Riouw (1621-1913) which include VOC archives transferred from Malacca.
- Nationaal Archief – virtually all papers from Malacca, 1641 to 1795, were sent to Batavia, and are preserved in the 'letters and papers from the Indies to the Heren XVII and Amsterdam Chamber' ([Overgekomen brieven en papieren uit Indiëaan de Heren XVII en de kamer Amsterdam](#)). This contains copies or originals of the VOC government in Malacca's documents.

Other Relevant Series

The [Dutch Reformed Church Malacca](#):

- 'Dooptboeken' Baptism registers – 1642-1688 (2007/0056189W), 1689-1709 (2007/0056192W), 1709-1742 (2007/0056190W), 1742-1790 (2007/0056191W).
- Resolutie Books – 1694-1717 (2007/0056193W), 1718-1740 (2007/0056194W) 1740-1772 (2007/0056195W), 1773-1825 (2007/0056196W).
- Rapporten – 1719-1773 (2007/0056197W).
- Kerk Book – 1782-1799 (2007/0056198W).
- Miscellaneous Book – (2007/0056203W).

Collection Access

- [OFA](#): Online Finding Aid for the Government and National Archives of Malaysia.
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventory of 'Dutch Records' (in Dutch and English).

Collection Data Sharing: none known. Note that OFA has a registration and request service.

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References

Bes, L. (2007). Records in a Rival's Repository: Archives of the Dutch East India Company and Related Materials in the India Office Records (British Library), London (and the National Archives of Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur). *Itinerario*, 31(3), 16–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S016511530001170>.

Fernando, M. R. (2005). The Lost Archives of Melaka: Are They Really Lost? *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 78(1 (288)), 1–36. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41493536>.

Gallop, A.T. (2006). Malay Documents In The Melaka Records in the British Library. *Itinerario* 30(2): 54-77. doi:10.1017/S0165115300013966.

Online Finding Aid. (n.d.). National Archives of Malaysia. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://ofa.arkib.gov.my/portal/index.php/en/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

Verhoeven, F. R. J. (1964). The Lost Archives of Dutch Malacca 1641-1824. *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 37(2 (206)), 11–27. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41492198>.

The Netherlands

[Nationaal Archief \(National Archive of the Netherlands\)](#)

National archives for the Netherlands, located in The Hague.

Relevant Series

'[Overzicht van VOC-archieven, 1594-1814](#)' conveniently lists all major relevant series of VOC archival material, and related resources such as the personal archives of officials. The scope of this is thorough, useful and freely available, and will not be replicated here.

Note that of the original Dutch VOC archives (series 1.04.02) it is estimated that only a quarter have survived to the present day.

Each archive series' inventory is complemented by a 'Beschrijving/Description' – these explain the form and scope of each series, and are therefore integral for those querying the prepared inventory. An introduction to 1.04.02 – the Inventory of the archives of the VOC, 1602-1795 – has also been prepared [in English](#).

Examples of relevant series, or parts of series, to the MOB-VOC project include (but are in no way limited to):

- Pelsaert's Journal regarding the voyage and wrecking of *Batavia* ([NL-HaNA_1.04.02_1098_539-701](#)).
- [Journal by Abel Tasman Jansz](#) from voyage to the Southland (NL-HANA_1.11.01.01_121), and [associated drawings](#) (NL-HaNA_1.11.01.01_320).
- [Journal kept on the ship Geelvink by Willem de Vlamingh](#) (NL-HaNA_1.04.02_5060), on [Nijptang by Gerrit Kolaert](#) (NL-HaNA_1.04.02_5062) and [Wezeltje by Laurens Zeeman](#) (NL-HaNA_1.04.02_5064), during the voyage to the Southland.
- Copy of the [Journal from the ship Zeewijk](#) with an account of its wrecking (NL-HaNA_1.04.02_11417).
- An [alphabetical listing of VOC ships](#) that were built, purchased or rented by the VOC (NL-HaNA_1.11.01.01_551).

Map collections: see Nationaal Archief overview '[Navigatie en Overzeese Expansie](#)'.

For example, an extensive map collection including VOC material for the route from the Netherlands to Batavia, and onward to Japan: [NL-HaNA, Collection Hans and Eva Kok, 4.HEK](#).

Many of the Nationaal Archief maps feature in the published series [Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie](#) (reference list provided at the start of [this section](#)).

Other Relevant Series

The Nationaal Archief as the repository of archives of the Dutch government also contain records of modern consideration of the VOC, its heritage and historical legacy. These can relate to laws, policies, agreements and communication about the location, ownership, preservation and excavation or salvage of VOC material worldwide. Some examples:

- 2.05.118 Inventory of the code archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs [Ministerie van Buitenlandse Zaken], 1955-1964 [Anonymised], [813.53 – 13659](#) report regarding the

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discovery of *Batavia* and *Vergulde Draak* and legal aspects regarding the finding of valuable material.

- 2.05.330 Inventory of the code archive of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs [Ministerie van Buitenlandse Zaken], (1937) 1975-1984 (2008), [811.1 – 10255-10259](#) meetings regarding the ANCODS agreement, and the rights of the Netherlands to shipwrecks of the VOC along the Western Australian coastline.
- 2.05.445 Inventory of the archives of the Dutch diplomatic representation in Tanzania, (1950) 2001-2012 (2014), [A.5.1 – 613](#) report on the legislation regarding the salvage of historic shipwrecks of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) wrecked near Mauritius 1978 – 1984.
- 2.08.5012 Inventory of the archives of the Ministry of Finance: Directorate of Domains, 1945-1979, [39 – 39](#) concluding agreements regarding the salvage of shipwrecks on which the State can assert rights. 1945-1995 (concerns the salvage of *De Liefde*, *Prinses Maria*, *Hollandia*, and *Akerandam*).
- 2.27.19 Inventory of the archives of the Ministry of Culture, Recreation and Social Work, (1910) 1965 - 1982 (1990), [1.09.05 – 2374](#) regarding the investigation of Dutch shipwrecks on the Australian west coast, 1966-1968.

Collection Access

- Archive search through ‘Onderzoeken’ portal: <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/>. In Dutch but with auto-English translation available (Google translate plugin). Project in 2015–17 aimed to have 100% of the historic VOC series inventoried and digitised.
 - Digitised resources are indicated by a graphic of a screen indicates the resource is requestable but not digitised.
 - Digital viewer provides stable URLs, download options, and opportunity to view/create/contribute transcription.
- [Globalise](#): Project with the Nationaal Archief developing [fully searchable transcription](#) of the ‘Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren’ series.
- [Het Geheugen](#): portal for documentation related to the Netherlands. Curated selection of digitised material includes a collection of ‘[Japanese Demands](#)’ to the VOC.
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventory of ‘Dutch Records’ (in Dutch and English).

Collection Data Sharing

- All archive series have inventories which are available as exports in XML (Encoded Archival Description (EAD)) and pdf from the portal, and digital scans are manually downloadable from the interface.
- [API available](#) for archive inventories and data scans/digital objects.
- Archive is following a Linked Open Data strategy and users can [search the archive using SPARQL](#).
- Indexes created as a result of research on the archives are available to be searched and downloaded (CSV):

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- [VOC: Oost-Indische testamenten](#) (VOC: East Indian wills).
- [VOC: Opvarenden](#) (VOC: Persons on board).
- [VOC: Overgekomen brieven en papieren](#) (VOC: Letters and papers received).
- [Sailing Letters](#) (from the Dutch Prize Papers project).

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Associated Projects/Exhibitions/Resources

The Nationaal Archief has collaborated or led multiple projects related to the VOC and their archives. Note involvement with the Network Digitaal Erfgoed/Digital Heritage Network which facilitates availability and enhancement of their collections using digital methodologies.

- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#), with Rijksuniversiteit te Utrecht.
 - Published inventories, archival skill building, digitisation across worldwide VOC archives (Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia, Western Cape Archives and Records Service, National Archives of Sri Lanka, Tamil Nadu Archives, British Library, Arkib Negara Malaysia).
 - Associated with UNESCO Memory of the World register.
 - Current resource platform is no longer supported but efforts to make live once more – see update on [Maritiem Portal](#).
- [UNESCO Memory of the World register](#) – Archives of the Dutch East India Company.
- Project '[De ijsberg zichtbaar maken](#)': searchable transcription of the VOC archives using a handwriting machine learning tool. Transcription data available CC0.
- Exhibition: 'De Wereld van de VOC' [The World of the VOC], 2017–2018.
- [Atlas of Mutual Heritage](#), with Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Rijksmuseum and Koninklijke Bibliotheek.
 - A searchable interface regarding the places and expeditions related to the VOC and WIC (map interface) and the documentation (predominantly visual: maps, drawings, prints and paintings) about them.
 - Provides digital access to resources across multiple international institutions.
- Projects in partnership with Huygens ING:
 - [The Dutch East India Company's shipping between the Netherlands and Asia 1595–1795](#) (Huygens ING) - csv download or search interface.
 - [Bookkeeper-General Batavia/Boekhouder-Generaal Batavia](#) (Huygens ING) - interface for searching voyages and cargo of VOC with a separate [Glossary](#).
 - [Globalise project](#) – a follow up project to 'De ijsberg zichtbaar maken' (above) developing an online infrastructure for VOC documents and reports through text recognition and machine learning ([current project 2021–2026](#)).

References

Gommans, J., Bes, L., & Kruijtzter, G. (2001). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 1. Bibliography and Archival Guide to the National Archives at the Hague (The Netherlands)*. Manohar Publ.

<https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/archief/2.14.97/invnr/8ED/file/Volume%20%20-%20Bibliography%20and%20Archival%20Guide%20to%20the%20National%20Archives%20at%20The%20Hague>.

Guleij, R., Knaap, G. J., Nasr, R., Noordervliet, N., Broecke, F. van den, & Dresscher, T. (Eds.). (2017). *Het Grote VOC Book* [The Dutch East India Company book]. WBooks, in co-operation with Nationaal Archief.

Nationaal Archief. (2024, September 6). Nationaal Archief. <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/>.

Overzicht van VOC-archieven, 1594-1814. (n.d.). Nationaal Archief. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/zoekhulpen/overzicht-van-voc-archieven-1594-1814>.

Pennings, J., & Raben, R. (1992). *Introduction to the Archives of the Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie*. Nationaal Archief. https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/sites/default/files/afbeeldingen/toegangen/NL-HaNA_1.04.02_introduction-VOC.pdf.

TANAP Database of VOC documents. (2018, June 19). *Maritiem Portal*. <https://maritiemportal.nl/tanap-database-of-voc-documents/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

[Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden](#) (Leiden University Library)

Library for the University of Leiden began in the 16th Century, and primarily collects material in support of the teaching, research and strategic goals of the university. Its special collections extend across medieval manuscripts, archives, old prints, maps, sketches, drawings and photographs.

Relevant Collections

- [Dutch East India Company charts collection](#), part of the Manuscript Maps Collection (largely from the map collection of [Bodel Neijenhuis](#)).
- VOC Governor General [Joan van Hoorn Archive](#).
- [Lapidarium Archive](#) – images of inscriptions in churches and cemeteries in former offices of the VOC in Asia and West Africa.
- [Collection of regulations concerning the administration of Batavia](#) (KITLV).

Collection Access

- Library [online catalogue](#).
- [Digital Collections](#).
- Part of the Bodel Neijenhuis collections feature as part of the [Atlas of Mutual Heritage](#).

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing

- Rights are reserved for information provided in collection database/catalogue. See [Terms and Conditions](#) regarding allowed uses.
- Digitised collections made available unless third party copyright.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- '[Mapping the Dragon: Vietnam through the eyes of the Dutch mapmakers](#)' (digital exhibition), by Martijn Storms in collaboration with Lam Ngo. Exhibition: Joke Pronk and Liesbeth van Wijk. September 2023.

References

Storms, M. (2023, September). *Mapping the Dragon: Vietnam through the eyes of the Dutch mapmakers* [Exhibition]. Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden.
<https://webpresentations.universiteitleiden.nl/s/vietnam/page/home>.

Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden. (n.d.). Universiteit Leiden. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.bibliotheek.universiteitleiden.nl/>.

Vries, D. de. (1996). *Uit de kaartenwinkel van de VOC. Catalogus van zeekaarten van de Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie in de Collectie Bodel Nijenhuis*. Alphen aan den Rijn.

[Universiteitsbibliotheek Utrecht, Special Collections](#)

Special collections held in the Library of Utrecht University. These collections include rare books, manuscripts and maps.

Relevant Collections

- [Cartography](#), for example:
 - '[Atlas Maior](#)' by Willem Jansz Blaeu.
 - [Manuscript maps by Isaac de Graaf, 1737](#) (Atlantic, Java Sea, Batavia and Bantam, Sunda Strait, and Sumatra).
 - [Partial Indian Ocean portolan](#) manuscript map reused to bind a book (Emendationum et observationum liber II).
 - [Portolan Map of Europe](#) by Willem Jansz Blaeu, 1615 (not VOC map).
 - An 18th century atlas of Ceylon: '[Beschryving van Zee-kusten, voornaamste baayen en ankerplaatsen, mitsgaders de daartoe behoorende land-vertooningen van het Eyland Ceylon](#)'.
 - 1644 Map of the south-west Pacific signed by Tasman '[Een grondigh onderwijs hoemen alder bequaemst sal cruijssen...](#)'.
- Books & Journals, for example, [Hindustani grammar](#) – 'Instructie of onderwijsinghe der Hindoustanse en Persiaanse ...' by VOC employee Joan Josua Ketelaar.

Collection Access

- Catalogue made available through [WorldCat](#) which connects to digitised collections ([list of digitised titles](#) available).
- Collections also searchable through [BASE](#).

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: Data available in WorldCat is (c) OCLC, no clear licensing statement for Utrecht University content.

References

Special Collections. (2024, August 5). Utrecht University. <https://www.uu.nl/en/special-collections>.

South Africa

[Kaapse Argiefbewaarplek/Western Cape Archives and Records Service, Cape Town](#)

The archives for the Province of the Western Cape. It holds ‘one of the most complete collections of VOC records’ (Hendrich, 2017, p. 95), that of the Government at Cape Town, back to the establishment of the outpost in 1652.

Relevant Series

- VOC government archives, the main components of which are:
 - Council of Policy (1652-1795) (C) (ZA KAB #_#_ZK1/1-1/277).
 - The Court of Justice (1652-1843) (CJ).
 - The Orphan Chamber (later Master of Supreme Court) (1670-1951) (MOOC).
- Maps from the 17th century onwards.

Collection Access

- [NAAIRS database](#), managed by the National Archives and Records Service of South Africa. Note: search function requires knowledge of series – TANAP useful.
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventory of holdings.

Collection Data Sharing: Three separate projects have made transcriptions of the archives (Malan & Liebenberg, 2020).

- TANAP (2001-2003) – made transcriptions of the Resolutions of the Council of Policy.
- Transcription of Estate Papers of the Cape of Good Hope (TEPC) (2004-2008) made transcriptions of selected papers from the Orphan Chamber and related documents.
- The Cape VOC Dagregisters/Journals Project (2015-2020) focused on journals and their verbatim copies.

The first two of these were originally made available through the TANAP project website but are not accessible in its current web-archive form. The [Nationaal Archief is working on making these available online again](#).

Digital access, on CD/DVD, is available if you can access or purchase the [Tracing History Trust](#) products, such as at the Archives and Records Service.

The Genealogical Society of South Africa (GSSA) has selected transcriptions of the Western Cape archive holdings of the [Court of Justice](#) and [Orphan Chamber](#) available on their website.

Licensing: No clear statement. GSSA requests ‘not be used in or by any commercial enterprise’.

References

Bes, L., & Kruitzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

Hendrich, G. (2017). 'A rich storehouse for research': The historical development of the Western Cape Archives and Records Service. *Southern Journal for Contemporary History*, 42(2), 74–97. <https://doi.org/10.38140/sjch.v42i2.3362>.

Malan, A., & Liebenberg, H. (2020). *Projects to transcribe archival documents: 2001-2020*. Tracing History Trust. <https://sadilar.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Summary-of-THT-projects-1.pdf>.

Provincial Archive Service: Overview. (n.d.). Western Cape Government. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.westerncape.gov.za/cape-archives>.

South African Records Transcribed. (n.d.). Genealogical Society of South Africa. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://eggssa.org/sarecords/>.

'tahirfarrath'. (2012, May 6). The TEPC Transcription Project. *Cape Malays... and Their Heritage*. <https://toyerfarrath.wordpress.com/2012/05/06/the-tepc-transcription-project/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

Products. (n.d.). Tracing History Trust. Retrieved 28 November 2024, from <https://www.tracinghistorytrust.co.za/products.htm>.

Sri Lanka

National Archives of Sri Lanka

The National Archives of Sri Lanka located in Colombo.

Relevant Series

- [Archives of the Dutch Central Government of Coastal Ceylon](#) (1640-1796).
- [Map Collection](#) – includes Dutch Period Maps and Plans which were handed over to the British administration in 1796.

Other Relevant Series

- [Consistory of the Dutch Reformed Church in Ceylon](#) (1735-1837) – also note listing of the Wolvendaal Church and Christian Reformed Church in Colombo by Bes & Kruijtzter (2015).

Collection Access

- [Online Index of the Sri Lanka National Archives](#): browsable by archival description or authority.
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventories for Dutch Central Government series.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: none stated.

References

Bes, L., & Kruijtzter, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

Sri Lanka National Archives. (n.d.). Department of National Archives Sri Lanka. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://archives.gov.lk/English>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

Switzerland

[Stiftsbibliothek, St. Gallen](#) (St. Gallen Abbey Library)

The research library, with a focus on the Middle Ages originally served the monastery/abbey at the site, and is now run by the Catholic Denomination Within the Canton of St Galls.

Relevant Collections

- Manuscript Journal and Travel Diary of George Franz Mueller (VOC Soldier 1669-1682): consists of illustrated Travel Diary ([Reisebuch](#)) and [chronological prose account](#) of his time in Indonesia.

Collection Access

- Online Union Catalogue [St Galler Bibliotheksnetz](#) (doesn't include manuscripts).
- Some manuscripts available through [e-codices](#) – the Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland.

Collection Data Sharing: e-codices allows metadata harvesting through [OAI interface based on Dublin Core](#).

Licensing: Digitised images through e-codices are either in the Public Domain or CC-BY-NC, and metadata use is CC-BY, unless using the OAI interface, which is Public Domain. See [Terms of Use](#).

References

Bes, L., & Kruitzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

<https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/archief/2.14.97/invnr/8ED/file/Volume%203%20-%20Archival%20Guide%20to%20Repositories%20Outside%20The%20Netherlands>.

Stiftsbezirk St. Gallen - Abbey Library. (n.d.). Stiftsbezirk St. Gallen. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.stiftsbezirk.ch/en/stiftsbibliothek>.

United Kingdom

The British Library

The National Library for the UK which encompasses millions of books as well as prints and drawings, maps, and manuscripts. Of particular interest are the former India Office Records – documents accumulated or acquired by the India Office (manager of British colonial interests in Asia: Britain occupied many VOC interests after the demise of the VOC and when Napoleonic France occupied the Netherlands).

Relevant Series

- Dutch Records from Malacca in the India Office Records ('Malacca Political Council, Court of Justice, and Orphan Chamber') (c1685-1835), [IOR/R/9](#) – VOC records from the VOC Government in Malacca.

Relevant Collections

- [Diary of Leendert Hasenbosch](#) – Dutch East India Company soldier who was deserted for sodomy.

Other Relevant Collections

- [MSS Eur – MacKenzie Private Collection](#) – an accumulation of manuscripts relating to (south) India and Indonesia, some of which derive from or are copies of VOC documents.
- Klencke Atlas, from the King's Topographical Collection, presented to King Charles II in 1660. Contains engravings by Joan Blaeu and Hondius.
- See also overview produced by [TANAP - archives](#).

Collection Access

- British Library Collections Online: currently down after a major cyber-attack.
 - The India Office Records have been [temporarily added to the National Archives Discovery](#) service to assist researchers during the outage: [India Office Records listing in the National Archives](#).
- [Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#): archived website of the TANAP project contains inventories of relevant records.

Collection Data Sharing

- The British Library has a dedicated '[BL Lab](#)' for data sharing and use of discrete sets of digital collections and data. No Dutch East India collections, but requests for datasets can be made.
- Most of the digital collection and electronic resources are currently unavailable due to the cyber attack.
- Out of copyright works are generally available on Archive.org and Flickr.

Licensing

- The British Library retains copyright of content created by them (e.g. collection data records) and asks that content not be used to create a database without their permission.

- Datasets and collection content copyright is clearly marked, with efforts to communicate clearly public domain or that made available under a Creative Commons licence.

References

Bes, L. (2007). Records in a Rival's Repository: Archives of the Dutch East India Company and Related Materials in the India Office Records (British Library), London (and the National Archives of Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur). *Itinerario*, 31(3), 16–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0165115300001170>.

Bes, L., & Kruitzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

The British Library: The National Library of the UK. (n.d.). The British Library. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.bl.uk/>.

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>.

[Historic Environment Scotland \(HES\)/Àrainneachd Eachdraidheil Alba and the Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historic Environment of Scotland \(RCAHMS\)](#)

The public body for the investigation, care and promotion of Scotland’s historic environment across archaeological, architectural, industrial and maritime heritage. Their archive contains research, records and images relating to sites and related activity.

Relevant Collections

Associated documentary material, such as excavation reports, artefact photographs and drawings of the:

- *Kennemerland* (1664).
- *De Liefde* (1711).
- *Adelaar* (1728).

Collection Access: The archive of RCAHMS are made available through the [CANMORE](#) online catalogue – only some items digitised.

Site Register/Portal

CANMORE holds the national register of sites, with 24 [registered wrecked ‘Dutch East Indiaman’](#).

Collection Data Sharing: wreck locations exportable to csv or kml; collection records to csv. Note site location results are OSGB36 (EPSG:27700) Protected.

Licensing: Collections are subject to Crown Copyright, or copyright is held by HES or third parties, and is indicated in records. Use/re-use of the database and its content is limited to personal, individual and educational use: see [Terms and Conditions](#).

References

National Record of the Historic Environment. (n.d.). Historic Environment Scotland (HES)/Àrainneachd Eachdraidheil Alba. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.historicenvironment.scot/archives-and-research/archives-and-collections/national-record-of-the-historic-environment/>.

National Archives, Kew

National Archives for the United Kingdom, located in Kew.

Relevant Series

- High Court of Admiralty, Prize Court, Prize Papers – Includes [6,000 boxes of 'Prize Papers' seized from ships in the 17th and 18th centuries](#).

Other Relevant Series

- [Secretaries of State: State Papers Foreign, Holland](#) (c1560-1780) – Note digitised in partnership with Gale Cengage Learning and available with institutional subscription.
- [Advisory Committee on Historic Wreck Sites \(ACHWS\)](#) – Agendas, Minutes and Papers.

Collection Access: [Discovery](#) is the National Archives portal. Note: also holds descriptions for more than 3,500 other archives held across the UK.

Collection Data Sharing: the [Discovery Web API](#) (still in development) aims to provide access to series description in The National Archives and also over 2,500 other institutions across the UK. Access provided on application. Use should adhere to Terms and Conditions.

Licensing: Content of National Archives material is in the majority available under the [Open Government Licence v3.0](#).

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Prize Papers Project](#), in partnership with the University of Oldenburg. Digitisation of content includes [objects](#).

References

Bes, L., & Krutzler, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

<https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/archief/2.14.97/invnr/8ED/file/Volume%203%20-%20Archival%20Guide%20to%20Repositories%20Outside%20The%20Netherlands>.

The National Archives (n.d.). The National Archives. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/>.

Prizepapers. (n.d.). Prizepapers. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.prizepapers.de/>.

United States of America

Bloomington Libraries - Lilly Library, Indiana University

Bloomington Libraries are responsible for the library, archival and special collections of Indiana University, located in Indianapolis in the United States. The Lilly Library is the rare books, manuscripts, and special collections library.

Relevant Collections

Boxer Manuscript II, 1500-1899 – the Collections of Charles Ralph Boxer (1904-2000). Research interests early contact between Europeans, particularly the Dutch, the Portuguese, and Jesuit missionaries, and Japan.

- Series: Bound; Sub-series: Dutch.
 - Verzameling van handteekeningen van personen, sedert 1594 in dienst van de Oost en de West-Indische Compagnie.' 1594.
 - Dutch East India Company Documents, 1602-1800.
 - 'St. James Fight.'
 - 'Sententie tegens Johan Barton de Mombas e carta original do Principe Nassau.' 1673.
 - 'Dutch East India Company Coastal Profiles from the North Atlantic to the South China Sea.' ca. 1680.
 - 'Logbook of VOC ship *Flora Vellum*.' 1731-.
 - Johan Paul Schagen. 'Beknopt vertug van 't werk 't welk dagelijke gedaan moet verden ten Comptoire van Heere Directeur Generaal van Nederlants Indië.' 29 November 1741.
 - 'Willem Jansz. van Amsterdam, admiral, en Willem Jansz. Van Amersfoort, vice-commandeur der O.I.C., in de eerste helft der 17de eeuw.' 1872.
- Series: Individually Foldered.
 - (Box 3 – 9 signed documents) 'Dutch East India Company (VOC) Records.' [A collection of original and copies of documents signed by a series of VOC administrators, who were or became Governor-General.] 1692-1736.
- Series: Oversize.
 - 'V.O.C. – Aanstelling brief van Antonio van Diemen' [letter patent from Directors of the VOC, appointing Van Diemen Director General and commander of the ten ship fleet to Batavia in 1632]. Middleburg, 1 October 1632.

Collection Access: [Archives online](#).

Collection Data Sharing: the Archival finding aid downloadable as XML (EAD); or in HTML.

Licensing: All Rights Reserved – permission outside of fair use must be obtained from the copyright holder.

References

Bes, L., & Krutzler, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

<https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/archief/2.14.97/invnr/8ED/file/Volume%203%20-%20Archival%20Guide%20to%20Repositories%20Outside%20The%20Netherlands>.

Repositories - Archives Online at Indiana University. (n.d.). Indiana University. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://archives.iu.edu/>.

Harvard Library

The Library for Harvard University, Massachusetts, United States – the oldest library in the US and one of the largest university libraries in the world. The Map Collection, which largely focuses on the Americas and Europe, has material relating to Dutch 17th and 18th century mapping and navigation.

Relevant Collections

- [Sea Atlases](#):
 - Willem Janszoon Blaeu's 1623 '[Het licht der see-vaert](#).'
 - de Wit's 1654 [Dutch Sea Atlas](#).
 - Pieter Goos' 1662 '[Le Grande en Nouveau Miroir ou Flambeau de la Mer](#).'
 - Gerard van Keulen's 1734 '[De Nieuwe Grootte Lichtende Zee-Fakkel](#).'
 - Louis Renard's 1745 '[Atlas van zeevaart en koophandel door de geheele weereldt](#).'
- Note also:
 - Arrowsmith '[World Map Showing Routes of Exploration and Discovery](#),' 1790.
 - [Clemenz Heinrich Wehdemann drawings of plants collected at Cape Town](#) (former VOC army enlistee sent to Cape Town).

Collection Access

- [HOLLIS](#) Library Catalogue.
- [Curiosity Collections](#): curated selection of collections digitised.
- [Harvard GeoSpatial Library](#): georeferenced search mechanism across Harvard and other US University map collections.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: Harvard Library makes their content available CC-BY unless governed by a third-party license.

Associated Projects/Exhibitions

- [Sea Atlases: A selection of atlases from the Harvard Map Collection](#) [online]

References

Harvard Library. (n.d.). *Sea Atlases: A selection of atlases from the Harvard Map Collection*. Retrieved 5 August 2024, from <http://sea-atlases.org/>.

Welcome to Library.Harvard. (2024, August 26). Harvard Library. <https://library.harvard.edu/>.

The Vatican

[Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana](#) (Vatican Apostolic Library)

The Library for the Vatican.

Relevant Collections

- Reg.lat.[2105](#), [2106](#) and [2107](#) – Three bound volumes, or atlases, of Johannes Vingboons watercolours originally from the collections of Queen Cristina of Sweden, featuring maps and drawings of VOC posts and ports in Africa.

Collection Access

- [Library catalog](#) (OPAC).
- [Library digital collections](#) – note images are watermarked.

Collection Data Sharing: none known.

Licensing: Vatican Library reserves all rights.

References

Vatican Apostolic Library. (n.d.). Vatican Apostolic Library. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.vaticanlibrary.va/>.

Other collections noted ...

[Baan Hollanda Foundation](#) - Information Centre on the History of Dutch-Thai Relations, Ayutthaya, Thailand

Located on the site of the former VOC Trading Post at Ayutthaya, and exhibits artefacts from excavation of the site.

[Bảo tàng Cổ vật Cung đình](#) (Hue Museum of Royal Antiquities), Hue, Vietnam

I was not able to determine the full scope of collections, but the institution holds a collection of Matchlock guns and 3 Dutch cannons made in 1640, 1661 and 1677/78 (Trương, 2011).

[Fort Belvoir](#), Virginia, U.S.A.

Four Dutch cannon, cast Middleburg, Netherlands, in 1626 and 1628 by Michael Burgerhuys, gifted to Japan 17th Century. Seized post WWII from Japan.

[Hirado Dutch Trading Post](#), Japan

Reconstruction of the Trading Post that was located in the small 1609-1640 after which trade could only occur through Dejima. I have not been able to determine whether material excavated from the site, or dredged from the harbour, are located here. Note also the nearby [Matsura Historical Museum](#).

[James Ford Bell Library](#), University of Minnesota, USA

Extensive historical map collection; also note contains documents of the Swedish East India Company.

[Museo Mario Brozoski de Puerto Deseado](#), Argentina

The Museum holds the finds from 2004-2006 investigations that located the wreck of the Dutch Southern Company yacht *Hoorn* (1615) in the Deseado River. This ship was part of the expedition with *Eendracht* led by Willem Cornelisz Schouten and Jacob le Maire which successfully found a route to the East Indies around South America. The Museum also holds items from British HMS *Swift*.

[Museum Arkeologi Onrust](#) (Onrust Archaeological Museum/Park), Indonesia

Part of the Jakarta Maritime Museum Management Unit which manages cultural heritage areas in the 'Thousand Islands' precinct. The Museum is located on Onrust Island where the VOC had shipyards and warehouses, and the collections features items excavated from that location.

[Museum and Art Gallery](#), Northern Territory, Darwin, Australia

The major collecting institution for the Northern Territory. They hold a small collection of items that bear the VOC insignia: a plaque from Desa Warawawang, Lakor Island, Southeastern Islands, South Moluccas, and a small cannon signed 'P Seest', 1777, also sourced from Indonesia (Bennett & Kelty,

2014). They also hold a VOC copper doir, dated 1780, sourced from Campbell Macknight's Macassan archaeological collection from fieldwork along the north coast of Australia: S111, from site 32G - Äningemerrugawa Island (Shasm Island to North Point Island) (Campbell Macknight, 1969).

[Nagasaki City Dejima Restoration Office, Japan](#)

The site was the centre of all European trade with Japan c.1640-1850. Today the site has been archaeologically investigated and the trade post buildings reconstructed. I have not been able to determine the extent or location of any archaeological collections. There is at least one VOC cannon at the site.

[National Museum of Taiwan History, Tainan, Taiwan](#)

The national museum holds works that relate to maritime trade and the colonial periods. Also note their recent exhibition [Transcending 1624 - Taiwan and the World](#) 1/2-30/6/2024.

[Natural History Museum, London, UK](#)

The national Natural History collection for the UK. Contains collections and works by individuals associated with the VOC, e.g. the [Hermann Herbarium of Sri Lankan plants](#); items collected by [Engelbert Kaempfer](#) from Japan (part of the Sloane Herbarium).

[Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands](#)

Botanical collections and works about Asian botany across books, journals, paintings and photographs (Bibliotheek van Naturalis). Collections include material collected and authored during the VOC period, for example, the [Hortus Indicus Malabaricus](#), a twelve-volume work on the flora of Asia, was authored by a Commissioner General of the VOC.

[Peabody Essex Museum, Massachusetts, USA](#)

The Peabody Essex Museum founding collections were that of the East India Marine Society in Salem, Massachusetts. The collections are a combination of 'natural and artificial curiosities' from the Pacific Northwest, Asia, Africa, Oceania, and India, acquired through maritime trade and travel. The Museum holds an impressive collection of Asian Export Art and Maritime History and Art that depicts, refers to or was part of VOC activity, such as Chinese export ceramics, Indian export textiles and other works. These are particularly evident in their exhibition with the Rijksmuseum 'Asia in Amsterdam' (Corrigan et al., 2015).

Projects and Resources

This section of the report details digital projects, platforms and resources that use, relate to, or share VOC collections, sites, and data (some may have already been referred to in relation to the institutions listed above).

[ASEAN Cultural Heritage Digital Archive \(ACHDA\)](#)

Digital collection portal that was in development by the Association of Southeast Asian Nations. First phase involved museums, galleries and libraries of Indonesia, Malaysia and Thailand, and was launched 27 February 2020. See: <https://asean.org/in-focus/>.

Website does not seem to work – <https://heritage.asean.org> – project may have faltered.

[Australia on the Map, Australasian Hydrographic Society](#)

Volunteer organisation emerging from the 400-year anniversary (2006) of the reported first European encounter with the Australian coast.

Features ‘Landing List’ – a register of ‘encounters’ with Australian coastline 1606 to 1814, and an English translation of the VOC Charter.

Landing List is also available through [Project Gutenberg](#).

[Big Anchor Project](#)

Project by the Nautical Archaeology Society, UK.

A fun, participatory project to record maritime heritage through registering instances of ‘anchors’. The anchor is often the most prominent public presence of maritime heritage due to the fact they are often used as public ornaments or repurposed for memorials. This project utilises this quality and created a mechanism through which to engage with a broader narrative of maritime heritage through the distribution of a single object type.

Users can add as little or as much as they like – from photograph and location, to specific descriptive data such as size and features. The hope is that through crowdsourcing data, a comprehensive tool for anchor identification will develop.

Data sharing: Uploaded data is considered the copyright of Nautical Archaeology Society. No data sharing mechanisms.

[Dutch Atlas of Mutual Heritage \(AMH\)](#)

‘The most complete overview of documentation about the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and the West India Company (WIC).’

Joint project between the Nationaal Archief, Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Rijksmuseum Amsterdam, and Koninklijke Bibliotheek, originally in collaboration with the TANAP project.

A GIS interface, or ‘Atlas’, launched in 2002 leveraging places and expeditions for access to documentary material about those places and associated activities of the VOC and WIC. Featured documentary materials, or ‘images’, are both digitised and richly described. Places are referred to as

‘Forts’ or ‘Posts’, and are conceptually linked through ‘Expeditions’, all of which are described in data and textual fields.

Features images of items from multiple national and international institutions (Amsterdam Historic Museum, Atlas Van Stolk, Badische Landesbibliothek, National Library of France, Bodel Nijenhuis / Universiteitsbibliotheek R.U.L., British Library, Fries Museum, Groninger Museum, KITLV, Royal Library, Maritime Museum, Museum Bronbeek, Nagasaki Municipal Museum, National Archive, National Library of Indonesia, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, RACM, Rijksmuseum Amsterdam, Scheepvaartmuseum, Stedelijk Museum Alkmaar, Tropenmuseum / KIT, University Library / UvA, Westfries Museum, and Zeeuws Museum) (Navarrete Hernández 2014, 50).

Data sharing: no access to or sharing of underlying data of collections or places/expeditions.

[Dutch Ships and Sailors](#)

A project that brings together/provides an infrastructure for multiple maritime historical datasets using semantic web technology, specifically focusing on the ships and their crew. Identifies and develops common vocabularies to enrich and link existing data.

Utilises the VOC-Opvarenden (Nationaal Archief), Dutch-Asiatic Shipping, and Bookkeeper-General Batavia datasets/indexes. Also uses and makes available (xlsx) the [Generale Zeemonsterrollen VOC, 1691-1791](#) (also available through Maritiem Portal) which details 5321 records of ships and crew composition.

Infrastructure requires use of query language (SPARQL).

Data sharing: list of source datasets provided, and resulting data available through [DANS](#).

[Dutch Trading Post Network](#)

Network of institutions in the private and public sector that work with heritage of the Dutch East India Company (VOC).

Relevant places currently involved: Ambon (City Government), Anping (Taijiang National Park), Ayutthaya (Baan Hollanda Foundation), Banda (Banda Heritage Foundation), Galle (Galle Heritage Foundation), Hirado (Hirado Dutch Trading Post), Jakarta (Indonesian Documentation Centre of Architecture), Melaka (Melaka World Heritage Office), Muziris (Muziris Heritage Office), Nagasaki (Nagasaki City Dejima Restoration Office), Tainan (Tainan Cultural Association) and Ternate (Ternate Heritage Society).

Aims are to:

- Share knowledge and encourage research.
- Promote exchange/interaction, including education and skills.
- Increase awareness of VOC history and related sites, and the links between them.

Note: No updates since 2021.

[Europe's Asian Centuries: Trading Eurasia 1600-1830, Global History and Culture Centre, University of Warwick](#)

An academic research project led by Professor Maxine Berg that aimed to compare Europe's trade with India in high quality textiles and other fine manufactured goods with its trade with China in

porcelain and other consumer and luxury goods. The project used the records of Europe's East India companies and major museum collections of export-ware objects.

The project's '[Dutch data](#)' is derived from the National Archives series ('VOC resolutions'), 'Eisen der Retouren' or demands for returns in books (NA/VOC/159-173). The spreadsheets list the amount, different types and qualities of goods ordered from the Dutch Republic over this period.

The project also developed a textile database and glossary and conducted oral histories with modern Indian textile industry.

The project's XLSX data downloads are not available to external users. Contact project lead Professor Maxine Berg for access.

[Het Geheugen](#)

Het Geheugen/The History is a digital image portal for curated collections of materials (paintings, drawings, stamps, posters and photographs) about or relating to the Netherlands from 92 institutions. The portal is a service of the Koninklijke Bibliotheek funded by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. The last curated collections were added in 2012 and it is currently a static resource.

Features a general search tool, and browsing by institution and by curated 'Collections' is possible. In this way it is both a database and guided exhibition/communication of institutional collections. There is no data export.

Collections of interest include:

- [Sunken Treasures](#): maritime objects from shipwrecks in the National Maritime Archaeology Collection (RCE).
- [Japanese Demands](#): digitised archive of the Nationaal Archief that records the gifts to maintain trade relationship between the VOC and a Japanese Shogun.
- [The Netherlands – Japan](#): digital exhibition of the collections from the Koninklijke Bibliotheek and the National Diet Library of Japan recognising the 400 year relationship between the two countries which started with VOC trading relations.
- [Atlases from the Maritime Museum](#): Digitisation of The Atlas Van Loon and Johannes van Keulen's Zee-Fakkel, two of the highlights of 17th century cartography, held by the Scheepvaartmuseum.

[Global Encounters and First Nations Peoples: 1000 Years of Australian History](#)

Project led by Professor Lynette Russell AM at Monash University which explores the encounters between Australia's Indigenous peoples and voyages from the sea over the course of a millennium. The project focuses at centring First Nations experience, knowledge and agency to explore a period of history that has been overwhelmingly told from Euro-centric perspectives, or overlooked entirely.

Project outputs related to the VOC include (but are not limited to):

- An '[Encounters Map](#)' – provides details regarding the instances of encounter along the Australian coastline.

- The '[1623 Project](#)' – a blog following the voyages of *Pera* and *Arnhem* as part of the Carstensz. expedition along the coast of Cape York Peninsula in 1623 and their encounters with the Indigenous First Nations communities.

[GLOBALISE Project, Huygens ING](#)

Current research project (Jan 2022-Dec 2026) based on the 'Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren' ('Letters and papers received', OBP) of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) held by the Nationaal Archief.

The project aims to semantically map the information on people, places and activities about the VOC and the peoples they came in contact with held within the content of this archive.

This will involve:

- transcribing the digital scans of this archive using advanced automatic handwritten text recognition techniques (an extension of the project '[De ijsberg zichtbaar maken](#)' ([Making the iceberg visible](#))).
- Use language modelling to recognise 'entities' within the text and derive a 'digital encyclopaedia' from the resource.
- Manually check automated data extraction.
- Integrate the results into the GLOBALISE thesaurus – Old Dutch/Dutch/English.
- Re-contextualise entities and naming derived from the archive through developing a knowledge graph (in partnership with guest/partner researchers).
- Make content, such as encyclopaedia, thesaurus and linguistic model, available to researchers.

Experiments and prototypes of tools using the project data are made available through the [GLOBALISE LAB](#).

Data is made available through their [Dataverse](#). Relevant datasets currently include:

- [GLOBALISE Thesaurus - Commodities](#) (subject-specific classification/hierarchisation and thesaurus of commodities shipped in the early modern Indian Ocean World).
- [ESTA Database Locations](#) (the locations in the Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) project's database on slave trade movements, often maritime, in the larger Indian Ocean basin and East Asia).
- [VOC Prices in the Dutch-Asian Trade, 1608-1800](#) (contains original (true to source), extrapolated, interpolated and imputed data on the prices of different commodities in their place of purchase and in Amsterdam).

[Global Sea Routes \(GSR\): A Historical Geodatabase of European Global Navigation \(1500-1900\)](#)

Relational geo-database of voyages, ships, people, maps and places for the period 1500-1900, to represent global maritime connections (Project is current as of 2024). The project is developed by [DiSU](#) (University of Trieste-Department of Humanities), [Miur-Prin 2017](#), [Regione Friuli Venezia Giulia](#), [Fondazione Benefica Kathleen Foreman Casali](#), with the collaboration of the [Magazzino 26-Civico Museo del Mare](#), Trieste, [IMM - Istituto Idrografico della Marina](#) (Italian Navy Hydrographic

Institute), and [AIC - Associazione italiana cartografia](#) (Italian Cartographic Association). Content produced by the project is published under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 license. Uses NodeGoat – the web-based data management and analysis environment developed by LAB1100.

The project uses archival and published source material – e.g. maps, travel accounts and logbooks. For the VOC, uses Bruijn et al. (1987, 1979, 1979) *Dutch Asiatic Shipping in the 17th and 18th Centuries*, 3 Vols, and the Huygens ING data resource ‘The Dutch East India Company’s Shipping Between the Netherlands and Asia 1595-1795’ (see below).

[Huygens ING, KNAW Resources](#)

Netherlands research institute for history and culture, part of the wider KNAW Humanities Cluster which focuses ‘on connecting people, research, data and collections’.

Multiple digital resources are hosted and developed by or with Huygens ING. These include:

- Digitised publications on the VOC, including indexes/transcriptions of related archives published in the 19th and 20th centuries.
- Open resources/data resulting from research projects.

Some individual datasets and files are also available through [DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities](#) (also an institute of KNAW).

Licensing: [CC BY-NC-SA](#).

Digital projects/databases include the following. Note some, such as [GLOBALISE](#), are also listed separately.

- ‘The Dutch East India Company’s shipping between the Netherlands and Asia 1595-1795’, otherwise known as ‘[Dutch Asiatic Shipping](#)’ (DAS). This is the digital index of the key aspects of every VOC voyage detailed in *Dutch Asiatic Shipping in the 17th and 18th Centuries* (Bruijn et al., 1979-1987), derived primarily from the logbooks kept in the VOC archives (Nationaal Archief). Includes:
 - Digitisation of *Dutch Asiatic Shipping* publication (pdf).
 - Database of voyages – 8194 – for browsing and searching.
 - Download csv datasets of voyages, including with data of people onboard.
 - List of errata.
- [Boekhouder-Generaal Batavia](#) (Bookkeeper-General Batavia) is a database for the circulation of commodities of the VOC in the 18th century, derived from the surviving VOC Bookkeeper General’s accounts held in the Nationaal Archief. Includes:
 - Database of voyages – 18,322 – for browsing, searching and downloading (xlsx).
 - Database of cargo – 245,405 – for browsing, searching and downloading (xlsx – whole dataset cannot be downloaded at once).
- [VOC-Glossarium](#) (in Dutch) is a database of Dutch terms from the VOC archives, developed from multiple published sources to aid in understanding the material. Can be browsed and searched. Also available as a publication for download (pdf).

[De ijsberg zichtbaar maken \(Making the iceberg visible\)](#)

Nationaal Archief project for transcribing the content of archives, with transcriptions improved/enhanced through machine learning to identify people, places and times. Made available through the Nationaal Archief. This project has been expanded upon by the GLOBALISE project (see listing in this document).

The project started with the VOC archives (Nationaal Archief 1.04.02). Scans, transcriptions and resulting indexes are available CC0. Training data for the machine learning has also been made available ([Keijser, 2024](#)).

[Managing Cultural Heritage Underwater \(MACHU\)](#)

Project by Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. User only interface (log-in required).

Web-based GIS application for management and research of underwater cultural heritage sites, initially at a European scale with seven separate countries. The digital system is also used for the exchange of data on Dutch ships (of all periods) overseas.

Data is provided by MACHU partners and third parties as layers, and users can create new layers for personal use. A log-in is required for use of resource due to sensitive nature of data (such as the exact locations of UCH sites), and use limited to the scientific community and professionals (note comparison with MaSS which is a more public oriented approach).

[Maritime Stepping Stones \(MaSS\)](#)

Project by Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, developed from the RCE Wrecks in Situ and MACHU projects.

GIS interface for wrecks and UCH sites, specifically to place the sites in their archaeological and heritage environments, for the benefit and interest of a general public. Anyone can apply to become contributors to the platform.

Filters include by site/vessel type, shipping route, and broad historical subject areas.

Data sharing: API for 'search', 'list', 'get' and 'references' requests, returns in JSON. Data provided as CC BY-SA. No data store.

[Old Maps Online](#)

A map interface for searching and viewing 'old maps'. Currently over 500,000 maps added. Partnering institutions include British Library, Leiden University and Nationaal Archief.

The project is volunteer run, developed from collaboration between Klokan Technologies GmbH, Switzerland and The University of Portsmouth, UK with funding from JISC and MapTiler.com.

Users can add maps, georeference, view, overlay and compare in map interface (Open Street Map), and transcribe map content. Maps are searchable through description content, timeline, attributes, and geolocation. The platform allows geotiff exports of maps. A 'Georeferencer' assists in assigning geolocations to scanned images for upload to the platform.

[De VOC Site](#)

A website and database with compiled information on the history, trading posts, and ships of the VOC, as well as information regarding books and other resources about them. Website resource managed and produced by Jaap van Overbeek.

Includes searchable glossaries on:

- ‘Ship-building’.
- ‘Sails and rigging’.
- ‘Staff and organisation’.
- ‘Navigation’.
- ‘Products’.
- ‘Geographical names’.
- Nicolaas Witsen’s 1671 *Explanation of ship proverbs, and various own names*.

‘Links’ page gives reference to online resources. Many are now out of date/no longer supported suggesting the website is no longer actively maintained.

All rights are reserved for use of the website’s content – reproduction permission to administrator info@vocsite.nl. No data export.

[Het Maritiem Erfgoedonderzoek van Onroerend Erfgoed \(Maritime Heritage Survey of Immovable Heritage, Belgium\)](#)

Database ‘Maritieme Archeologie’ supported by the Vlaams Instituut voor het Onroerend Erfgoed, Cel Maritiem Erfgoed (VIOE – Flemish Heritage Institute), Provincie West-Vlaanderen – Museum Walraversijde, and Flanders Marine Institute (VLEZ). Project completed (?) 2014.

Register of ‘wrecks’, ‘structures’, ‘artefacts’, ‘events’, ‘locations’ and references/resources (photographs, charts/maps, publications, museums) for maritime heritage in Flanders.

Two ‘Dutch Eastindiamen’ wrecks listed – *Vliegent Hert* (as ‘Vliegent Hart’) and *Noordmunster*.

No search mechanism or data export.

[Maritiem Portal \(Maritime Portal\)](#)

Portal, in Dutch, managed by the ‘Maritieme Koepel’ (Maritime Organisation) – a group of museums, research institutes, associations and foundations in the field of maritime history in the Netherlands, and as part of the Maritime-Historical Data Network of the Huygens ING – KNAW.

Intentions are to bring the many maritime-historical organisations in contact with one another as well as to make their resources and efforts more visible to the general public. Designed as a resource to be browsed. Content of the website is CC BY-NC-ND.

Information includes:

- Agenda – events/exhibitions/symposia etc.
- Institutions – list of participating and relevant institutions to Maritime History.
- Collections – blog or feed of descriptions and links to resources, such as data, projects, dissertations, books, magazines etc.

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- Links – grouped by different cultural periods. [1600-1780](#) relevant.
- Access to the New Maritime History of the Netherlands (as well as the old one).
- Collections portal – in development by the Netwerk Maritieme Bronnen (NMB – Maritime Resources Network) (contact Gerhard de Kok).

[Maritime Archaeological Archive Repository and Educational Resource \(MAARER\)](#)

Resource developed and managed by a group of independent individuals for education and information. It is a good demonstration of public engagement and demand for data, as well as curated content.

Resources include:

- Artefact archive (data) – artefacts recovered from *Vliegende Hert* (as 'T'Vliegende Hart') and *Rooswijk*.
- Shipwreck Archive (data).
 - located and investigated VOC ships.
 - VOC shipwrecks in media/museum (incomplete).
 - VOC shipwrecks by year sunk.
- Shared research papers, books, online videos and documentaries.
- Featured photographers.
- 3D resources (imbedded Sketchfab).

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[Maritime Careers: The Life and Work of Dutch Merchant Marine Sailors, 1700-Present](#)

A blog by historians Jelle van Lottum and Lodewijk Petram featuring updates and insights from their research into maritime careers/biographies as part of multiple, broader projects which utilise archival source material. Scope includes 18th century VOC sailors.

Connected to Dutch Prize Papers project and VOC Data Experience, supported by Huygens ING.

[Prize Papers projects](#)

The Prize Papers, held by the [British National Archives, Kew](#), are papers from ships captured by British privateers and the Royal Navy between 1652 and 1815, as well as the court papers generated by legal proceedings to determine the legality of the 'prize'.

There are two projects associated with the Prize Papers: the 'Dutch Prize Papers' project, Huygens Institute, and the 'Prize Papers' project, led by Göttingen Academy of Sciences and Humanities. Both projects involve the digitisation and 'sorting' of the 'Prize Papers'.

[Dutch Prize Papers](#), Huygens Institute project targeted two specific series for digitisation within the Prize Papers, HCA 30 and HCA 32. They created a database of the documents contained within these series with data regarding the date, ship and shipmaster. The scans are available through [Nationaal Archief series 2.22.24](#), as well as an [index](#) and related [dataset](#).

The [Prize Papers project](#) led by Göttingen Academy of Sciences and Humanities, based at the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Germany, and The National Archives, UK, extends the work of the Dutch Prize Papers project. It aims to digitise, catalogue, describe and present in an open-access research-oriented database the whole of the Prize Papers series. The project is mindful of the ‘materiality’ of the archive and documentation is not just focusing on textual content. Project outputs include Workshops and [‘Documentaries’](#) that explain and explore the archive as material object, a reconfiguring/representation of collections.

Searching/browsing directed through Documents, Ships, Court processes, Document types, Subjects, materiality, and appeals. Research portal still under development at the time of writing this report: <https://portal.prizepapers.de/index/>.

[Silk Roads Programme, UNESCO](#)

Website for the representation of the rich history and shared legacy of the historic Silk Roads, which includes the activity of the VOC.

Contains information and links to relevant ‘Institutions’, ‘Museums’, ‘Cities’, ‘Countries’, and a ‘Knowledge Bank’ (publications). Also contains information under certain ‘themes’ such as – relevant to this project – ‘Documentary Heritage’ (archives) and ‘Underwater Heritage’ (shipwrecks).

[Southeast Asia Historical Maps: Digital Historical Maps of Singapore and Southeast Asia project](#)

An online digital collection curated to showcase pre-1900 maps of Southeast Asia, funded by a Singapore Ministry of Education Social Science Research (SSR) Thematic Grant. Participating collections include National Library of Singapore, Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden, Yale University Library – Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library, and Bodleian Libraries, presented by Yale NUS College.

Maps are searchable according to collection, author/creator, publisher, date, and geolocation, as well as map attributes, such as presence of cartouches, or particular geographical features, such as the presence of forts.

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[Stigting VOC Foundation – ‘Interaktiewe Kaart van VOC in die Kaap’ \[Map\]](#)

Geolocated VOC related buildings, farms, outposts, shipwrecks, cannon stations etc present in the vicinity of ‘the Cape’, presented in [Google Maps](#) for public use. The resource was developed by the [VOC Foundation](#), South Africa (Volunteer organisation) in 2021-2022. The data is available as KML download, and the Foundation retains copyright.

[Towards a New Age of Partnership \(TANAP\)](#)

Project led by the Nationaal Archief and Leiden University for the preservation and protection of VOC archives internationally, and their improved accessibility and use.

Archives referenced include:

- National Archief.

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- Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia - ANRI (Indonesian National Archives).
- Tamil Nadu Archives (Chennai, India).
- National Archives of Sri Lanka, Colombo.
- Kaapse Argiefbewaarplek/Western Cape Archives and Records Service, Cape Town.
- British Library, India Office collections.
- Arkib Negara Malaysia (National Archives, Malaysia).

Project website feature:

- Description of each of the archive institutions.
- Information about the VOC, its administration, structure, and archives.
- Inventories of relevant VOC archives (browsable or downloadable as pdf – EAD standard).
- A search of the database of VOC documents – by reference code, establishment, or geographical name.
- Virtual reconstruction of archives of VOC establishments – where original administration was lost.
- Searchable transcription of the Western Cape Resolutions of the Council of Policy.
- Searchable transcription of the Western Cape Inventories of the Orphan Chamber.
- Glossary for Western Cape Archives.

Original website is now inactive, and only accessible through web.archive.org. This has affected the functionality of some of the resources. The Nationaal Archief are currently working to make the site available again at tanap.nl.

Note: related registration of the ‘Archives of the Dutch East India Company’ as part of the UNESCO ‘Memory of the World’ in 2003 (application submitted 2002).

[Wreck Site](#)

Wreck site is a public wreck database, where users can access documentation of wrecks around the world. Some content and functionality, including adding/editing and exporting information is reserved for subscribers.

Data sharing: for subscribers only.

[Wrecks in Documents](#)

Dataset of c. 400 ships wrecked in the Texels by RCE for the [MACHU](#) project, made available through the Maritime Portal by Huygens ING: <https://maritiemportal.nl/wrecks-in-documents-dataset/>.

Data is in an XLSX spreadsheet, utilising Geonames, Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names, CC BY-NC-ND.

References

A working public reference library for the MOB-VOC project is accessible at <https://www.zotero.org/groups/5409389/mob-voc/library>.

Individuals

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Institution/Project/Resource websites

The 1623 Project. (2023, April 12). Global Encounters and First Nations People.

<https://www.monash.edu/arts/monash-indigenous-studies/global-encounters-and-first-nations-peoples/news-and-blog/the-1623-project>

Accueil Monnaie de Paris. (n.d.). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.monnaiedeparis.fr/en>

A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection. (n.d.). Kansalliskirjasto Nationalbiblioteket [National Library of Finland]. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/en/collections/e-nordenskiold-collection>

Amsterdam Museum. (n.d.). Amsterdam Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.amsterdammuseum.nl/>

Archief Resources. (n.d.). Huygens Instituut. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/resources/>

Archives of the Dutch East India Company—Memory of the World. (n.d.). UNESCO. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://www.unesco.org/en/memory-world/archives-dutch-east-india-company>

Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia. (n.d.). <https://anri.go.id/>

Art Gallery Greater Vic. (n.d.). Art Gallery of Greater Victoria. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://aggv.ca/>

Art Gallery of South Australia. (n.d.). AGSA - The Art Gallery of South Australia. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.agsa.sa.gov.au/>

ASEAN GOING DIGITAL to preserve the region's cultural heritage. (n.d.). In Focus - ASEAN Main Portal. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://asean.org/in-focus/>

Asian Civilisations Museum. (n.d.). Asian Civilisations Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/acm/>

Atlas of Mutual Heritage. (n.d.). Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.atlasofmutualheritage.nl/en/>

Australasian Hydrographic Society. (2022, March 28). *Australia on the Map.* InternetArchive. <https://web.archive.org/web/20220328232753/https://www.australiaonthemap.org.au/>

Australian National Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Australian National Maritime Museum. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.sea.museum/>

Australian National Maritime Museum, Sydney, Australia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/australia-national-maritime-museum>

Aziatische Keramiek—Platform voor liefhebbers van Aziatische Keramiek. (n.d.). Aziatische Keramiek. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.aziatiskeramiek.nl/>

Bảo tàng lịch sử Quốc gia [Vietnam National Museum of History]. (n.d.). *Bảo Tàng Lịch Sử Quốc Gia [Vietnam National Museum of History].* Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://baotanglichsu.vn/en>

Bảo Tàng Tỉnh Bà Rịa - Vũng Tàu [Ba Ria - Vung Tau Museum]. (n.d.). *Bảo Tàng Tỉnh Bà Rịa - Vũng Tàu [Ba Ria - Vung Tau Museum].* Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.baotangbrvt.org.vn/>

Bayworld, Port Elizabeth. (n.d.). Bayworld. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.bayworld.co.za/>

Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum. (n.d.). Bergens Sjøfartsmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sjofartsmuseum.museumvest.no/>

Bezoek Batavialand, het museum van Flevoland, te Lelystad. (n.d.). Batavialand. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.batavialand.nl/>

Bibliothèque Nationale de France. (2024, September 3). BnF - Site institutionnel. <https://www.bnf.fr/>

Big Anchor Project. (n.d.). Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://biganchorproject.com/>

Bijzonder geld: De Nationale Numismatische Collectie. (n.d.). De Nederlandsche Bank. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.dnb.nl/betalen/bijzonder-geld-de-nationale-numismatische-collectie/>

Blue Penny Museum | Art & History of Mauritius. (n.d.). Blue Penny Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://bluepenny.museum>

Blue Penny Museum. (n.d.). *MoMAA Museum of Modern African Art.* Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://momaa.org/directory/blue-penny-museum/>

Boekhouder-Generaal Batavia / Bookkeeper-General Batavia. (n.d.). Huygens ING. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://bgb.huygens.knaw.nl/>

The British Library: The National Library of the UK. (n.d.). The British Library. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.bl.uk/>

British Museum. (n.d.). The British Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.britishmuseum.org/>

Bruijn, J. R., Gaastra, F. S., & Schöffer, I. (2022, November 10). *The Dutch East India Company's shipping between the Netherlands and Asia 1595-1795 (Dutch-Asiatic Shipping in the 17th and 18th centuries)* [Huygens Instituut]. https://resources.huygens.knaw.nl/das/index.html_en

Catalogue of Library Holdings. (n.d.). The Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://rgssa.org.au/library/catalogue-of-library-holdings>

The Coin Cabinet—Museum of Cultural History. (n.d.). University of Oslo. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.khm.uio.no/english/collections/coin-cabinet/index.html>

ColBase: Integrated Collections Database of the National Institutes for Cultural Heritage, Japan. (n.d.). ColBase. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://colbase.nich.go.jp/?locale=en>

Columbus House—Museum of Porto Santo. (n.d.). Cultura Madeira. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://cultura.madeira.gov.pt/en/columbus-house-porto-santo-museum>

Dejima, Nagasaki. (n.d.). Dejima. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://nagasakidejima.jp/english/nagasakidejima.jp/english/>

Department of Archaeology. (n.d.). University of Cape Town. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://science.uct.ac.za/departments/archaeology>

Digital Historical Maps of Southeast Asia. (n.d.). Southeast Asia Historical Maps. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://historicalmaps.yale-nus.edu.sg/>

Dutch Prize Papers | Homepage. (n.d.). Huygens Instituut. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://prizepapers.huygens.knaw.nl/>

Dutch Ships and Sailors. (n.d.). Huygens ING. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://dutchshipsandsailors.nl/>

Dutch Trading Post Heritage Network. (n.d.). DTPHN. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.dtpnhn.org>

East London Museum. (n.d.). East London Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.elmuseum.za.org/East-London-Museum/>

Europe's Asian Centuries: Trading Eurasia 1600-1830. (n.d.). The University of Warwick. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/arts/history/ghcc/eac/>

Frederik Hendrik Museum. (n.d.). Mauritius Museums Council. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://mauritiusmuseums.govmu.org/mauritiusmuseums/?page_id=1822

Global Encounters. (n.d.). Global Encounters. Retrieved 29 November 2024, from <https://globalencounters.net/>

Global Encounters & First Nations Peoples: 1000 Years of Australian History. (n.d.). Monash Indigenous Studies Centre. Retrieved 29 November 2024, from <https://www.monash.edu/arts/monash-indigenous-studies/global-encounters-and-first-nations-peoples>

Global Sea Routes | Public Interface. (n.d.). Nodegoat. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://gsr.nodegoat.net/viewer.p/57/2230/types/all/list/>

Groninger Museum. (n.d.). Groninger Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.groningermuseum.nl/en/>

Het Geheugen. (n.d.). Het Geheugen, Ontwikkeld Door de Koninklijke Bibliotheek. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://geheugen.delpher.nl/nl>

Het Scheepvaartmuseum | The National Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Het Scheepvaartmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.hetscheepvaartmuseum.com/>

Hirado Dutch Trading Post Homepage - Hirado Dutch Trading Post Reconstructed Buildings of the Nationally Designated Historic Site 'Hirado Dutch Trading Post Ruins' [Official]. (n.d.). 平戸オランダ商館 / Hirado Dutch Trading Post. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://hirado-shoukan.jp/>

Holdings. (n.d.). Directorate of State Archives, Kolkata, West Bengal. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://sadte.wb.gov.in/index.php/holdings>

Hout Bay Museum. (n.d.). Hout Bay Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://houtbaymuseum.co.za/>

Huygens Institute & partners. (2024, June 20). *GLOBALISE: Unlocking the history of early globalisation and colonialism for researchers and the general public*. GLOBALISE. <https://globalise.huygens.knaw.nl/>

Interaktiewe Kaart van VOC in die Kaap. (n.d.). Foundation VOC. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://archive.voc-kaap.org/projects/interaktiewe-kaart/>

Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. (n.d.). Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/>

Isles of Scilly Museum. (n.d.). *Isles of Scilly Museum*. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.iosmuseum.org/>

Iziko Museums. (n.d.). Iziko Museums of South Africa. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.iziko.org.za/>

James Ford Bell Library. (2024, September 8). University of Minnesota Libraries. <https://www.lib.umn.edu/collections/special/bell>

KBR • Royal Library of Belgium. (2024, June 14). KBR. <https://www.kbr.be/en/>

Klokan Technologies GmbH. (n.d.). *OldMaps Online*. OldMapsOnline. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://www.oldmapsonline.org/>

Kunstmuseum Den Haag—Hét museum voor moderne kunst in Nederland—Te Den Haag. (n.d.). Kunstmuseum Den Haag. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.kunstmuseum.nl/nl>

Kyoto National Museum. (n.d.). Kyoto National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kyohaku.go.jp/eng/>

Kyushu National Museum. (n.d.). Kyushu National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.kyuhaku.jp/>

Lottum, J. van, & Petram, L. (n.d.). *Maritime Careers—The Life and Work of Dutch Merchant Marine Sailors, 1700-Present*. Maritime Careers. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://www.maritimecareers.eu/>

Lukut Museum. (n.d.). Department of Museums Malaysia. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.jmm.gov.my/en/museum/lukut-museum>

MAARER. (n.d.). MAARER - Maritime Archaeological Archive Repository & Educational Resource. Retrieved 3 September 2024, from <https://www.maarer.com/>

Macau Museum. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/museu-do-centro-cientifico-e-cultural-de-macau>

Macau Scientific and Cultural Centre. (n.d.). *Centro Científico e Cultural de Macau*. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.cccm.gov.pt/en/>

Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/marine-heritage-gallery-indonesia>

Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta (MHG). (n.d.). Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta (MHG). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://marineheritagegallery.wordpress.com/>

Maritiem Museum Rotterdam—*Ontdek de enorme invloed van de maritieme wereld op ons dagelijks leven*. (n.d.). Maritiem Museum Rotterdam. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://maritiemmuseum.nl/>

Maritiem Portal – *Alles over maritieme geschiedenis*. (n.d.). Maritiem Portal. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://maritiemportal.nl/>

Maritieme Archeologie: *Databank voor Maritiem Erfgoed*. (n.d.). Maritieme Archeologie. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://www.maritieme-archeologie.be/default.aspx>

Maritime Archaeology Databases. (n.d.). Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/>

Maritime Archaeology Trust. (n.d.). *Maritime Archaeology Trust*. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://maritimearchaeologytrust.org/>

Maritime Archaeology Unit. (n.d.). Central Cultural Fund. <https://mau.ccf.gov.lk/>

Maritime Archaeological Depot. (n.d.). Batavialand. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://www.batavialand.nl/kennis-en-collecties/maritiem-archeologisch-depot>

MaritimeLanka. (n.d.). Maritime Asia. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://maritimeasia.ws/maritimelanka/index.html>

Maritime Museum. (n.d.). Department of National Museums. https://www.museum.gov.lk/web/index.php?option=com_regionalm&task=regionalmuseum&id=8&lang=en

Maritime Trade. (n.d.). Asian Civilisations Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/acm/galleries/maritime-trade/maritime-trade>

MaSS—Stepping Stones of Maritime History. (n.d.). [Database]. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://mass.cultureelerfgoed.nl/>

Matsura Historical Museum – Housing over a thousand years of history. (n.d.). Matsura Historical Museum. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <http://www.matsura.or.jp/en/home-2/>

Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap. (2019, September 11). *MACHU (Managing Cultural Heritage Underwater) [Onderwerp]*. Cultural Heritage Agency; Ministerie van Onderwijs, Cultuur en Wetenschap. <https://english.cultureelerfgoed.nl/topics/maritime-heritage/machu>

Monnaie de Paris, Paris, France. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/monnaie-de-paris>

Musée national des arts asiatiques-Guimet. (n.d.). Musée Guimet. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.guimet.fr/>

Museon-Omniversum. (n.d.). Museon Omniversum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museon-omniversum.nl/>

Museum Arkeologi Onrust - Sistem Registrasi Nasional Museum. (n.d.). Sistem Registrasi Nasional Museum Kemdikbud. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://10.24.26.63/museum/profile/museum+arkeologi+onrust>

Museum Joure, daar maak je het! (n.d.). Museum Joure. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museumjoure.nl/en/>

The Museum of St Helena Island. (n.d.). The Heritage of St Helena. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museumofsainthelena.org/>

Museus de Cabo Verde. (n.d.). Museus de Cabo Verde. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.museus.cv/en/home>

Museu Quinta das Cruzes. (n.d.). Quinta Das Cruzes Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://mqc.madeira.gov.pt/en/>

muZEEum. (n.d.). Maritiem Muzeum Zeeland. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.muzeem.nl/english>

Nara National Museum. (n.d.). Nara National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.narahaku.go.jp/english/>

Nationaal Archief. (2024, September 6). Nationaal Archief. <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/>

Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen, Amsterdam, Netherlands. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/tropenmuseum>

The National Archives (n.d.). The National Archives. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/>

National History Museum. (n.d.). Mauritius Museums Council. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://mauritiusemuseums.govmu.org/mauritiusemuseums/?page_id=1843

National Library of Australia. (n.d.). National Library of Australia. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.nla.gov.au/>

National Museum of Singapore. (n.d.). National Museum of Singapore. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/nationalmuseum/>

National Museum of Taiwan History. (n.d.). National Museum of Taiwan History. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nmth.gov.tw/en/Default.aspx>

National Record of the Historic Environment. (n.d.). Historic Environment Scotland (HES)/Àrainneachd Eachdraidheil Alba. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.historicenvironment.scot/archives-and-research/archives-and-collections/national-record-of-the-historic-environment/>

National Shipwreck Database of Sri Lanka. (n.d.). Central Cultural Fund. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://nsd.ccf.gov.lk/index.php>

The Natural History Museum. (n.d.). The Natural History Museum. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nhm.ac.uk/>

Naturalis Biodiversity Center | Museum and research in Leiden. (n.d.). Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.naturalis.nl/en>

Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/naturalis-biodiversity-center>

Nautical Museums Trust Limited. (n.d.). *Shipwreck Museum.* Shipwreck Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://shipwreckmuseum.co.uk/>

Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven. (n.d.). Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://zilvermuseum.com/>

OKS - Ottema-Kingma Stichting. (n.d.). OKS - Ottema-Kingma Stichting. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.oks.nl/>

Online Finding Aid. (n.d.). National Archives of Malaysia. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://ofa.arkib.gov.my/portal/index.php/en/>

Országos Széchényi Könyvtár. (n.d.). Országos Széchényi Könyvtár. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://oszk.hu/en>

Österreichische Nationalbibliothek - Startseite. (n.d.). Österreichische Nationalbibliothek. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.onb.ac.at/>

Our Story. (n.d.). Baan Hollanda. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://baanhollanda.org/our-story/>

Overbeek, J. van. (n.d.). *De VOC Site: Homepage.* De VOCsite. Retrieved 3 September 2024, from <https://www.vocsite.nl/index.php>

Overzicht van VOC-archieven, 1594-1814. (n.d.). Nationaal Archief. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/onderzoeken/zoekhulpen/overzicht-van-voc-archieven-1594-1814>

Peabody Essex Museum | World-Renowned Art Museum In Salem, MA. (n.d.). Peabody Essex Museum. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.pem.org/>

Plataforma Online. (n.d.). Museu Da Madeira. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://museus.madeira.gov.pt/>

Port-Louis. (n.d.). Musée National de La Marine. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.musee-marine.fr/en/our-museums/port-louis.html>

Powerhouse Museum. (n.d.). Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://powerhouse.com.au/>

The Princessehof. (n.d.). Keramiek Museum Princessehof. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://princessehof.nl/undefined>

Prizepapers. (n.d.). Prizepapers. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.prizepapers.de/>

Project 'Verborgen kaart': Versmelten van de wetenschappen. (n.d.). Maritiem Museum Rotterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://maritiemmuseum.nl/onderzoek/project-verborgen-kaart>

Products. (n.d.). Tracing History Trust. Retrieved 28 November 2024, from <https://www.tracinghistorytrust.co.za/products.htm>

Provincial Archive Service: Overview. (n.d.). Western Cape Government. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.westerncape.gov.za/cape-archives>

Repositories - Archives Online at Indiana University. (n.d.). Indiana University. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://archives.iu.edu/>

Rijksdienst Cultureel Erfgoed [Cultural Heritage Agency]. (n.d.). Rijksdienst Cultureel Erfgoed. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://english.cultureelerfgoed.nl/>

Rijksmuseum, hét museum van Nederland. (n.d.). Rijksmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/nl>

Royal Armouries, National museums of arms and armour. (n.d.). Royal Armouries. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://royalarmouries.org/>

Royal Collection Trust. (n.d.). Royal Collection Trust. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rct.uk/>

Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. (n.d.). The Royal Geographical Society of South Australia. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://rgssa.org.au/>

Royal Museums Greenwich. (n.d.). Royal Museums Greenwich. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.rmg.co.uk/>

SA Fisheries Museum. (n.d.). SA Fisheries Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://safisheriesmuseum.co.za/index.html>

SAHRA. (n.d.). South African Heritage Resources Agency. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.sahra.org.za/>

SAHRIS. (n.d.). South African Heritage Resources Information System. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sahris.org.za/>

Sejarah Nusantara. (n.d.). Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia. <https://sejarah-nusantara.anri.go.id/archive/>

Shaping Australia. (n.d.). Commonwealth Bank. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.commbank.com.au/about-us/shaping-australia.html>

Shetland Museum & Archives. (n.d.). Shetland Museum & Archives. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/>

The Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum. (n.d.). *The Shipwreck Centre & Maritime Museum*. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://museum.maritimearchaeologytrust.org/>

Shipwreck Collection | Maritime Museum. (n.d.). South Australian Maritime Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://maritime.history.sa.gov.au/collections/>

Shipwrecked ceramics. (n.d.). Victoria and Albert Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.vam.ac.uk/articles/shipwrecked-ceramics>

Shipwreck Museum. (n.d.). Western Cape Government. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.westerncape.gov.za/facility/shipwreck-museum>

Shipwreck Treasure Museum. (n.d.). Shipwreck Treasure Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://shipwreckcharlestown.co.uk/>

Sierra Leone Heritage. (n.d.). Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <http://www.sierraleoneheritage.org>

Sierra Leone National Museum. (n.d.). eHive. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://ehive.com/collections/6125/sierra-leone-national-museum>

Silk Roads Programme. (n.d.). UNESCO. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://en.unesco.org/silkroad/>

Simon's Town Museum. (n.d.). Simon's Town Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <http://www.simonstownmuseum.org.za/>

Skógar Museum—Museum Iceland. (n.d.). Skógasafn Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.skogasafn.is/skogar-museum/>

South African Records Transcribed. (n.d.). Genealogical Society of South Africa. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://eggsa.org/sarecords/>

Special Collections. (2024, August 5). Utrecht University. <https://www.uu.nl/en/special-collections>

Sri Lanka National Archives. (n.d.). Department of National Archives Sri Lanka. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://archives.gov.lk/English>

State Library New South Wales. (n.d.). State Library New South Wales. <https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/>

State Library of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia. (n.d.). Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/state-library-of-new-south-wales>

State Library of Western Australia. (n.d.). Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://slwa.wa.gov.au/>

Stichting Nationaal Museum van Wereldculturen en de Stichting Wereldmuseum Rotterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://collectie.wereldmuseum.nl/#/query/f2185a0b-61e9-41a4-8eed-6533d80c1f11>

Stichting Texels Museum. (n.d.). Stichting Texels Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.texelsmuseum.nl/>

Stiftsbezirk St. Gallen - Abbey Library. (n.d.). Stiftsbezirk St. Gallen. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.stiftsbezirk.ch/en/stiftsbibliothek>.

Tamil Nadu Archives and Historical Research. (n.d.). Tamil Nadu Archives and Historical Research. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://tamilnaduarchives.tn.gov.in/WEB/EN/>

TANAP: Towards a New Age of Partnership in Dutch East India Archives and Research. (2018, June 23). [Archived: Internet Archive]. TANAP. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180623003007/http://www.tanap.net/index.htm>

Te Papa. (n.d.). Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://tepapa.govt.nz/>

Tokyo National Museum - Tohaku. (n.d.). *Tokyo National Museum*. Tokyo National Museum. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.tnm.jp/>

Underwater Archaeology. (n.d.). National Monuments Service. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.archaeology.ie/underwater-archaeology>

Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden. (n.d.). Universiteit Leiden. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.bibliotheek.universiteitleiden.nl/>

V&A - The family of art, design and performance museums. (n.d.). *Victoria and Albert Museum*. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.vam.ac.uk/>

Vatican Apostolic Library. (n.d.). Vatican Apostolic Library. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://www.vaticanlibrary.va/>

VOC-Glossarium. Verklaringen van termen, verzameld uit de Rijks Geschiedkundige Publicatiën, die betrekking hebben op de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie. (2021, August 22). [Huygens Instituut]. Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis. <https://resources.huygens.knaw.nl/vocglossarium/inleiding>

Welcome to Library.Harvard. (2024, August 26). Harvard Library. <https://library.harvard.edu/>

Welcome to the National Museum of Ireland. (n.d.). National Museum of Ireland. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.museum.ie/en-ie/home>

Welcome to the National Museum of Malaysia. (n.d.). Muzium Negara. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.muziumnegara.gov.my/en>

Welcome to the SA Naval Museum. (n.d.). SA Naval Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://sanavymuseum.co.za/>, <https://sanavymuseum.co.za/>

Welcome to the Silentworld Foundation. (n.d.). Silentworld Foundation. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://silentworldfoundation.org.au/>

Welcome to the Western Australian Museum. (n.d.). Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://visit.museum.wa.gov.au/>

Wereldmuseum: Amsterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Amsterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://amsterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

Wereldmuseum: Leiden. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Leiden. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://leiden.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

Wereldmuseum: Rotterdam. (n.d.). Wereldmuseum Rotterdam. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://rotterdam.wereldmuseum.nl/nl>

Wrakkenmuseum Terschelling. (n.d.). Wrakkenmuseum Terschelling. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://wrakkenmuseum.nl/>

Wreck archive. (n.d.). National Monuments Service. Retrieved 5 September 2024, from <https://www.archaeology.ie/underwater-archaeology/wreck-archive>

Wreck Site. (n.d.). Wreck Site. Retrieved 3 September 2024, from <https://www.wrecksite.eu/>

Wrecks in Documents. (n.d.). Maritiem Portal. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://maritiemportal.nl/wrecks-in-documents-dataset/>

Zeeuws Archief. (n.d.). Zeeuws Archief. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/>

Zeeuws Museum—In Middelburg—Discover Zeeland. (n.d.). Zeeuws Museum. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsmuseum.nl/en>

Zoeken in transcripties. (n.d.). Nationaal Archief. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <https://zoekintranscripties.nl/>

广东省博物馆 [Guangdong Museum]. (n.d.). Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.gdmuseum.com/cn>

文物館 Art Museum. (n.d.). The Chinese University of Hong Kong Art Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.artmuseum.cuhk.edu.hk/en/>

Exhibitions

Akveld, L. M., & Jacobs, E. M. (2002). *De kleurrijke wereld van de VOC: Nationaal Jubileumboek VOC, 1602-2002* [The colourful world of the VOC: National Anniversary Book VOC, 1602-2002]. Thoth.

Bennett, J., & Kelty, R. (with Art Gallery of South Australia & Art Gallery of Western Australia). (2014). *Treasure ships: Art in the age of spices*. Art Gallery of South Australia.

Berghuis, T. J., Loon, P., & Museum van Loon (Eds.). (2013). *Suspended histories*. Museum Van Loon. <https://www.trfineart.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/Suspended-Histories-LR.pdf>

Bibliothèque Nationale de France. (2012). *L'Âge d'or des cartes marines. Quand l'Europe découvrait le monde* [Exhibits]. Bibliothèque Nationale de France. <https://expositions.bnf.fr/marine/index.htm>

Brickwrecks: Sunken ships in LEGO® Bricks. (n.d.). Australian National Maritime Museum. Retrieved 3 September 2024, from <https://www.sea.museum/whats-on/exhibitions/brickwrecks>

Brown, R. M., & Sjostrand, S. (2001). *Maritime archaeology and shipwreck ceramics in Malaysia*. Published on the occasion of the exhibition Malaysian Maritime Archaeology by Dept. of Museums & Antiquities in collaboration with Nanhai Marine Archaeology Sdn. Bhd.

Brunton, P. & State Library of New South Wales. (2006). *First sight: The Dutch mapping of Australia, 1606-1697*. State Library of New South Wales.
https://www2.sl.nsw.gov.au/archive/events/exhibitions/2006/firstsight/docs/firstsight_guide.pdf

Clark, G. (2014, February 17). Diane KW: At World's End. *CFile - Contemporary Ceramic Art + Design*.
<https://cfileonline.org/exhibition-diane-kw-worlds-end/>

Collecting and empire. (2020, August 21). *British Museum*.
<https://www.britishmuseum.org/blog/collecting-and-empire>

Corrigan, K., Campen, J. van, Diercks, F., Blyberg, J. C., Peabody Essex Museum, & Rijksmuseum (Netherlands) (Eds.). (2015). *Asia in Amsterdam: The culture of luxury in the Golden Age*. Peabody Essex Museum; Rijksmuseum.

Council of Australian State Libraries (CASL) & National Library of Australia. (2006, September 6). *South Land to New Holland: Dutch Charting of Australia 1606–1756*. National Library of Australia.
<https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20060906040101/http://www.nla.gov.au/exhibitions/southland/index.html>

Dewez, S. (2006). *Western Edge. John Curtin Gallery. 6 October - 8 December 2006* (C. Malcolm, P. Williams, & B. Cotter, Eds.). John Curtin Gallery.

Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe. (n.d.). The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Faculty of Arts. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from
<https://arts.cuhk.edu.hk/web/index.php/news-and-events/enchanting-expeditions-chinese-trade-porcelains-across-globe>

Flores, W., & Modest, W. (with Obata, I.). (2024). *Onze koloniale erfenis [Our colonial heritage]*. Lannoo; Wereldmuseum Amsterdam.

Gaillard, K., Berg, E. van den, & Keramiekmuseum Princessehof (Eds.). (2019). *Gezonken schatten: Vondsten uit scheepswrakken van de maritieme zijderoute 800-1900 = Sunken treasures: discoveries in shipwrecks from the maritime silk road 800-1900*. Waanders Uitgevers.

Guanyu Wang, & Art Museum, The Chinese University of Hong Kong. (n.d.). *Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe*. Google Arts & Culture. Retrieved 6 August 2024, from
<https://artsandculture.google.com/story/rAXhy7Zg9ox7ow?hl=en>

Guleij, R., Knaap, G. J., Nasr, R., Noordervliet, N., Broecke, F. van den, & Dresscher, T. (Eds.) (with Nationaal Archief). (2017). *Het Grote VOC Book [The Dutch East India Company book]*. WBooks, in co-operation with Nationaal Archief.

Harvard Library. (n.d.). *Sea Atlases: A selection of atlases from the Harvard Map Collection*. Retrieved 5 August 2024, from <http://sea-atlases.org/>

Hofmann, C., Richard, H., & Vagnon, E. (with Bibliothèque nationale de France). (2012). *L'âge d'or des cartes marines: Quand l'Europe découvrait le monde [exposition, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris, 23 octobre 2012-27 janvier 2013]*. Seuil Bibliothèque nationale de France.

Hogarth, C. (with Museum of Victoria, Western Australian Museum, & Queensland Museum). (2000). *Shipwreck: Discoveries from our earliest shipwrecks, 1622-1797*. International Cultural Corporation of Australia. <https://archive.org/details/shipwreckdiscove0000hoga>

Huyn, T. (2019, June). Di sản từ những con tàu đắm / Sunken treasures. *Heritage*, 36–41.

IJzerman, J. W., & Vereeniging Koloniaal Instituut Amsterdam. (1919). *Catalogus van de tentoonstelling ter herdenking van het 300-jarig bestaan van Batavia, gehouden in het stedelijk museum, Amsterdam, Juni-Juli 1919 [Catalog of the exhibition commemorating the 300th anniversary of Batavia, held in the Stedelijk Museum, Amsterdam, June-July 1919]*. Vereeniging Koloniaal Instituut.

Jorgensen, D. (2016, November 4). Indian Ocean Shipwrecks: Four exhibitions in Western Australia. *Artlink Magazine*, 36(4). <https://www.artlink.com.au/articles/4544/indian-ocean-shipwrecks-four-exhibitions-in-weste/>

La route des Indes est pave d’inaccessibles paves. (2002, August 8). *Le Monde*, 19.

Lasschuijt, H., & Hessing, M. (2002). *Upstream guide 07.09 t/m 20.10.2001*. Stichting Upstream.

Lee, P., Andaya, L. Y., Watson Andaya, B., Newton, G., & Chong, A. (2016). *Port cities: Multicultural emporiums of Asia, 1500-1900*. Asian Civilisations Museum. https://www.academia.edu/55490903/Port_Cities_Multicultural_Emporiums_of_Asia_1500_1900

L’Hour, M., Long, L., & Rieth, . (1989). *Le ‘Mauritius’: La mmoire engloutie*. Casterman.

Lydon, J., Paterson, A., Souter, C., Snell, T., & Uhlmann, P. (2018). *Batavia: Giving voice to the voiceless* (P. Leach, Ed.). Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery.

Maritime Trade. (n.d.). Asian Civilisations Museum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/acm/galleries/maritime-trade/maritime-trade>

Mateer, J., Wattel, A., & John Curtin Gallery (Eds.). (2017). *Invisible genres: Two essays on iconclasm*.

McCarthy, M., Stanbury, M., & Jones, D. S. (2007). *Voyages of Grand Discovery* (M. McCarthy & V. Northey, Eds.). Western Australian Museum.

Muse des arts dcoratifs (Bordeaux, Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France) & Muse d’Aquitaine de la ville de Bordeaux (Eds.). (1998). *La route des Indes: Les Indes et l’Europe, changes artistiques et hritage commun, 1650-1850*. Muse des arts dcoratifs; Muse d’Aquitaine; Somogy ditions d’art.

Muse national de la marine, & De Thoisy-Dallem, A. (2002). *Trsors d’ocans: L’archologie sous-marine sur la route des Indes*. Musee national de la Marine.

National library of Australia (Ed.). (2013). *Mapping our world: Terra incognita to Australia*. National Library of Australia.

National Palace Museum. (2018, December 20). *Expedition to Asia—The Prominent Exchanges between East and West in the 17th Century* [Exhibits]. National Palace Museum; National Palace Museum. <https://theme.npm.edu.tw/exh107/ExpeditiontoAsia/en/index.html#main>

National Palace Museum. (2022, September 24). *Boundless – A Maritime Perspective of East-West Cultural Exchange in the 16th Century* [Exhibits]. National Palace Museum; National Palace Museum. <https://theme.npm.edu.tw/exh112/Boundless>

Peters, M., & Stichting Historisch Onderzoek in Woord en Beeld. (2002). *In steen geschreven: Leven en sterven van VOC-dienaren op de kust van Coromandel in India* [Written in stone: Life and death of VOC servants on the coast of Coromandel in India]. Stichting Historisch Onderzoek in Woord en Beeld; Uitgeverij Bas Lubberhuizen.

Pettifer, D., & Snell, T. (2020). *Drew Pettifer: A Sorrowful Act: the Wreck of the Zeewijk*. Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery.

Richards, M., & O'Connor, M. (Eds.). (1993). *Changing Coastlines. Putting Australia on the World Map 1493-1993*. National Library of Australia.

http://www.nla.gov.au/sites/default/files/changing_coastlines.pdf

Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Huygens Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis, & Quist, T. (2018, June 18). *De Rooswijk, een virtuele tentoonstelling* [The Rooswijk, a virtual exhibition] [Exhibits]. Huygens Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis. <http://rooswijk.huygens.knaw.nl/>

Rijksmuseum. (1980). *Prijs der zee. Vondsten uit wrakken van Nederlandse Oost-Indiëvaarders uit de zeventiende en achttiende eeuw in de verzameling van de afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis van het Rijksmuseum*. Rijksmuseum.

Russ, V. (2019). *Saltwater Mapping: A Berndt Museum exhibition at the Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery*. Berndt Museum of Anthropology, University of Western Australia.

Scheurbuik & Scheepsbeschuit. Leven aan boord van een VOC-schip. (n.d.). Zeeuws Archief. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/agenda/scheurbuik-scheepsbeschuit-leven-aan-boord-van-een-voc-schip/>

Sint Nicolaas, E., & Smeulders, V. (with Rijksmuseum). (2021). *Slavery: The story of João, Wally, Oopjen, Paulus, van Bengalen, Surapati, Sapali, Tula, Dirk, Lohkay*. Atlas contact Rijksmuseum.

Spiegel der Welt. (n.d.). Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/spiegelderwelt/>

State Library New South Wales. (n.d.). *Voyages of Discovery: The Great South Land*. State Library New South Wales. <https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/stories/voyages#!/st/0>

Storms, M. (2023, September). *Mapping the Dragon: Vietnam through the eyes of the Dutch mapmakers* [Exhibition]. Universitaire Bibliotheken Leiden. <https://webpresentations.universiteitleiden.nl/s/vietnam/page/home>

Submerged: Stories of Australia's shipwrecks. (n.d.). Australian National Maritime Museum. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.sea.museum/whats-on/exhibitions/submerged>

Tentoonstelling Afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis: Prijs der Zee: Vondsten uit wrakken van Oostindiëvaarders: 6 februari -1 augustus 1980. (1979). *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 27(4), 212–213.

Terry, M. (2000, June). Bring a plate [A Curious Coincidence exhibition—17th century Dutch explorers encounter Australia, part of this year's exploration of the United Dutch East India Company in Australian history]. *Signals*, 51, 4–6.

Under Southern Skies. (n.d.). Australian National Maritime Museum. Retrieved 9 August 2024, from <https://www.sea.museum/under-southern-skies>

Universtetet i Oslo Myntkabinettet & Dokumentasjonsprosjektet. (n.d.). *Norwegian coins through 1000 years*. Myntkabinettets Elektroniske Myntutstilling [University of Oslo's Coin Cabinet Exhibition]. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from https://www.dokpro.uio.no/umk_eng/utstill.html

Vink, M. (2003). Leo Akveld and Els M. Jacobs, *De Kleurrijke Wereld van de VOC: Nationaal Jubileumboek VOC, 1602–2002*. Bussum: Uitgeverij THOTH2002. 191 pp. ISBN 90-6868-300-4. *Itinerario*, 27(2), 155–158. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0165115300020611>

VOC Data Experience—VOC Data Experience. (2021, April 15). <https://vocdataexperience.nl/>

VOC-handel met Ceylon. (n.d.). Zeeuws Archief. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/agenda/foto-expositie-voc-handel-met-ceylon/>

Western Australian Museum. (2016). *Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World*. Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum. (n.d.). *1616 Dirk Hartog*. Western Australian Museum. Retrieved 11 September 2024, from <http://museum.wa.gov.au/explore/dirk-hartog>

Wind in the sails. Marine Painters from the Golden Age: Paintings from the Anthony Inder Rieden collection. (n.d.). muZEEum. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.muzeem.nl/en/node/221>

Wrecked! Tragedy and the Southern Seas. (n.d.). South Australian Maritime Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://maritime.history.sa.gov.au/events/wrecked-tragedy-and-the-southern-seas/>

Zeeland en Japan. Eilanden in contact. (n.d.). Zeeuws Archief. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/agenda/zeeland-en-japan-eilanden-in-contact/>

石文誠, 廖伯豪, & 吳佳霓 (with 吳密察 & 鄭維中). (2024). 「跨.1624: 世界島臺灣」特展展覽專刊 [Transcending 1624: Taiwan and the world] (鳳氣至純平 & Christopher J. Finder (范大龍), Trans.). 國立臺灣歷史博物館 [National Museum of Taiwan History]. https://www.nmth.gov.tw/News_Publish_Content.aspx?n=4164&s=200849

References

Adams, G. K. (2024, August 22). Fears for collection as shipwreck museum is put up for sale. Museums Association. <https://www.museumsassociation.org/museums-journal/news/2024/08/fears-for-collection-as-shipwreck-museum-is-put-up-for-sale/>

The A. E. Nordenskiöld Collection in the Helsinki University Library. Annotated Catalogue of Maps made up to 1800. (1979–1995). Vol. I–III. Compiled by Ann-Mari Mickwitz, Leena Miekkaavaara and Tuula Rantanen. Vol. IV. Compiled by Tuula Rantanen. Vol. V:1–2. By Cecilia af Forselles-Riska. Helsinki.

Agreement between Australia and the Netherlands Concerning Old Dutch Shipwrecks, and Arrangement [1972] ATS 18 (1972). <https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/other/dfat/treaties/ATS/1972/18.html>

A hymn board from the golden ship. (n.d.). Skógasafn Museum. Retrieved 13 August 2024, from <https://www.skogafn.is/skogar-museum/artifacts/a-hymn-board-from-the-golden-ship/>

Ariese, C. (2012). *Databases of the people aboard the VOC ships Batavia (1629) & Zeewijk (1725): An analysis of the potential for finding the Dutch castaways' human remains in Australia*. WA Museum. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.16_people_aborde_the_voc_ships_batavia_and_zeewijk.pdf

Arnim, Y. von (2003). *'Kraak' porcelain from the shipwreck Banda (1615) recovered by Jacques Dumas in 1979*. Mauritius Museums Council; Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Arnim, Y. von (2015, July). Le quadri-centenaire de la mort de Pieter Both et les vestiges du naufrage de sa flotte à Maurice. *Diodon. Bulletin du Mauritius Marine Conservation Society*, 36(1), 12–16.

Arnim, Y. von (2023). *Artefacts from the Banda, a Dutch East Indiaman wrecked at Mauritius in 1615, a shipwreck artefact catalogue*. Mauritius Museums Council and Mauritius Marine Conservation Society.

Attahiyyat, C., & Dinas Museum dan Pemugaran. (2000). *Pulau Onrust* [Onrust Island]. Dinas Museum dan Pemugaran Propinsi DKI Jakarta.

Australian National Maritime Museum. (2001). Temporary Exhibitions. In *Australian National Maritime Museum Annual Report 2000-2001* (pp. 11–14). Australian National Maritime Museum. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-2062498302>

Australian National Maritime Museum. (2023). *Australian National Maritime Museum Annual Report 2022-23*. Australian National Maritime Museum. <https://www.sea.museum/about/corporate-information/planning-and-reporting/annual-reports>

The Batavia Tapestry: A tragic tale told in stitch. (2017). *Signals*, 119, 22–29.

Bax, A., & Martin, C. J. M. (1974). De Liefde. A Dutch East Indiaman lost on the Out Skerries, Shetland, in 1711. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 3(1), 81–90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1974.tb00861.x>

Berg, M., Gottman, F., Hodacs, H., & Nierstrasz, C. (Eds.). (2015). *Goods from the East, 1600-1800: Trading Eurasia*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Bettencourt, J., Dias, A., Lima, C., Chouzenoux, C., Fonseca, C., Pereira, D., Lopes, G., Coelho, I., Monteiro, J., Lima, J., Alves, M. E., Carvalho, P., & Silva, T. (2020). Arqueologia Marítima em Cabo Verde: Enquadramento e primeiros resultados do projecto concha. In *Arqueologia em Portugal. 2020 – Estado da Questão* (pp. 2071–2084). Associação dos Arqueólogos Portugueses.

Bes, L. (2007). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 2. Archival Guide to the Repositories in The Netherlands Other than the National Archives*. Manohar Publishers & Distributors.

Bes, L. (2007). Records in a Rival's Repository: Archives of the Dutch East India Company and Related Materials in the India Office Records (British Library), London (and the National Archives of Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur). *Itinerario*, 31(3), 16–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0165115300001170>

Bes, L. (2012). Gold-Leaf Flattery, Calcuttan Dust, and a Brand New Flagpole: Five Little-Known VOC Collections in Asia on India and Ceylon. *Itinerario*, 36(1), 91–106. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0165115312000381>

Bes, L., & Kruitzer, G. (2015). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 3. Archival guide to repositories outside the Netherlands*. Manohar.

- B. K. [Bas Kist], J., & Sténuît, R. (1977). De 'Witte Leeuw'. De schipbreuk van een schip van de v.o.c. In 1613 en het onderwateronderzoek naar het wrak in 1976. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 25(4), 163–178.
- Blak, G. L. (2007). *Archives of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and the Local Institutions in Batavia (Jakarta)*. Brill.
- Bonke, H., Parthesius, R., & Pijl - Ketel, C. van der (Eds.). (2007). *Artefacts catalogue Avondster site 1998-2004: the Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman that was wrecked twice in Ceylon*. Centre for International Heritage Activities.
- Bound, M. (1997). The Dutch East Indiaman 'Nassau.' *Minerva*, 8(5), 28–32.
- Bound, M., Ong Soo Hin, & Pickford, N. (1998). The Dutch East Indiaman 'Nassau', lost at the Battle of Cape Rachado, Straits of Malacca. In M. Bound (Ed.), *Excavating ships of war* (pp. 84–105). Anthony Nelson.
- Brady, K. (2017). The Zeepaard and the Blind Harbour wreck: Investigations of two 17th-century wrecks in Broadhaven Bay (County Mayo, Ireland). In J. Gawronski, A. Van Holk, & J. Schokkenbroek (Eds.), *Ships And Maritime Landscapes: Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Symposium on Boat and Ship Archaeology, Amsterdam 2012* (pp. 416–422). Barkhuis.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt20p56b6>
- Brinck, N. (2020). *Kanonnen van Nederland: Nederlands geschut en andere oude kanonnen in Nederland [Guns of the Netherlands: Dutch cannon and other old guns in the Netherlands]* (2nd revised edition). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed.
- Brinckmann, H. (2008, November 12). *Erasmus/De Liefde*. Under auspices of the Japan-Netherlands Society, Tokyo National Museum. https://habri.jp/uk/contents/erasmus_de_liefde.html
- British Museum. (2023, 18 October). *British Museum sets out plans to digitise fully the collection* [Press Release]. https://www.britishmuseum.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/British_Museum_sets_out_plans_to_digitise_fully_the_collection.pdf
- Brommer, B. (2009). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. V. Afrika/Africa*. (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Brown, R. M., & Sjostrand, S. (2001). *Maritime archaeology and shipwreck ceramics in Malaysia*. Published on the occasion of the exhibition Malaysian Maritime Archaeology by Dept. of Museums & Antiquities in collaboration with Nanhai Marine Archaeology Sdn. Bhd.
- Brugge, Jeroen ter. 'Wrakvondsten in het Rijksmuseum: evaluatie en koersbepaling voor de toekomst' Notitie van de afdeling geschiedenis. [Internal Report]. Rijksmuseum, September 2018.
- Bruijn, J. R., Gaastra, F. S., & Schöffer, I. (1979-1987). *Dutch-Asiatic shipping in the 17th and 18th centuries* (3 Vols). Nijhoff.
- Burningham, N., & Jong, A. (1997). The Duyfken Project: An Age of Discovery ship reconstruction as experimental archaeology. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 26(4), 277–292.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1997.tb01339.x>
- Calderon, Mary Jane. (1989). Underwater Archaeology in the Philippines. *Philippine Quarterly of Culture and Society* 17(4): 322–25.

Campbell, P. B. (2023). A History of Maritime Archaeological Thought. In S. A. Rich & P. B. Campbell (Eds.), *Contemporary philosophy for maritime archaeology: Flat ontologies, oceanic thought, and the Anthropocene* (pp. 11–34). sidestone press. <https://www.sidestone.com/books/contemporary-philosophy-for-maritime-archaeology>

Campbell Macknight, C. (1969). *The Macassans: a study of the early trepang industry along the Northern Territory coast* [PhD, Australian National University]. <https://doi.org/10.25911/5d78dc67c8646>

Campen, Jan van, Ebeltje Hartkamp-Jonxis, and Rijksmuseum. *Asian Splendour: Company Art in the Rijksmuseum*. Zutphen, Netherlands: Walburg Pers, 2011.

Castro, F., Jobling, J., Budsberg, N., Loewen, B., & Dieulefet, G. (2020). *Marine Astrolabes Catalogue* (ShipLAB Report 16.3). J. Richard Steffy Ship Reconstruction Laboratory, Texas A&M University. <https://www.academia.edu/download/63768183/SLR16.3-Astrolabes20200628-54641-p73cil.pdf>

Ciarlo, N. C. (2008). La Arqueología Subacuática En Argentina. Reseña Histórica De Los Antecedentes, Desarrollo De La Especialidad Y Estado Actual De Las Investigaciones. *Revista de Arqueología Americana*, 26, 41–69.

Craddock, P. T., and D. R. Hook. 'Ingots from the Sea: The British Museum Collection of Ingots'. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 16, no. 3 (August 1987): 201–6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1987.tb00587.x>.

Craddock, Paul, and Duncan Hook. 'An Economic History of the Post-Medieval World in 50 Ingots: The British Museum Collection of Ingots from Dated Wrecks'. *The British Museum Technical Research Bulletin* 6 (2012): 55–68.

Curtsinger, B., & Sténuit, B. (1975, August). The Treasure of Porto Santo. *National Geographic*, 148, 120–136.

Da Costa Kaufmann, T., & North, M. (2015). *Mediating Netherlandish Art and Material Culture in Asia*. Amsterdam University Press. https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/315/edited_volume/book/66408

Dauchez, D. M. (2022, March 31). *Die Arqueonautas Studiensammlung im Maritimen Museum*. Internationales Maritimes Museum Hamburg. <https://www.imm-hamburg.de/2022/03/die-arqueonautas-studiensammlung-im-maritimen-museum/>

Delgado, J. P. (Ed.). (1997). *Encyclopaedia of underwater and maritime archaeology*. British Museum press.

Demerre, I., Gevaert, G., Lenaerts, T., Lettens, J., Pieters, M., & Zeebroek, I. (2006). www.maritieme-archeologie.be: A database for Belgian maritime archaeology. In J. Mees (Ed.), *VLIZ Young Scientists' Day, Brugge, Belgium 31 March 2006: Book of abstracts* (pp. 30–31). Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ). <https://www.vliz.be/imisdocs/publications/ocrd/229361.pdf>

Desroches, J.-P. (2001). The maritime trade routes gallery in the Musée Guimet. *Orientations*, 32(1), 64–67.

Devendra, S. (2002). Dutch Shipwrecks in Galle: The Avondster Project. In S. Kelegama & R. Madawela (Eds.), *400 Years of Dutch-Sri Lanka Relations, 1602-2002*. Institute of Policy Studies of Sri Lanka.

Devendra, S., & Muthucumarana, R. (2015). Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka: Twenty five years old and a new beginning. In S. Tripathi (Ed.), *Shipwrecks Around the World: revelations of the past* (pp. 381–424). Delta Book World.

De Vries, G., & Hall, J. (2001). *The Muzzle Loading Cannon of South Africa: A technical study*. Cannon Association of South Africa.

Diessen, R. van, & Nelemans, B. (2008). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. IV. Ceylon* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.

Digitisation of Dutch Landownership Documents Finished. (n.d.). DutchCulture. Retrieved 6 September 2024, from <https://dutchculture.nl/digitisation-dutch-landownership-documents-finished>

Dobbs, C. T. C., & Price, R. A. (1991). The Kennemerland site. An Interim Report. The sixth and seventh seasons, 1984 & 1987, and the identification of five golf clubs. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 20(2), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1991.tb00305.x>

Doe, F. van der, Loo, I. J. van, & Schwartz, J. H. F. (Eds.). (2001). *Archiefstukken over de VOC in het Zeeuws Archief (GIDS23)*. Zeeuws Archief. <https://www.zeeuwsarchief.nl/zoekgids/archiefstukken-over-de-voc-in-het-zeeuws-archief/>

Duivenvoorde, W. van. (2008). Appendix C: Bibliography for Identified Dutch Shipwreck Sites. *The Batavia Shipwreck: An archaeological study of an early seventeenth-century Dutch East Indiaman* (pp. 516-557). [Doctor of Philosophy, Texas A&M University]. <https://hdl.handle.net/1969.1/ETD-TAMU-2872>

Duivenvoorde, W. Van. (2015). *Dutch East India Company (VOC) Shipbuilding: The Archaeological Study of Batavia and Other Seventeenth-Century VOC Ships*. Ed Rachal Series in Nautical Archaeology. College Station: Texas A&M University Press.

Edwards, H. (2000). *Treasures of the deep: The extraordinary life and times of Captain Mike Hatcher*. HarperCollins Publishers.

Esmeraldo, A. M. B. (2021). *A caminho do oriente: Os vestígios do Slot ter Hooge (1724) na dinâmica da navegação da companhia holandesa das índias orientais* [Eastbound: The Remains of the Slot Ter Hooge (1724) Within the Dutch East India Company Navigational Dynamics] [Masters in Archaeology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/caminho-do-oriente-os-vestigios-slot-ter-hooge/docview/3059426500/se-2>

Fernando, M. R. (2005). The Lost Archives of Melaka: Are They Really Lost? *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 78(1 (288)), 1–36. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41493536>

Floore, P. M., & Jayasena, R. M. (Eds.). (2003). Historical Archaeology of Fort Frederik Hendrik, a Dutch East India Company outpost at Mauritius: A report on the 1997-2003 excavation seasons. *Hollandia*, 37. Zaandijk, NL: Hollandia Archeologen. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26506.59841>

Foncin, M., Destombes, M., & La Roncière, M. de. (1963). *Catalogue des cartes nautiques sur vélin conservées au département des Cartes et plans*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France.

- Forster, W. A., & Higgs, K. B. (1973). The Kennemerland, 1971 An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 2(2), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1973.tb00518.x>
- Gallop, A.T. (2006). Malay Documents In The Melaka Records in the British Library. *Itinerario* 30(2), 54-77. doi:10.1017/S0165115300013966
- Gawroński, J., Kist, B., & Stokvis-Van Boetzelaer, O. (1992). *Hollandia compendium: a contribution to the history, archeology, classification and lexicography of a 150 ft. Dutch East Indiaman (1740-1750)*. Rijks Museum; Elsevier.
- Gommans, J., Bes, L., & Kruijtzter, G. (2001). *Dutch sources on South Asia, c. 1600-1825. Volume 1. Bibliography and Archival Guide to the National Archives at the Hague (The Netherlands)*. Manohar Publ.
- Gommans, J. J. L., Bos, J., & Kruijtzter, G. (2010). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. VI. Voore-Indië, Perzië, Arabisch Schiereiland/India, Persia, Arabian Peninsula* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Gommans, J. J. L., & Diessen, R. van. (2010). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. VII. Oost-Azie, Birma tot Japan/East Asia, Burma to Japan* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.
- Green, J. N. (1986). The Survey of the VOC fluit *Risdam* (1727), Malaysia. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 15(2), 93–104.
- Green, J. N. (1989). *The loss of the Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie retourschip Batavia, Western Australia 1629: an excavation report and catalogue of artefacts*. BAR International Series 489. British Archaeological Reports.
- Green, J. N. (1998). *The Australian-Sri Lanka-Netherlands Galle Harbour Project 1992-1998*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology.
- Green, J. N. (2018). *The mystery of the missing VOC shipwreck in the Houtman Abrolhos Islands, Western Australia*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology Special Publication 20. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/zeewij_report_0.pdf
- Green, J. (2020). The Zeewijk Story and the Missing Second Wreck. *Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, 15(4), 333–364. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-020-09268-8>
- Green, J., & Devendra, S. (1993). Interim report on the joint Sri Lanka-Australian maritime archaeology training and research programme, 1992–3. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 22(4), 331–343. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1993.tb00429.x>
- Green, J. N., & Devendra, S. (1994). *Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka: The Galle Harbour Project, 1992*. Archaeology Department of Sri Lanka; Central Cultural Fund; West Australian Maritime Museum; Postgraduate Institute of Archaeology.
- Green, J., Devendra, S., & Parthesius, R. (Eds.). (1998). Sri Lanka Department of Archaeology report on the joint Sri Lanka - Australia - Netherlands Galle Harbour Project 1996 - 1997: archaeology, history, conservation and training. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.04_galle_harbour_project.pdf

Green, J., Gainsford, M., & Stanbury, M. (Eds.). (2004). *Department of Maritime Archaeology, Western Australian Maritime Museum. A compendium of projects, programmes and publications 1971-2003*. Australian National Centre of Excellence for Maritime Archaeology.

https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.09_compendium_0.pdf

Green, J. N., & Gangadharam, E. V. (1985). *The Survey of the V.O.C. Fluit Risdam (1727), Malaysia*. WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports No. 25. WA Museum.

Green, J., Millar, K., & Devendra, S. (1993). *Maritime Archaeology in Sri Lanka, the Galle Harbour Project-1993: an interim report* (No. 65; WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports). WA Museum. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.065_galle_harbour.pdf

Green, J., & Parthesius, R. (1998). *Papers from the Seminar 'Galle—A Port City in History: 15 November 1997, Galle'*. Sri Lankan Department of Archaeology; Australian National Centre for Excellent in Maritime Archaeology; Western Australian Maritime Museum; University of Amsterdam. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.02_galle_a_port_city.pdf

Green, J., & Paterson, A. (Eds.). (2020). *Shipwrecks of the roaring forties: Researching some of Australia's earliest shipwrecks*. UWA Publishing.

Green, J. N., & Zuiderbaan, L. H. (1977). *The loss of the Verenigde oostindische compagnie Jacht Vergulde Draeck, Western Australia 1656: an historical background and excavation report with an appendix on similar loss of the fluit Lastdrager*. British Archaeological Reports 36. British Archaeological Reports.

Griffith, L. & Diane KW. (2014, February 17). Leza Griffith Interviews Diane KW about At World's End. *CFile - Contemporary Ceramic Art + Design*. <https://cfileonline.org/interview-leza-griffith-interviews-diane-kw-worlds-end/>

Henderson, J. (2019). Oceans without History? Marine Cultural Heritage and the Sustainable Development Agenda. *Sustainability* 11(18), 5080, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11185080>.

Hendrich, G. (2017). 'A rich storehouse for research': The historical development of the Western Cape Archives and Records Service. *Southern Journal for Contemporary History*, 42(2), 74–97. <https://doi.org/10.38140/sjch.v42i2.3362>

Hervé, R., Hugonnard-Roche, H., & Pognon, E. (1974). *Catalogue des cartes géographiques sur parchemin conservées au département des Cartes et plans*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France.

Historic Bronze Cannons, Fort Belvoir, VA. (n.d.). EverGreene. Retrieved 9 September 2024, from <https://evergreene.com/projects/bronze-cannon-conservation-fort-belvoir/>

Historic England Research Records: Loosdrecht. (n.d.). Heritage Gateway. https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/Gateway/Results_Single.aspx?uid=22e698c8-4161-45e6-bd74-cee1b93282c4&resourceID=19191

History Trust of South Australia. (2006). Twenty sixth annual report of the History Trust of South Australia for the year ended 30 June 2006 [Annual Report]. History Trust of South Australia. <https://www.history.sa.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/annual-report-2005-06.pdf>

History Trust of South Australia. (2007). Twenty seventh annual report of the History Trust of South Australia for the year ended 30 June 2007 [Annual Report]. History Trust of South Australia. <https://www.history.sa.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/annual-report-2006-07.pdf>

Keijser, L. (2024). *6000 ground truth of VOC and notarial deeds 3.000.000 HTR of VOC, WIC and notarial deeds* (Version 8.1) [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11209325>

Keurs, P. ter (2006) *Indonesia. The Discovery of the Past*. Edited by Endang Sri Hardiati and Pieter ter Keurs. Amsterdam: KIT Publishers.

Kist, J. B. (1975). Iets over een achttiende-eeuwse draaibas. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 23(2), 99–99.

Kist, J. B. (1989). Sifflet van zilver, Nederland(?), vóór 1613. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 37(3), 194–197.

Interesting Relics. The history of the State. Discovery and Explorations. Many Brave Deeds Recalled. (1914, July 7). *The Advertiser*, 15. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article6424240>

Jacobs, Els M. and Nederlands Scheepvaart Museum. *In Pursuit of Pepper and Tea: The Story of the Dutch East India Company*. Zutphen, Amsterdam: Walburg Pers for Nederlands Scheepvaart Museum, 1991.

Jarrige, J.-F. (2001). Activités du musée national des Arts asiatiques—Guimet. *Arts Asiatiques*, 56, 110–128.

Ketelaar, E. (2008) Exploration of the archived world: from De Vlamingh's Plate to digital realitie. *Archives & Manuscripts*, 36(2), 13-33. <https://publications.archivists.org.au/index.php/asa/article/view/9965>.

Klose, J. E. (n.d.) 'The 'Oosterland' (1697), Table Bay, Cape Town, South Africa'. Historical Archaeology Research Group. Cape Town: Department of Archaeology, University of Cape Town [Unpublished catalogue].

Klose, J. (2000). Oriental ceramics retrieved from three Dutch East India Company ships wrecked off the coast of southern Africa: *Oosterland* (1697), *Bennebroek* (1713) and *Brederode* (1785). *Transactions of the Oriental Ceramic Society*, 64, 63–81.

Klose, J. E. (2003) 'The Peter Sacks wreck. Believed to be the 'Bennebroek' (1713). A catalogue of ceramics salvaged from a wreck of the Kieskamma River, South Africa'. Historical Archaeology Research Group. Cape Town: Department of Archaeology, University of Cape Town [Unpublished catalogue, 2003].

Knaap, G. J. (2007). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. II. Java en Madoera/Java and Madura* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.

la Grange, Lesa, Martijn Manders, Briegle Williams, John Gribble and Leon Derksen (2024). *Dutch Shipwrecks in South African Waters: A Brief History of Sites, Stores and Archives* [Unpublished Report].

Larn, R., & Butler, T. (2019, March 13). *Charlestown Shipwreck Museum* [Interview]. Mapping Museum research project, Bishopsgate Institute. <https://www.bishopsgate.org.uk/collections/charlestown-shipwreck-museum>

Latest News. (1891, December 14). *Evening Journal*, 2. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article198425844>

La route des Indes est pavée d'inaccessibles épaves. (2002, August 8). *Le Monde*, 19.

Lee, P., & Wang, N. (2017, January). Port Cities: Multicultural Emporiums of Asia, 1500-1900. *MuseSG*, 9(3). <https://www.roots.gov.sg/stories-landing/stories/port-cities-multicultural-emporiums-of-asia-1500-1900/story>

L'Hour, M. (n.d.). *Le Mauritius, 1609 (Gabon)*. Archéologie Sous-Marine, Ministère de La Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://archeologie.culture.gouv.fr/archeo-sous-marine/fr/le-mauritius1609-gabon>

L'Hour, M. (n.d.). *Le Mauritius, 1609 (Gabon)*. Archéologie Sous-Marine, Ministère de La Culture. Retrieved 14 August 2024, from <https://archeologie.culture.gouv.fr/archeo-sous-marine/fr/le-mauritius1609-gabon>

L'Hour, M., Long, L., & Rieth, É. (1989). *Le 'Mauritius': La mémoire engloutie*. Casterman.

L'Hour, M., Long, L., & Rieth, E. (1990). The wreck of an 'experimental' ship of the 'Oost-Indische Compagnie': The *Mauritius* (1609). *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 19(1), 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1990.tb00235.x>

Lightley, R. A. (1976). 'An 18th Century Dutch East Indiaman, Found at Cape Town, 1971'. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 5(4), 305–16.

Malan, A., & Liebenberg, H. (2020). *Projects to transcribe archival documents: 2001-2020*. Tracing History Trust. <https://sadilar.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Summary-of-THT-projects-1.pdf>

Manders, M. (2006). The In Situ Protection of a Dutch Colonial Vessel in Sri Lankan Waters. In R. Gernier, D. Nutley, & I. Cochran (Eds.), *Underwater Cultural Heritage at Risk: Managing Natural and Human Impacts* (Heritage at Risk Special Edition, pp. 58–60). ICOMOS. <https://www.icomos.org/public/risk/2006/20manders2006an.pdf>

Manders, M., van Dissel, A., Brouwers, W., Fink, M., Spoelstra, J., de Hoop, R., Heijink, M., Lemmers, A., Heitz, A., & de Vroomen, O. (2022). *Wrakkentelling: Een kwantitatief onderzoek naar historische Nederlandse scheepswrakken in de wereld* (Revised). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2022/01/01/wrakkentelling-2022>

Manders, M., & Kuijper, W. (2015). Shipwrecks in Dutch Waters with Botanical Cargo or Victuals. In C. Bakels & H. Kamermans (Eds.), *Excerpta Archaeologica Leidensia* (pp. 141–172). Leiden University.

Marsden, P. (1972a). The wreck of the Dutch East Indiaman *Amsterdam* near Hastings, 1749: An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 1(1), 73–96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1972.tb00677.x>

Marsden, P. (1972b). The Wreck of the Dutch East-Indiaman *Amsterdam*. *The Mariners Mirror*, 58(1), 5–26. <https://snr.org.uk/the-wreck-of-the-dutch-east-indiaman-amsterdam/>

Marsden, P. (1973). The Investigation of the Wreck of the *Amsterdam*. In D. J. Blackman (Ed.), *Marine archaeology: proceedings of the twenty-third symposium of the Colston Research Society held in the University of Bristol, April 4th to 8th, 1971* (pp. 483–492). Butterworths.

Marsden, P. (1974). *The wreck of the Amsterdam*. Hutchinson.

Marsden, P. (1976) 'The Meresteyn, Wrecked in 1702, near Cape Town, South Africa'. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 5(3), 201–19.

Marsden, P. (1978). A reconstruction of the treasure of the *Amsterdam* and the *Hollandia*, and their significance. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 7(2), 133–148.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1978.tb01057.x>

Marsden, P., & Butler, T. (2019, March 15). *Shipwreck Museum* [Interview Transcription]. The Mapping Museum research project, Bishopsgate Institute.
<https://www.bishopsgate.org.uk/collections/shipwreck-museum>

Martin, C. J. M. (1987). Pipes from the Dutch East Indiaman *Kennemerland*, 1664. In P. Davey (Ed.), *The Archaeology of the clay tobacco pipe: Vol. 10. Scotland* (pp. 211–224). B.A.R.

Martin, C. & P. Martin. (2018). Record of Work Carried out on the Finds from the Wreck of the Dutch East Indiaman *Kennemerland* (1664), Out Skerries, Shetland. Data Structure Report. Historic Environment Scotland, March 2018 [Unpublished Report].

Martin, P. (2020a, February 18). Shipwrecks in Shetland Part 1. Shetland Museum & Archives.
<https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/blog/shipwrecks-in-shetland>

Martin, P. (2020b, May 4). Shipwrecks in Shetland Part 2. Shetland Museum & Archives.
<https://www.shetlandmuseumandarchives.org.uk/blog/shipwrecks-in-shetland-part-2>

Mather, W. (2022, March). Blood money: the coins of Batavia. *Signals*, 138, 18–25.
<https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.505767704268899>

McCarthy, M., Stanbury, M., & Jones, D. S. (2007). *Voyages of Grand Discovery* (M. McCarthy & V. Northey, Eds.). Western Australian Museum.

Miller, G. L. (1992). The Second Destruction of the *Geldermalsen*. *Historical Archaeology* 26(4), 124–31, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25616201>.

Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries. (2018). *Shipwreck map on Indonesian waters* [Graphic]. Marine Heritage Gallery Jakarta, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia; Google Arts & Culture.
<https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/shipwreck-map-on-indonesian-waters/tgE7tnzFujTEoQ>

Musée national de la marine, & De Thoisy-Dallem, A. (2002). *Trésors d'océans: L'archéologie sous-marine sur la route des Indes*. Musée national de la Marine.

Navarrete Hernández, T. (2014). *A History of Digitization: Dutch Museums*. Univ. of Amsterdam.

New name: Wereldmuseum. (2023, October 4). Wereldmuseum Leiden.
<https://leiden.wereldmuseum.nl/en/about-wereldmuseum-leiden/press/press-releases/new-name>

News. Western Hemisphere, St Helena. (1977). *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 6(3), 257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1977.tb01018.x>

Nierstrasz, C. (2015). *Rivalry for Trade in Tea and Textiles: The English and Dutch East India companies (1700–1800)*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Odegard, E. (2022). Maritime India in Dutch sources: The Dutch East India Company port records of Cochin and Bimilipatnam. *International Journal of Maritime History*, 34(2), 340–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/08438714221098476>

OOI Keat Gin. (2015). Maritime Treasures off Peninsula Malaysia. *Journal of Indo-Pacific Archaeology*, 36, 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.7152/jipa.v36i0.14910>

Ostkamp, S. (2014). The Dutch 17th-century porcelain trade from an archaeological perspective. In J. van Campen & T. M. Eliëns (Eds.), *Chinese and Japanese porcelain for the Dutch Golden Age* (pp. 53–85). Waanders Uitgevers, in collaboration with Rijksmuseum Amsterdam; Gemeentemuseum Den Haag; Groninger Museum; Keramiekmuseum Princessehof.

Out Among the People. (1951, January 24). *The Advertiser*, 4. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article45708741>

Parthesius, R. (2002). Het wrak van VOC-schip Avondster in de haven van Galle (Sri Lanka): Een potentiële bron van kennis over de Europese expansie in Azië. In M. H. Bartels, E. H. P. Cordfunke, & H. Sarfatij (Eds.), *Hollanders uit en thuis: archeologie, geschiedenis en bouwhistorie gedurende de VOC-tijd in de Oost, de West en thuis; cultuurhistorie van de Nederlandse expansie* (pp. 61–70). Verloren.

Parthesius, R. (Ed.). (2007). *Excavation report of the VOC-ship Avondster (1659). The Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman that was wrecked twice in Ceylon*. Centre for International Heritage Activities. <https://mass.cultureelerfgoed.nl/documents/00000041.pdf>

Parthesius, R., & Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten (Centre for International Heritage Activities). (2014). *Inventory and analyses of archival sources in the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives in the Netherlands in order to contribute to possible locations and identification of VOC shipwrecks off the Western Australian Coast* (310; WA Museum, Department of Maritime Archaeology Reports). Western Australian Museum Foundation; Centrum voor Internationale Erfgoedactiviteiten. https://museum.wa.gov.au/maritime-archaeology-db/sites/default/files/no.310_cie_research_report_voc_shipwrecks_off_western_australian_coast_1.pdf

Parthesius, R., Millar, K., Devendra, S., & Green, J. (Eds.). (2003). *Sri Lanka Maritime Archaeological Unit report on the Avondster Project 2001-2002*. Amsterdams Historisch Museum. https://www.maritimeasia.ws/maritimelanka/avondster/Avondster_2001-02.pdf

Parthesius, R., Millar, K., & Jeffery, B. (2005). Preliminary Report on the Excavation of the 17th-Century Anglo-Dutch East-Indiaman Avondster in Bay of Galle, Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 34(2), 216–237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.2005.00056.x>

Pennings, J., & Raben, R. (1992). *Introduction to the Archives of the Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie*. Nationaal Archief. https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/sites/default/files/afbeeldingen/toegangen/NL-HaNA_1.04.02_introduction-VOC.pdf

Persak, E. (2014). A celebration of manuscripts in the Kerry Stokes Collection. *The Australian Library Journal*, 63(1), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049670.2013.872551>

Petram, L., & Van Rossum, M. (2022). Transforming historical research practices – a digital infrastructure for the VOC archives (GLOBALISE). *International Journal of Maritime History*, 34(3), 494–502. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08438714221112873>

Pijl-Ketel, C. L. van der. (1989). Een olifanten-kendi afkomstig uit het vondstcomplex van de Oostindiëvaarder de ‘Witte Leeuw’, China, vóór 1613. *Bulletin van Het Rijksmuseum*, 37(3), 198–200.

Polkinghorne, M. (2023). Michael Abbott and the Southeast Asian Ceramic Archaeology Laboratory at Flinders University. In J. Bennett & R. Kelty (Eds.), *Interwoven journeys: The Michael Abbott collections of Asian art* (pp. 124–129). Art Gallery of South Australia.

Polkinghorne, M., Pearson, N., Van Duivenvoorde, W., Nayati, W., Tahir, Z., Ridwan, N. N. H., Forrest, C., Tan, N. H., Popelka-Filcoff, R., Morton, C., Kowlessar, J., & Staniforth, M. (2024). Reuniting orphaned cargoes: Recovering cultural knowledge from salvaged and dispersed underwater cultural heritage in Southeast Asia. *Marine Policy*, 163, 106074.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106074>

Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1974). The second season of work on the Kennemerland site, 1973 An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 3(2), 257–268.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1974.tb00882.x>

Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1977). The Kennemerland site: The third and fourth seasons 1974 and 1976, An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 6(3), 187–218.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1977.tb01006.x>

Price, R., & Muckelroy, K. (1979). The Kennemerland site: The fifth season, 1978. An interim report. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 8(4), 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1979.tb01137.x>

Price, R., Muckelroy, K., & Willies, L. (1980). The Kennemerland site: *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 9(1), 7–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.1980.tb01266.x>

Reichert, R., Scheijde, A., Wytykowski, P., & Zajder, R. (2018). *Sierra Leone 2014. Final Report of the Flag No. 160 Two Expeditions*. Wyprawy Wrakowe. <https://wyprawywrakowe.pl/en/final-report-of-the-two-sierra-leone-expeditions/>

Rodrigues, J. (2012). Early Looting and Destruction of Australian Shipwreck Sites: Legislation, Education, and an Amnesty for Long-Term Preservation. In P. K. Lazrus & A. W. Barker (Eds.), *All the King's Horses* (pp. 71–90). University Press of Colorado. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jj.3850486.8>

Roever, A. G. de, & Brommer, B. (2008). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. III. Indische Archipel en Oceanië/Malay Archipelago and Oceania* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.

Rønning, B. R. (1974). Myntene fra Akerendam. In L. Petterson & A. Thowsen (Eds.), *Sjøfartshistorisk årbok 1973* (pp. 124–128). Bergens sjøfartsmuseum.

Royal Geographical Society. (1913, June 27). *The Journal*, 2. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article200879144>

Schilder, G. (2010). *Sailing for the East: History & catalogue of manuscript charts on vellum of the Dutch East India Company (VOC), 1602-1799*. Hes & De Graaf.

Schilder, G., Moerman, J., Ormeling, F., Brink, P. van den, & Ferwerda, H. (2006). *Grote atlas van de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie/Comprehensive Atlas of the Dutch United East India Company. I. Atlas Isaak de Graaf/Atlas Amsterdam* (1st ed). Atlas Maior.

Schrire, C. (2014). *Historical Archaeology in South Africa: Material Culture of the Dutch East India Company at the Cape*. Left Coast Press, Inc.

- Schuit, H. G., Bull, D., & Holtrop, M. (2017). *Shared Heritage in Museums in South Africa: Opportunities for Collaboration - Publicatie* (Shared Cultural Heritage). Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2017/01/01/shared-heritage-in-museums-in-south-africa-opportunities-for-collaboration>
- Sharfman, J., Boshoff, J. & Parthesius, R. (2012). Maritime and Underwater Cultural Heritage in South Africa: The Development of Relevant Management Strategies in the Historical Maritime Context of the Southern Tip of Africa. *Journal of Maritime Archaeology* 7, 87–109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-012-9101-1>
- Sténuît, R. (1978, October). The sunken treasure of St. Helena. *National Geographic Magazine*, 154(4), 562–576. National Geographic Virtual Library.
- Stevens, H., & Rijksmuseum. (1998). *Dutch enterprise and the VOC, 1602-1799* (S. Herman, Trans.). Walburg Pers for Stichting Rijksmuseum Amsterdam.
- ‘tahirfarrath’. (2012, May 6). The TEPC Transcription Project. *Cape Malays... and Their Heritage*. <https://toyerfarrath.wordpress.com/2012/05/06/the-tepc-transcription-project/>
- Tirvengadam, D. D. (1983). The *Saint-Géran*: From literary myth to museum object. *Museum International*, 35(1), 54–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0033.1983.tb00426.x>
- Trương P. (2011). Về ba khẩu súng thần công Hà Lan ở Bảo tàng Cổ vật Cung đình Huế/About three Dutch cannons at Huế Royal Antiquities Museum. *Tạp chí Nghiên cứu và Phát triển*, 6(89), 128–138. <https://vjol.info.vn/index.php/ncpt-hue/article/view/5716>
- Van der Pijl–Ketel, C. L., ed. (1982). *The Ceramic Load of the Witte Leeuw (1613)*. Amsterdam: Rijksmuseum.
- Verhoeven, F. R. J. (1964). The Lost Archives of Dutch Malacca 1641-1824. *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 37(2 (206)), 11–27. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41492198>
- Vernon, G. (2001). Who gets the ‘treasure’? The role of the East London Museum in shipwreck salvage with special reference to the *Grosvenor*. *South African Museums Association Bulletin*, 27, 66–67.
- Vries, D. de. (1996). *Uit de kaartenwinkel van de VOC. Catalogus van zeekaarten van de Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie in de Collectie Bodel Nijenhuis*. Alphen aan den Rijn.
- Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1974). Vergulde Draeck. Catalogue of Artifacts. Illustrations. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 1, Western Australian Museum.
- Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. [1974]. Batavia Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 2, Western Australian Museum.
- Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1979). Catalogue of Dutch Relics. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 3, Western Australian Museum.
- Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1982). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 4, Western Australian Museum.
- Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1983). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 5, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (1985). ANCODS Catalogue. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 6, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, Stanbury, M., & Sawday, F. (1991). ANCODS 1991. Report and Catalogue of Artefacts. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 7, Western Australian Museum.

Western Australian Museum, & Stanbury, M. (2002). ANCODS 2002. Report on the Dutch Shipwreck Collections. Special Publication of the Department of Maritime Archaeology 8, Western Australian Museum.

Weber, W. (2006). A Dutchman no longer knows his own past, the 'tVliegende Hart collection therefore seems to have been hidden in the MuZEEum. In M. Pieters, G. Gevaert, J. Mees, & J. Seys (Eds.), *Colloquium: To sea or not to sea—2nd international colloquium on maritime and fluvial archaeology in the southern North Sea area, Brugge (Belgium), 21-23 September 2006: Book of abstracts* (pp. 87–88). Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ). <https://www.vliz.vlaanderen/en/imis>

Werz, B. E. J. S., & Klose, J. E. (1994). Ceramic analysis from the VOC Ship Oosterland (1697). *The South African Journal of Science*, 90(10), 522–526.

Worth, H. (2013). The Duyfken: An exploration of the roles of a replica ship. *The Great Circle: Journal of the Australian Association for Maritime History*, 35(1), 75–95.
<https://doi.org/10.3316/informit.538644489146921>

Zeeuws Museum. (2022). *Zeeuws Museum Collection Evaluation*. Zeeuws Museum.
https://www.zeeuwsmuseum.nl/en/about-the-museum/organisation/what-we-do/cw_engels.pdf

Zilverbaren van de VOC. (n.d.). *Nederlands Zilvermuseum Schoonhoven*. Retrieved September 18, 2024, from <https://zilvermuseum.com/bezoek/zilverbaren-van-de-voc/>

Appendix: List of exhibitions

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
[300th Anniversary of Batavia]	Koloniaal Instituut Amsterdam	1-Jun-1919	1-Jul-1919	Stedelijk Museum, Amsterdam
Prijs der zee. Vondsten uit wrakken van Nederlandse Oost-Indiëvaarders uit de zeventiende en achttiende eeuw in de verzameling van de afdeling Nederlandse Geschiedenis van het Rijksmuseum	Rijksmuseum	6-Feb-80	3-Aug-80	Rijksmuseum
T Vliegt Hart 1729-1735: op zoek naar een gezonken schip	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen	11-Jun-83	11-Sep-83	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen
Schatten van het 'TVliegt Hart	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen	13-Jul-84	29-Sep-84	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen
Shipwreck! discoveries from our earliest shipwrecks 1622-1797	Australian Bicentennial Authority; Museum of Victoria; WA Museum; Queensland Museum	8-Jan-88	Jun-89	WA Museum; South Australian Museum; Museums and Art Galleries of the Northern Territory; Museum of Victoria; Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery; Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, Launceston; Queensland Museum; Australian National Maritime Museum; Maritiem Museum Prins Hendrik (Maritiem Museum Rotterdam)
Terra Australis: the furthest shore	Art Gallery of New South Wales	27-Jul-88	9-Oct-88	Art Gallery of New South Wales
L'exposition Mauritius la mémoire engloutie	Musée national de la Marine	16-Mar-89	11-Sep-89	Musée national de la Marine, Paris
De Zeeuwse VOC boven water, 10 jaar onderzoek naar scheepswrakken	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen	27-Jun-92	27-Sep-92	Stedelijk Museum, Vlissingen
Changing Coastlines: putting Australia on the world map 1493-1993	National Library of Australia	5-Nov-93	1-Aug-94	National Library of Australia; Australian National Maritime Museum; Western Australian Museum

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
La Route des Indes. Les Indes et l'Europe: échanges artistiques et héritage commun 1650-1850	Musée d'Aquitaine; Musée des Arts décoratifs (Bordeaux)	11-Dec-98	14-Mar-99	Musée d'Aquitaine, Musée des Arts décoratifs - Ville de Bordeaux
Commerce and Conquest: the story of the Dutch United East India Company	Australian National Maritime Museum	24-Nov-99	30-Jul-00	Australian National Maritime Museum
Batavia: a magnificent ship, an incredible story	Australian National Maritime Museum	5-Dec-99	19-Mar-01	Australian National Maritime Museum
A Curious Coincidence - Two 17th-century Dutch explorers encounter Australia	Australian National Maritime Museum	30-Aug-00	28-Feb-01	Australian National Maritime Museum
Zeeland en Japan. Eilanden in contact	Zeeuws Archief	18-Sep-00	3-Feb-01	Zeeuws Archief
Malaysian Maritime Archaeology Exhibition	Muzium Negara, Malaysia	15-Nov-01	?	Muzium Negara, Malaysia
Peper en pilaeren: de Verenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie in munten en penningen (1602-1799) [Pepper and pillars: the Dutch East India Company in coins and medals (1602-1799)]	Teylers Museum, Haarlem	10-Dec-01	9-Jun-02	Teylers Museum, Haarlem
Foto's uit verre landen van Ferry Andre de la Porte	Stichting Historisch Onderzoek in Woord en Beeld	12-Jan-02	8-Apr-02	Rijksmuseum
De Kleurrijke Wereld van de VOC (The Colourful World of the VOC)		16-Mar-02	27-Oct-02	Scheepvaartmuseum; Maritiem Museum Rotterdam
Trésors d'océans: l'archéologie sous-marine sur la route des Indes	Musée national de la Marine	22-Jun-02	15-Dec-02	Musée national de la Marine, Port Louis
Scheurboek & Scheepsbeschuit. Leven aan boord van een VOC-schip	Zeeuws Archief	5-Jul-02	11-Jan-03	Zeeuws Archief
Upstream	Stichting Upstream	7-Sep-02	20-Sep-02	Hoorn [14 locations]; Amsterdam [11 locations]
De Nederlandse ontmoeting met Azië, 1600–1950 [The Dutch encounter with Asia, 1600-1950]	Rijksmuseum	12-Oct-02	9-Feb-03	Rijksmuseum

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
Dutch Masters from the collections of the Baroda Museum and Picture Gallery, Vadodara and Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj Vastu Sangrahalaya, Mumbai	Royal Netherlands Embassy; Stichting Restauratie Atelier Limburg (SRAL)	9-Nov-02	6-Jan-03	New Delhi, National Museum; Bangalore, Karnataka Chitrakala Parsshad; Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj Vastu Sangrahalaya
Wrecked! Tragedy and the Southern Seas	South Australian Maritime Museum	24-Mar-05	2-Sep-05	South Australian Maritime Museum; multiple centres (touring)
South Land to New Holland: Dutch charting of Australia 1606-1756	National Library of Australia	2006	N/A	Online Exhibition
First sight: the Dutch mapping of Australia, 1606-1697	State Library of New South Wales	6-Mar-06	4-Jun-06	Picture Gallery, Mitchell Wing, SLNSW
Western Edge	Curtin University, John Curtin Gallery	6-Oct-06	8-Dec-06	John Curtin Gallery
Voyages of Grand Discovery	WA Museum	20-Jul-07	18-Nov-07	WA Maritime Museum
Holland en Japan, 400 jaar handel [Holland and Japan, 400 years of trade]	Rijksmuseum	11-Feb-09	25-May-09	Schiphol Airport
Still Life/Our Life (Zest Festival)	Kalbarri Development Association; Australian Research Centre of Excellence for the History of Emotions	1-Jun-2012	31-Jan-2013	Allen Centre, 70 Grey Street Kalbarri
L'âge d'or des cartes marines: quand l'Europe découvrait le monde	Bibliothèque Nationale de France	23-Oct-12	27-Jan-13	Bibliothèque Nationale de France
Suspended Histories	Museum Van Loon	5-Oct-13	20-Jan-14	Museum Van Loon
Mapping our World: Terra Incognita to Australia	National Library of Australia	7-Nov-13	10-Mar-14	National Library of Australia
Treasure Ships: Art in the Age of Spices	Art Gallery of South Australia; Art Gallery of Western Australia	13-Jun-15	31-Jan-16	Art Gallery of South Australia; Art Gallery of Western Australia
Azië > Amsterdam. Luxe in de Gouden Eeuw	Peabody Essex Museum; Rijksmuseum	17-Oct-15	17-Jan-16	Rijksmuseum
1616. Dirk Hartog	WA Museum	2016	N/A	Online Exhibition

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
Asia in Amsterdam: The Culture of Luxury in the Golden Age	Peabody Essex Museum; Rijksmuseum	27-Feb-16	5-Jun-16	Peabody Essex Museum
Invisible Genres	John Curtin Gallery	22-Sep-16	4-Dec-16	John Curtin Gallery
Mapping Australia	AAMU Museum for Contemporary Aboriginal Art in Utrecht	4-Oct-16	15-Jan-17	AAMU Museum, Utrecht
Salt Water Mapping	Berndt Museum, University of Western Australia	8-Oct-16	10-Dec-16	Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery
Travellers and Traders in the Indian Ocean World	WA Museum; British Museum	31-Oct-16	23-Apr-17	WA Maritime Museum
Dutch Diaspora: The Orphans of the Dutch East India Company	Curtin University	Nov-16	Feb-17	Museum of Geraldton, WA Museum
Port Cities: Multicultural Emporiums of Asia, 1500-1900	Asian Civilisations Museum	4-Nov-16	19-Feb-17	Asian Civilizations Museum
Through Tasman's Eyes		6-Dec-16	6-Feb-17	Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery
Early Dutch Explorers	Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands; Dutch Culture; Shared Cultural Heritage program; Allport Bequest	9-Feb-17	5-Mar-17	Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery
De Wereld van de VOC [The World of the VOC]	Nationaal Archief	24-Feb-17	24-Jun-18	Nationaal Archief
Blaeu's wereld in kaart: meestercartograaf in de Gouden Eeuw	Scheepvaartmuseum	14-Apr-17	30-Sep-18	Scheepvaartmuseum
Batavia. Giving Voice to the Voiceless.	University of Western Australia; Edith Cowan University	7-Oct-17	9-Mar-18	Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery; Geraldton Regional Art Gallery
How we ditched the Dutch: De kaping van de laatste VOC-vloot	Maritime Museum Rotterdam	7-Oct-17	3-Jun-18	Maritime Museum Rotterdam

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
Abel Tasman-Welkom aan boord!	Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands; Dutch Culture; Shared Cultural Heritage program; Allport Bequest	24-Nov-17	18-Feb-18	Noordelijk Scheepvaartmuseum
Abel Tasman: an expedition to the unknown South Land	Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands; Dutch Culture; Shared Cultural Heritage program; Allport Bequest	2-Dec-17	4-Dec-17	Maritime Museum in Auckland
Submerged. Stories of Australia's shipwrecks	Australian National Maritime Museum; Australian Maritime Museums Council	1-Feb-18	1-Feb-20	Multiple
VOC-handel met Ceylon	Zeeuws Archief	12-Feb-18	23-May-20	Zeeuws Archief
The VOC in Sri Lanka: Forts in the land of elephants and cinnamon	Dutch Fortress Museum Naarden	19-May-18	18-Nov-18	Dutch Fortress Museum Naarden
De Rooswijk, een virtuele tentoonstelling [The Rooswijk, a virtual exhibition]	Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed; Huygens Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis	18-Jun-18	N/A	Online Exhibition
Expedition to Asia. The Prominent Exchanges between East and West in the 17th Century	National Palace Museum, Taiwan	20-Dec-18	10-Mar-19	National Palace Museum, Taiwan
Di Sản Từ Những Con Tàu Cổ [Maritime Secrets from Ancient Shipwrecks]	Vietnam National Museum of History	18-Jan-19	18-May-19	Vietnam National Museum of History
Cartografie & Curiosa [Maps and Marvels]	Scheepvaartmuseum	10-May-19	30-Dec-25	Scheepvaartmuseum
Belayi – Open Your Eyes!	Batavia Coast Maritime Heritage Association	29-Jul-19	9-Aug-19	Queens Park Theatre, Geraldton

Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
Gezonken Schatten: geheimen van de Maritieme Zijderoute [Sunken Treasures: secrets of the maritime silk road]	Keramiek Museum Princessehof	7-Sep-19	30-Aug-20	Keramiek Museum Princessehof
De Houtman, best fout man? 400 jaar De Houtmaneilanden [De Houtman, pretty bad man? 400 years of the Houtman Islands]	Stedelijk Museum, Alkmaar	9-Nov-19	1-Mar-20	Stedelijk Museum, Alkmaar
A sorrowful act: the wreck of the Zeewijk	Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery	29-Aug-20	5-Dec-20	Lawrence Wilson Art Gallery
Wind in de zeilen [Wind in the sails]	Maritiem Muzeum Zeeland	7-Sep-20	30-Jun-21	Maritiem Muzeum Zeeland
VOC Data Experience	Studio Bertels; Huygens ING	16-Apr-21	30-Sep-21	Het Scheepvaartmuseum
Slavery	Rijksmuseum	5-Jun-21	29-Aug-21	Rijksmuseum
Enchanting Expeditions: Chinese Trade Porcelains across the Globe	Art Museum, Chinese University of Hong Kong	25-Sep-21	6-Jul-22	Art Museum, Chinese University of Hong Kong
VOC Data Experience	Studio Bertels; Huygens ING	Dec-21	?	Maritiem Museum Rotterdam
Wam Wardanup: Strangers on the Shore	Janet Holmes à Court; PerthFest	12-Feb-22	12-Mar-22	No. 10 Gallery, West Perth
Onze Koloniale Erfenis [Our Colonial Inheritance]	Wereld Museum (Tropenmuseum)	23-Jun-22	?	Wereld Museum, Amsterdam
Brickwrecks: Sunken ships in LEGO® Bricks	Australian National Maritime Museum; WA Museum	27-Jun-22	18-Sep-23	WA Maritime Museum; WA Museum Geraldton; Australian National Maritime Museum
Batavia 1629 National Heritage Listed Place Guide	WA Museum	2-Sep-22	N/A	Online Exhibition
VOC Data Experience	Studio Bertels; Huygens ING	10-Feb-23	22-Oct-23	Nationaal Archief
Op de kaart [On the Map]	Nationaal Archief	10-Feb-23	22-Oct-23	Nationaal Archief
Boundless: A Maritime Perspective of east-west cultural exchange in the 16th Century	National Palace Museum, Taiwan	23-Nov-23	18-Feb-24	National Palace Museum, Taiwan
Mooi Goed! Spullen Boven Water [Beautifully Good! Stuff above water]	Batavialand	8-Dec-23	12-May-24	Museum Batavialand

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Exhibition	Organisation	Date start	Date end	Venue
Transcending 1624: Taiwan and the World [跨·1624 : 世界島臺灣]	National Museum of Taiwan History; Kobe City Museum	1-Feb-24	30-Jun-24	National Museum of Taiwan History
Voyages of Discovery	State Library of New South Wales	?	N/A	Online Exhibition
Pala – Nutmeg Tales of Banda	Westfries Museum	?	N/A	Online Exhibition